

Model Order Reduction for Parametric High Dimensional Models in the Analysis of Financial Risk

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To my parents and my brother

Abstract

Financial risk analysis is an excellent way of identifying and assessing the factors that may negatively affect investments. Investors use it to determine whether to undertake a particular investment, the plausible return and how to mitigate an activity's potential losses. However, the risk analysis of financial instruments often requires the valuation of such instruments under a wide range of future market scenarios, demanding efficient algorithms. In this thesis, the financial instruments are evaluated via the dynamics of short-rate models, based on the convection-diffusion-reaction partial differential equations (PDEs). These models are calibrated based on several thousand simulated yield curves that serve as market scenarios, which generate a high dimensional parameter space. In short, to perform the risk analysis, the financial model is needed to be solved for such a high dimensional parameter space, which requires efficient algorithms.

Thus, this thesis presents a model order reduction (MOR) approach based on the proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) method to generate small model approximations for high dimensional parametric PDEs. The small model approximation called the reduced model is obtained by projecting the high dimensional model onto some reduced basis. The POD method relies on the method of snapshots in order to obtain the reduced basis. The snapshots are obtained by solving the full model generated by discretizing a PDE for some training parameters, which are further combined into a single matrix known as the snapshot matrix. Subsequently, the reduced basis is obtained by computing the truncated singular value decomposition (SVD) of the snapshot matrix.

In this work, the training parameters are chosen based on greedy sampling approaches. We propose an adaptive greedy sampling approach that utilizes an optimized search based on surrogate modeling for the selection of the training parameter set. This approach avoids the cost of computing the error estimator for each parameter within the parameter space and instead uses a surrogate model to locate the training parameter set. The best suitable reduced model is procured such that the total error is less than the user-defined tolerance. The three significant numerical errors considered are the discretization error associated with the full model, the model order reduction error, and the parameter sampling error.

This new technique is analyzed, implemented, and tested on industrial data of two financial instruments: A floater with caps and floors under the one-factor Hull-White model and a

puttable steepener solved using the two-factor Hull-White model. The results illustrate that the reduced model approach works well for short-rate models and show potential applications in historical or Monte-Carlo value-at-risk calculations.

Zusammenfassung

Die finanzielle Risikoanalyse ist ein hervorragendes Mittel, um die Faktoren zu ermitteln und zu bewerten, die sich negativ auf Investitionen auswirken können. Investoren nutzen sie, um zu entscheiden, ob eine bestimmte Investition getätigt werden soll, welche Rendite zu erwarten ist und wie die potenziellen Verluste einer Aktivität gemindert werden können. Die Risikoanalyse von Finanzinstrumenten erfordert jedoch häufig die Bewertung solcher Instrumente unter einer Vielzahl von zukünftigen Marktszenarien, was effiziente Algorithmen erfordert. In dieser Arbeit werden die Finanzinstrumente über die Dynamik von short-rate Modellen, die auf Konvektions-Diffusions-Reaktion partiellen Differentialgleichungen (PDEs) beruhen. Diese Modelle werden auf der Grundlage von mehreren tausend simulierten Zinskurven kalibriert, die als Marktszenarien dienen und einen hochdimensionalen Parameterraum erzeugen. Kurz gesagt, um die Risikoanalyse durchzuführen, muss das Finanzmodell für einen solchen hochdimensionalen Parameterraum gelöst werden, was effiziente Algorithmen erfordert.

Daher wird in dieser Dissertation ein Ansatz zur Modellreduktion (MOR) vorgestellt, der auf der Methode der proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) basiert, um kleine Modellapproximationen für die hochdimensionalen parametrischen PDEs zu erzeugen. Die kleine Modellapproximation, das so genannte reduzierte Modell, erhält man durch Projektion des hochdimensionalen Modells auf eine reduzierte Basis. Die POD-Methode stützt sich auf die Methode der Snapshots, um die reduzierte Basis zu erhalten. Zunächst werden die Snapshots durch die Lösung des full Modells erhalten, das durch Diskretisierung einer PDE für einige Trainingsparameter erzeugt wird, die dann zu einer einzigen Matrix, der Snapshot-Matrix, zusammengefasst werden. Anschließend wird die reduzierte Basis durch Berechnung der verkürzten Singulärwertzerlegung (SVD) der Snapshot-Matrix ermittelt.

In dieser Studie werden die Trainingsparameter auf der Grundlage von Greedy-Sampling-Methoden ausgewählt. Wir schlagen einen adaptiven Greedy-Sampling-Algorithmus vor, der eine optimierte Suche auf der Grundlage der Surrogat-Modellierung für die Auswahl des Trainingsparametersatzes verwendet. Diese Methode umgeht die Kosten für die Berechnung des Fehlerschätzers für jeden Parameter im Parameterraum und verwendet stattdessen ein Ersatzmodell, um den Trainingsparametersatz zu finden. Das am besten geeignete reduzierte Modell ist so konstruiert, dass der totale Fehler kleiner ist als die vom Benutzer definierte Toleranz. Die drei wesentlichen numerischen Fehler, die berücksichtigt werden, sind der Diskretisierungs-

fehler des vollen Modells, der fehler bei der Reduzierung der Modellordnung und der fehler bei der Parameterauswahl.

Diese neue Technik wird analysiert, implementiert und anhand von Industriedaten für zwei Finanzinstrumente getestet: Ein Floater with Caps und Floors nach dem one-factor Hull-White-Model und ein Puttable Steepener nach dem two-factor Hull-White-Model. Die Resultate illustrieren, dass der Ansatz des reduzierte Modells für short-rate Modelle gut funktioniert und zeigen mögliche Anwendungen in historischen oder Monte-Carlo Value-at-Risk Berechnungen.

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Scope of the Study	6
1.2	Thesis Outline	7
1.3	PRIIPs and European Regulations	8
2	Valuation Functions	13
2.1	Short-Rate Models	13
2.1.1	Vasicek Model and Cox-Ingersoll-Ross Model	15
2.1.2	Hull-White model	16
2.1.3	Black-Karasinski Model	19
2.1.4	Two-Factor Hull-White Model	19
2.2	Yield Curve Simulation	21
2.3	Calibration of the Parameter $a(t)$	24
2.4	Calibration of the Parameter $\theta(t)$	26
3	Numerical Methods	29
3.1	Finite Difference Method	29
3.1.1	Spatial Discretization	29
3.1.2	Time Discretization	30
3.1.3	Finite Difference Method for the one-factor Hull-White Model	31
3.2	Finite Element Method	34
3.2.1	Weak Form	34
3.2.2	Shape Functions	37
4	Model Order Reduction	41
4.1	Greedy Sampling	44
4.1.1	Drawbacks	47
4.1.2	Computational Cost	48
4.2	Adaptive Greedy Sampling Method	48
4.2.1	Surrogate Modeling	49

4.2.2	Adaptive Greedy Sampling Algorithm	53
4.2.3	Computational Cost	57
5	Error Analysis	59
5.1	Discretization of a PDE	62
5.1.1	Time Discretization	62
5.1.2	Spatial Discretization	64
5.2	Model Order Reduction Error	70
5.3	Sampling Error	79
5.4	Sensitivity Analysis	83
5.5	Model Hierarchy: Stopping Criteria	88
6	Applications and Results	91
6.1	Floater with Caps and Floors	91
6.1.1	Model Order Reduction	94
6.1.2	Floater Performance Scenario Values	104
6.2	Callable/Puttable Steepener	106
6.2.1	Model Order Reduction	109
6.2.2	Steepener Performance Scenario Values	118
6.3	Sensitivity Analysis	119
7	Conclusion and Outlook	121
7.1	Outlook	122
A	List of Essential Terms	135

List of Figures

1.1	The calculation steps for category three instruments.	11
3.1	Linear triangular element with i, j, k nodes	38
4.1	Use of a surrogate model to replace costly original model simulations: $--\rightarrow$: Expensive, since it involves many simulations of an original model. \rightarrow : Cheap, since training and employing a surrogate model.	49
5.1	A model hierarchy showing errors arising in the analysis of the mathematical model.	60
5.2	Mesh refinement method	65
5.3	Model hierarchy for model order reduction	89
6.1	10 000 simulated yield curves obtained by bootstrapping after five years (left) and ten years (right) in the future for the floater instrument.	92
6.2	The discretization error estimator and the grid convergence index vs the full model size for the floater instrument.	94
6.3	Evolution of maximal and average residuals in each iteration of classical greedy algorithm for the floater instrument.	95
6.4	Evolution of maximal and average residuals with varying cardinality of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ of classical greedy algorithm for the floater instrument.	95
6.5	Floater instrument: Classical Greedy Sampling: Projection error associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition (left), and a plot of the relative error between the full model and the reduced model obtained using the classical greedy sampling approach (right).	96
6.6	Drawback of the classical greedy sampling for the floater instrument.	97
6.7	Floater instrument: Principal component analysis error (left) and predicted values obtained using the surrogate model for an error estimator vs actual values (right).	98
6.8	Maximal and average residuals per iteration of adaptive greedy algorithm for the floater instrument.	99

6.9	Floater instrument: Adaptive Greedy Sampling: Projection error associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition (left), and a plot of the relative error between the full model and the reduced model obtained using adaptive greedy sampling (right).	99
6.10	Comparison of classical (CG) and adaptive (AG) greedy sampling approach for the floater instrument.	100
6.11	An approximate model for the relative error to monitor the convergence of the adaptive greedy algorithm for the floater instrument.	101
6.12	Randomization effect on classical and adaptive greedy sampling approaches for the floater instrument.	101
6.13	A model hierarchy showing errors arising in the analysis of the mathematical model for the floater instrument.	102
6.14	Distribution of floater values after five years and ten years.	105
6.15	10 000 simulated yield curves obtained by bootstrapping after five years and ten years in the future for the steepener instrument.	107
6.16	The discretization error estimator and the grid convergence index (5.22) vs the full model size for the steepener instrument.	108
6.17	Evolution of maximum and average residuals with each iteration of the classical greedy algorithm for the steepener instrument.	109
6.18	Steepener instrument: Classical Greedy Sampling: Projection error associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition (left). A plot of the relative error between the full model and the reduced model obtained using the classical greedy sampling approach (right).	110
6.19	Drawback of the classical greedy (CG) sampling approach for the steepener instrument.	110
6.20	Steepener instrument: Principal component analysis error (left) and predicted values obtained using the surrogate model for an error estimator vs actual values (right).	111
6.21	Evolution of maximum and average residuals with each iteration of the adaptive greedy algorithm for the steepener instrument.	112
6.22	Steepener instrument: Adaptive Greedy Sampling: Projection error associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition (left), and a plot of the relative error between the full model and the reduced model obtained using adaptive greedy sampling approach (right).	113
6.23	Comparison of the classical greedy (CG) approach vs adaptive greedy (AG) approach for the steepener instrument.	113
6.24	The error model $\bar{\epsilon}_{RM}$ based on the available error set E_p for four different greedy iterations for the steepener instrument.	114

6.25	Effect of random sampling on classical and adaptive greedy sampling for the steeper instrument.	115
6.26	A model hierarchy showing errors arising in the analysis of the mathematical model for the steeper instrument.	116
6.27	Distribution of 10 000 results for the steeper instrument after five years (left) and ten years (right).	118

List of Tables

1.1	Market risk classification	10
4.1	List of symbols used in Algorithm 4 and 5	55
6.1	Numerical Example of a floater with caps and floors.	92
6.2	Mean squared error of prediction	98
6.3	Computing time/ reduction time (T_Q) to generate projection subspace for the floater instrument.	103
6.4	Evaluation time for the floater instrument.	104
6.5	Computational time comparison: SVD vs Randomized SVD for the floater instrument.	104
6.6	Results for a floater with cap and floor.	105
6.7	Numerical Example of a puttable Steepener.	106
6.8	Mean squared error of prediction for the steepener instrument	111
6.9	Computing time/ reduction time (T_Q) to generate a reduced basis for the steepener instrument.	116
6.10	Evaluation time for the steepener instrument.	117
6.11	Computational time comparison: SVD vs Randomized SVD for the steepener instrument.	117
6.12	Results for the puttable steepener.	118
6.13	Sensitivity analysis: local and global sensitivity indices (Floater instrument).	119
6.14	Sensitivity analysis: local and global sensitivity indices (Steepener instrument).	119

Chapter 1

Introduction

Investors use risk analysis to determine whether to undertake a particular venture, the plausible return and how to mitigate an activity's potential losses. It is essential to be aware of the financial risk associated with an invested product. The risk analysis of financial instruments often requires the valuation of such instruments under a wide range of future market scenarios. The market scenarios (e.g., values of equity prices, stock indices, foreign exchange rates, interest rates) are then input parameters in a valuation function that delivers the fair value of such financial instruments. Examples of such risk analysis tasks are the calculation of Value at Risk (VaR) or the expected shortfall to estimate worst-case scenarios of financial holdings [1, 66, 119]. VaR is defined as the maximum amount of loss over a given holding period for a given level of confidence. For example, if 95% one week VaR is € 100, then there is 95% confidence that over a week, the investment will not lose more than € 100. On the other hand, the expected shortfall, also known as the conditional Value at Risk (CVaR), is the expected value that describes the average of losses when the value falls below VaR. The expected shortfall can be calculated as the expected value of all possible losses exceeding VaR. In short, VaR represents a worst-case loss, while CVaR is the expected loss if that worst-case threshold is ever crossed. Researchers and market practitioners have paid more attention to Value at Risk in analyzing the market risk in recent years. The three different VaR approaches widely used are the parametric VaR, the historical VaR, and the Monte Carlo VaR.

1. The parametric VaR assumes some probability distribution for underlying risk factors (e.g., equity prices or processes of stock indices). The future parametric values of a financial instrument can then be estimated via its sensitivities with respect to the underlying risk factors. Assuming these values follow the same distribution, we can calculate the maximum loss within the specified confidence level. Formally, VaR can be calculated using the formula, $\text{VaR} = \sigma N^{-1}(x)$, where σ is the standard deviation of the instrument prices, x is the confidence level, and N is the standard normal cumulative distribution. It is a linear approach, as it is assumed that instrument prices change

linearly with respect to changes in the risk factors. Therefore, it is not capable of capturing nonlinear effects, such as nonlinear payoffs or calls.

2. The historical VaR approach applies historic day-to-day changes of the underlying prices to the current status (today) to obtain an empiric distribution of tomorrow's underlying prices. The method calculates the historical changes in the given risk factors based on their time series. Historical scenarios s_i are then generated by applying these historical changes to today's risk factors. The underlying instrument is valued under every historical scenario using an appropriate valuation function. The differences between the historical scenario values $V(s_i)$ and today's value $V(t_0)$ are then calculated and sorted into scenario delta values $\Delta V_i = V(s_i) - V(t_0)$. The $x\%$ historical VaR is then given as the $(100 - x)\%$ quantile of the sorted scenario delta values. The expected shortfall can easily be calculated by averaging over the values below the VaR quantile. If a historical data range of one year (approx. 250 business days) is used, then the value of the financial instrument has to be calculated 250 times.
3. Monte Carlo VaR applies a Monte Carlo simulation to obtain a wide range of underlying values. The approach uses some multivariate distribution function, i.e., a copula, to generate the market scenarios. A typical setup would be to assume Gaussian distributions for the marginal distributions and to use a Gaussian copula. Once the market scenarios are available, the Monte Carlo method calculates the VaR in a similar sense as the historical VaR. Again, to calculate the values of the instrument, a valuation function has to be used. To obtain reasonably accurate results, Monte Carlo VaR typically needs thousands or tens of thousands of valuations.

For both historical and Monte Carlo VaR calculations, one has to solve the valuation function under many market scenarios, which is a computationally costly task and demands efficient algorithms.

Another important risk assessment task is the credit and debt value adjustments (CVA, DVA). CVA are estimates of possible losses when a counterparty in a financial *portfolio* defaults [46]. The difference between the credit-risk-free portfolio value and the true portfolio value in the presence of credit risk depends on the future liabilities of the counterparty and its default risk. For the generation of exposure scenarios, Monte Carlo simulation is the method of choice. Frequently, the positions between two market participants (often banks) contain many different risk factors (e.g., instruments in different currencies). In such cases, exposure calculation is a high-dimensional problem.

Packaged retail and insurance-based investment products (PRIIPs) are financial instruments that are *packaged* and offered to retail investors. We will come back to the definition of *packaged* and their categorization in Section 1.3. In order to make PRIIPs from different manufacturers more comparable concerning their risks and returns, the European regula-

tion (EU) 1286/2014 requires manufacturers of PRIIPs to supply key information documents (KIDs) to possible retail investors that are easy to read and to understand [33]. The commission delegated regulation (EU) 2017/653 formulates the details of how the risk and the possible returns of a PRIIP have to be calculated [34]. There are four different categories of PRIIPs. In this work, we concentrate on Category 3 instruments, for which at least 10 000 market data scenarios have to be generated, and the PRIIP has to be valued under these scenarios. While the time horizon (at which the distribution of future values is to be simulated) of VaR calculations is typically quite short (one business day or ten business days, sometimes until the end of the fiscal quarter), the time horizon of PRIIPs is the *recommended holding period* (RHP) of the PRIIP. This is typically in the range of years or even (e.g., in the case of structured life insurance contracts) decades. As a consequence, the calculation of PRIIPs key figures is computationally much more challenging than a VaR calculation of other instruments. The commission delegated regulation for PRIIPs does not prescribe which valuation functions should be used. Therefore, one can use any appropriate valuation function, namely plain discounting cash flows, closed-form solutions of Black-Scholes or Black 76 [53], numerical schemes for finance-related partial differential equations (PDEs) [1], or Monte Carlo and Quasi Monte Carlo Schemes for stochastic differential equations arising from e.g., Libor market models [72, 90]. When a financial instrument is equipped with optionalities like callabilities (for the issuer) or putabilities (for the investor) or when the instrument is path-dependent (e.g., autocallable instruments, target redemption notes), the valuation functions are more complex PDEs [17, 36, 49].

In this thesis, the financial instruments are evaluated via the dynamics of short-rate models [18], based on convection-diffusion-reaction partial differential equations. The choice of the short-rate model depends on the underlying financial instrument. Some of the prominent financial models are the one-factor Hull-White model [56], the shifted Black-Karasinski model [12], and the two-factor Hull-White model [59]. These models are calibrated based on market data like *yield curves* that generate a high dimensional parameter space [18]. In short, to perform the risk analysis, the financial model needs to be solved for such a high dimensional parameter space, and this requires efficient algorithms. For instruments with high complexity and long-time horizons, computing times of minutes for a single valuation are not unusual.

Thus, in this work, we implement a parametric model order reduction (MOR) approach to speed up these computationally costly simulations. MOR has become a popular tool in numerical analysis. However, it is less familiar in computational finance. There are few studies that apply MOR to solve computationally expensive problems in finance [20, 80, 99, 100]. Most of these studies use MOR to solve either option pricing models or speed up financial model calibrations. Nonetheless, the implemented model order reduction is an innovative and compelling approach for financial risk analysis that could potentially be used for historical and Monte Carlo value at risk calculations. We aim to design a model order reduction framework

as a black box as it may happen that the user does not have enough knowledge or background about these methods. Thus, the user prefers an automatic approach that produces the desired output with given inputs. We establish a parametric model order reduction approach based on a variant of the proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) approach, which significantly reduces the overall computation time [8, 10, 23]; (the POD method is also known as the Karhunen-Loève decomposition [44] or principal component analysis (PCA) [64] in statistics). This linear MOR approach used to solve both linear and nonlinear problems is computationally feasible [45] as it determines low dimensional linear (or affine) subspaces [89, 117] via a truncated singular value decomposition (SVD) of a snapshot matrix [109], that is computed by simulating the high dimensional parametric model for a small number of pre-selected training parameter values. The question of how to select these parameters is often the most challenging part of the process. Typically, one uses a fixed or uniform sampling [73], but this may neglect vital regions in the case of a high dimensional parameter space.

We present a greedy sampling algorithm to determine the best suitable parameter set, see also [4, 47, 85]. The basic idea is to select the parameters at which the error between the reduced and the high dimensional model is maximal. We compute the snapshots using these parameters and thus obtain the best suitable reduced basis to generate a fairly accurate reduced model. Since the calculation of the relative error between the full and reduced model is expensive, we also develop error estimators similar to [19, 116]. The classical greedy sampling algorithm then picks optimal parameters which yield the highest values for the error estimator. However, it is not computationally feasible to compute an error estimator for the entire parameter space. The error estimator is based on the norm of the residual, which scales with the size of the full model. This problem forces us to select a pre-defined parameter set as a subset of the high dimensional parameter space to train the greedy sampling algorithm. We usually select this pre-defined subset randomly. However, a random selection may neglect the crucial parameters within the parameter space. Thus, to surmount this problem, we constructed and implemented an adaptive greedy sampling approach. We locate the parameters using an adaptive method by constructing a surrogate model for the error estimator [4, 85]. The use of the surrogate model avoids the expensive computation of the error estimator over the entire parameter space. We construct this surrogate model based on the principal component regression (PCR) technique [70].

This thesis also provides a detailed error analysis of the developed model order reduction framework. We have considered the hierarchical framework to perform the error analysis that starts by considering the solution of the partial differential equation as the true solution. We then discretize the underlying PDE to generate the full model and project it on a reduced basis to obtain the reduced model. Each stage described here is associated with some numerical error. Three major numerical errors considered are the discretization error associated with the full model obtained by discretizing the PDE, the model order reduction error, and the

sampling error associated with the sampling algorithms. The total error associated with the model order reduction framework is the sum of these three significant errors. Our approach aims to minimize the total error such that it is less than the user-defined tolerance generating the suitable reduced model. In this work, we define the discretization error estimator based on estimating the differential equation’s exact solution, which is higher-order accurate than the underlying numerical solution [97]. The method is known as Richardson extrapolation [93], which uses a sequence of solutions to estimate the discretization error and can be applied to almost any type of discretization approach as well as to both local and global quantities [98]. The discretization error is mainly governed by the choice of the grid size. We present an approach to select the optimal grid size based on the developed error estimator. The model order reduction is composed of the projection error associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition approach and how well the reduced model approximates the full model [68]. Both the projection error and the reduced model error depend on the dimension of a reduced basis. We present an algorithm to select an optimal reduced dimension that minimizes the projection error and the reduced model error. To obtain a reduced basis, we have to compute a singular value decomposition of the snapshot matrix, which is a computationally costly task. Recent research has shown that the randomized singular value decomposition is noticeably faster than the basic SVD for some applications [77, 84, 113]. Thus, we use the randomized truncated singular value decomposition developed by Halko et al., [50], in the adaptive greedy sampling approach to determine the reduced basis. The sampling algorithm used to obtain the training parameters introduces the sampling error. In the adaptive greedy sampling, the projection error due to the principal component analysis and the prediction error of the surrogate model make the total sampling error. We develop the projection error due to the PCA in a similar sense to the projection error of the POD, while the mean square error of prediction is used to assess the quality of the surrogate model.

We have performed a sensitivity analysis for these errors to know the relative contribution of each error to the total error [102]. It provides useful insight into which numerical error contributes most to the variability of the model output [24]. Sensitivity analysis assists in improving the model output by selecting the proper grid size, the adequate reduced dimension, and best training parameters. It also helps to allocate computational resources efficiently as more computational effort could be spent on the most sensitive parameters.

To summarize, this thesis presents an approach to select the most prominent parameters (or scenarios) for which we solve the high dimensional model to obtain a reduced model. Thus, instead of performing thousands of costly simulations, we perform few expensive computations and simulate the remaining scenarios with the help of the reduced model economically. In this thesis, we perform risk analysis and test our algorithms for different PRIIPs. We have selected PRIIPs as test examples for a multitude of reasons. The idea that different instruments can be compared is a correct and important step in the direction of investor

protection and cost transparency. The PRIIPs regulation improves this transparency and helps investors assess the value for money of their investments. However, the preparation of a key information document that informs investors about risks and possible returns is an enormously time-consuming task. The regulation demands to perform several thousand simulations of the underlying instrument. For long-term structured interest rate instruments (maturity greater than five years), 60 000 computations must be carried out to determine the performance scenarios. Assuming a single valuation takes only one second, the whole computation will take almost a day. Therefore, it is interesting to test the developed model order reduction framework against such a challenging problem. Nevertheless, our approach can be extended to the more general case of the risk analysis. The developed techniques are analyzed, implemented, and tested on industrial data of different financial instruments. We have solved a numerical example of a *floaters* with *caps* and *floors* under the one-factor Hull-White model. To test algorithms for more complicated instruments, we have considered a numerical example of a *callable/puttable steepener*. For such instruments, we need to consider a multi-factor model. We solve a numerical example of the puttable steepener with caps and floors using the two-factor Hull-White model. The results illustrate that the model order reduction approach provides a significant speedup with excellent accuracy over the full model approach, demonstrating its potential applications in the historical or Monte Carlo Value at Risk calculations.

1.1 Scope of the Study

Based on the above discussion, the scope of this dissertation can be summarized as follows. The study will investigate the parametric model order reduction approach for the simulation of parametric interest rate models in financial risk analysis. Also, we will attempt to design the developed MOR framework as a black box in order to make it user-friendly.

We aim to provide a generalized but cost-efficient method for parameter selection to generate the optimal reduced basis. The method will generate reduced models which are easy and inexpensive to use and consequently can be implemented to perform a risk analysis of an underlying financial instrument. In order to validate the proposed MOR framework, we have used PRIIPs as test examples since the calculations of their key figures are much more challenging than VaR calculations of some other instruments. The scope of the dissertation can be outlined in the following points:

1. Presenting and formulating the model order reduction problem for the financial risk analysis.
2. Simulating and generating the market scenarios, i.e., simulated yield curves per PRIIPs regulation.

3. Developing an automatic, efficient, and effective methodology for parameter sampling.
4. Generating an optimal reduced basis based on efficiently sampled parameters and obtaining the reduced models.
5. Analyzing in detail the numerical errors associated with the developed model order reduction framework.
6. Presenting selected application examples and validating the MOR framework for those examples through numerical simulations.

1.2 Thesis Outline

The thesis is organized as follows. Chapter 1 introduces the thesis along with the types of PRIIPs and European regulations in Section 1.3. The section describes in detail the calculation steps for category three PRIIP instruments. The financial instruments are evaluated using some appropriate valuation function. Chapter 2 discusses these essential valuation functions, where Sections 2.1.2 and 2.1.4 present the one-factor Hull-White model and the two-factor Hull-White model with their respective PDEs. The model parameters of these valuation functions are obtained by calibrating them using simulated yield curves. The yield curve simulation process is described in Section 2.2. The calibration procedures for parameters $a(t)$ and $\theta(t)$ are explained in Sections 2.3 and 2.4, individually. Chapter 3 contains the numerical methods used for the discretization of PDEs. We have implemented the finite difference method in Section 3.1 for the one-factor Hull-White model and the finite element method in Section 3.2 for the two-factor Hull-White model. A detailed description of the designed model order reduction framework is illustrated in Chapter 4. To efficiently determine the training parameter groups, we have implemented the classical greedy sampling approach in Section 4.1. The drawbacks of the classical greedy explained in Subsection 4.1.1 motivated us to consider a more precise sampling technique. Therefore, in Section 4.2, we have presented the adaptive greedy sampling approach. The surrogate modeling and the adaptive greedy algorithm are explained in Subsections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2, respectively. Subsections 4.1.2 and 4.2.3 describes the computational cost required to run classical and adaptive greedy algorithms.

The reduced model is obtained such that the prominent numerical errors are minimized. Chapter 5 presents a detailed error analysis of the developed model order reduction framework. Section 5.1 describes the discretization error associated with the full model and presents algorithms to select suitable timestep and the full model dimension. The errors associated with the MOR approach and the algorithm to select an optimal reduced dimension are presented in Section 5.2. The sampling error associated with the sampling algorithms is described in Section 5.3. The sensitivity approach presented in Subsection 5.4 ranks the numerical errors according to their contribution to the total error and helps efficiently allocate the compu-

tational resources. The developed algorithms are then tested for two financial instruments in Chapter 6. The floater instrument is solved using the one-factor Hull-White model in Section 6.1, and the puttable steepener example presented in Section 6.2 is simulated using the two-factor Hull-White model. Finally, Chapter 7 concludes the thesis and presents an outlook.

1.3 PRIIPs and European Regulations

PRIIPs are at the core of the retail investment market and make up a market in Europe worth up to €10 trillion. They cover a range of financial products that are offered to retail investors. To improve the transparency of PRIIPs and as a protection measure, European Union introduced regulations on key information documents for PRIIPs. The keywords of PRIIPs are packaged and retail investment. When a financial instrument manufacturer has to decide if a key information document has to be provided, the following two questions have to be answered with *yes*. Is the instrument offered to retail investors, and is it packaged? If the instrument is only offered to professional investors, e.g., banks, insurance firms, capital management firms, then no KID has to be provided. Examples are fix-to-floating *swaps* or caps between banks. If the same fix-to-floating swap is offered to a retail investor, a KID has to be supplied. Again, if an instrument is offered to a retail investor but not packaged, no KID is necessary. Examples of such instruments are *bonds* with fixed-rate interest, shares of companies traded at exchanges. The regulations on PRIIPs aim to improve investor protection by standardizing pre-contractual information made available to private investors for investment products whose performance is based on the underlying assets. The key information document prescribed by the PRIIPs regulation is a short and standardized document. It contains information about the type and characteristics of the product, its objectives and risk profile, costs and fees, as well as potential returns and must be kept separate from any marketing material.

A KID must contain the following points on not more than three A4 pages:

1. General information on the product: Name of the product, name of the manufacturer, and its web address, date of the KID, name of the legal authorities for supervision.
2. What is this product?
3. What are the risks and what could I get in return?
4. What happens if [the name of the PRIIP manufacturer] is unable to pay out?
5. What are the costs?
6. How long should I hold it and can I take my money out early?

7. How can I complain?

8. Other relevant information.

To answer the question No. 3, one has to perform several thousand costly numerical simulations of the underlying instrument using an appropriate financial model. The commission delegated regulation (EU) 2017/653 formulates the details of how the risk and the possible returns of a PRIIP have to be calculated. The delegated regulation organizes PRIIPs into four categories.

Category 1: PRIIPs include instruments where the investor can lose more than the amount invested, but also *options*, *futures*, swaps instruments where prices are available on a basis less than monthly. A *Libor* cap is one of the examples.

Category 2: These instruments are either direct or synthetic linear investments for which at least two years of daily prices are available. (When prices are quoted less than daily, the time series has to be longer.) An example would be a synthetic exchange-traded fund based on DAX or the S&P500 index.

Category 3: These instruments are nonlinear investments, again with a time series of prices as with Category 2 instruments. Examples are many structured financial instruments, e.g., a floater with caps and floors.

Category 4: In these instruments the values depend on factors not observed in the market. Examples are life insurance instruments.

In this thesis, we deal with the Category 3 instruments. The calculation for a Category 3 instrument starts by determining a recommended holding period. A holding period is a period between the acquisition of an asset and its sale, i.e., the length of time during which an investor holds an underlying instrument. The recommended holding period gives an idea to an investor for how long one should hold the product to minimize the risk. Generally, the RHP is given in years. In most cases, manufacturers recommend holding the instrument until maturity. At the recommended holding period, a VaR equivalent volatility (VEV) has to be determined to calculate a market risk indicator (1 is very low risk, 7 is very high risk). Market risk classifications are shown in Table 1.1. For the market risk indicator, 10 000 different simulations of a market risk factor (e.g., yield curve) have to be performed. For each of those scenarios, the instrument has to be valued. From the distribution of the resulting values, the VaR can be calculated. The VaR shall be the value of the PRIIP at a confidence level of 97.5% at the end of the recommended holding period discounted to the present date using the expected risk-free discount factor (DF) from the present date to the end of the recommended holding period. Let $P_{97.5}$ be the value of the PRIIP at a confidence level of

Table 1.1: Market risk classification

Market risk classification	VaR equivalent volatility
1	$\text{VEV} < 0.5\%$
2	$0.50\% \leq \text{VEV} < 5.00\%$
3	$5.00\% \leq \text{VEV} < 12.0\%$
4	$12.0\% \leq \text{VEV} < 20.0\%$
5	$20.0\% \leq \text{VEV} < 30.0\%$
6	$30.0\% \leq \text{VEV} < 80.0\%$
7	$\text{VEV} > 80.0\%$

97.5% at the end of the recommended holding period. Furthermore, we calculate $\text{VaR}_{\text{price space}}$ by multiplying $P_{97.5}$ by the discount factor

$$\text{DF} = \exp(r(t_0, t_k)(t_k - t_0)),$$

where $r(t_0, t_k)$ is the yield at the tenor point t_k , t_0 is today and t_k is the maturity, i.e., the recommended holding period T . If the PRIIP prices are log-normal, then the distribution of its logarithm can be given as $\mathcal{N}(-\text{VEV}^2/2)T, \text{VEV}^2T)$. Using this lognormal assumption, the 97.5 percentile of VaR in price space would be

$$\begin{aligned} \text{VaR}_{\text{price space}} &= \exp\left(-\frac{T}{2}\text{VEV}^2 + z_{\alpha=0.025}\text{VEV}\sqrt{T}\right), \\ \ln(\text{VaR}_{\text{price space}}) &= -\frac{T}{2}\text{VEV}^2 - 1.96 \times \text{VEV}\sqrt{T}, \\ \text{VEV}^2 \cdot T + 3.92 \times \text{VEV}\sqrt{T} + 2 \times \ln(\text{VaR}_{\text{price space}}) &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

where $z_{\alpha=0.025} = -1.96$. We solve this quadratic equation for VEV

$$\begin{aligned} \text{VEV} &= \frac{-3.92\sqrt{T} \pm \sqrt{(3.92)^2T - 8T \times \ln(\text{VaR}_{\text{price space}})}}{2T}, \\ &= \frac{-1.96 \pm \sqrt{3.842 - 2 \times \ln(\text{VaR}_{\text{price space}})}}{\sqrt{T}}, \end{aligned}$$

and consider only the positive value

$$\text{VEV} = \frac{\sqrt{(3.842 - 2 \times \ln(\text{VaR}_{\text{price space}}))} - 1.96}{\sqrt{T}}. \quad (1.1)$$

Furthermore, to determine the performance scenario values, the instrument is simulated for 10 000 different market scenarios. These 10 000 values are then sorted into favorable, moderate, and unfavorable performance scenarios, which are the values at 90th, 50th, and 10th

percentile, respectively. If the recommended holding period is less than one year, then the performance scenarios are calculated only at the RHP. However, if the recommended holding period is longer than one year, then the performance scenarios at the intermediate holding periods (1 year, RHP/2, RHP) have to be calculated. Flowchart 1.1 shows the calculation steps for Category 3 instruments. For more details, see the joint committee of the European Supervisory Authorities flowcharts for the risk and reward calculations in the PRIIPs KID [35].

The calibration of the financial model generates a high dimensional parameter space which can be computationally costly, when no analytic solutions are available, e.g., in the case of the Black Karasinski model. Since we need to value the financial instrument for such a high dimensional parameter space, we establish a parametric model order reduction approach.

Figure 1.1: The calculation steps for category three instruments.

Chapter 2

Valuation Functions

The management of interest rate risks, i.e., the control of change in future cash flows due to the fluctuations in interest rates, is of great importance. The pricing of products based on the stochastic nature of the interest rate creates the necessity for suitable mathematical models. These mathematical models serve as the valuation functions for risk analysis where one has to evaluate the financial instrument under various market scenarios. The selection of the valuation function is a crucial task and depends on the underlying financial instrument. The interest rate models describe the future evolution of the interest rates using stochastic differential equations (SDEs). These stochastic models are often used in the valuation of interest rate derivatives and used as valuation functions. The SDEs can be solved either analytically or using PDE-based and Monte-Carlo-based numerical schemes. The PDE for the SDE can be derived using Ito's lemma [119] and constructing a risk-neutral portfolio. The PDE-based methods use finite difference or finite element type numerical schemes to solve the underlying PDE [17, 36, 49], while the Monte-Carlo-based methods use Monte Carlo or Quasi-Monte Carlo schemes to simulate SDEs [42, 104]. There are different interest rate models, for instance, short-rate models that express the interest rate itself as a stochastic process called the *short-rate* [18]. On the other hand, some models directly use market observable rates to establish models instead of taking a detour via short-rates. These models are called Libor market models or the swap market models, depending on which type of rates are considered [39]. These types of models are usually simulated using Monte Carlo or quasi-Monte Carlo schemes. In this thesis, we use PDE-based short-rate models as the valuation functions.

2.1 Short-Rate Models

Consider a *bank account*, also called a money-market account $B(t)$. When investing a certain amount in the bank account, we expect it to grow at some rate over time. A money-market account represents a risk-less investment with a continuous profit at a risk-free rate.

Definition 1. Bank account (Money-market account). Let $B(t)$ be the value of a bank account at time $t \geq 0$. We assume that the bank account evolves according to the following differential equation with $B(0) = 1$,

$$dB(t) = B(t)r(t)dt, \quad (2.1)$$

where $r(t)$ is a *short-rate*. This gives

$$B(t) = \exp\left(\int_0^t r_s ds\right). \quad (2.2)$$

According to the above definition, investing a unit amount at time $t = 0$ yields the value in (2.2) at time t , and r_s is the short-rate at which the bank account grows. This rate $r(t)$ is the growth rate of the bank account B within a small time interval $(t, t + dt)$. When working with interest-rate products, the study about the variability of interest rates is essential. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the short-rate as a stochastic process and it prompts us to construct a stochastic model that will describe the dynamics of the short-rate.

Let S be the price of a stock at the end of the n th trading day. The *daily return* from days n to $(n + 1)$ is given by $(S_{n+1} - S_n)/S_n$. In general, it is common to work with log returns, since the log return of k days can be easily computed by adding up the daily log returns as

$$\log(S_k/S_0) = \log(S_1/S_0) + \dots + \log(S_k/S_{k-1}).$$

Based on the assumption that the log returns over disjoint time intervals are stochastically independent, and are equally distributed, the central limit theorem [29] of probability theory implies that the log returns are normally distributed [25]. So, it is necessary to define a stochastic model in continuous time in which log returns over arbitrary time intervals are normally distributed. The *Brownian motion* provides these properties [2].

Definition 2. Brownian motion. A standard Brownian motion is a stochastic process $W(t)$ where $t \in \mathbb{R}$, i.e., a family of random variables $W(t)$, indexed by non-negative real numbers t with the following properties:

- At $t = 0$, $W_0 = 0$.
- With probability 1, the function $W(t)$ is continuous in t .
- For $t \geq 0$, the increment $W(t + s) - W(s)$ is normally distributed with mean 0 and variance t , i.e.,

$$W(t + s) - W(s) \sim N(0, t).$$

- For all n and times $t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{n-1} < t_n$, the increments $W(t_j) - W(t_{j-1})$ are stochastically independent.

Based on the definition of the Brownian motion, we can establish a stochastic differential equation. Consider an ordinary differential equation (ODE)

$$\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = q(t)X(t), \quad (2.3)$$

with an initial condition $X(0) = X_0$. When we consider ODE (2.3) with an assumption that the parameter $q(t)$ is not a deterministic but rather a stochastic parameter, we get a stochastic differential equation.

In our case, the stochastic parameter $q(t)$ is given as [48]

$$q(t) = f(t) + h(t)w(t),$$

where $w(t)$ is a white noise process. Thus, we get

$$\frac{dX(t)}{dt} = f(t)X(t) + h(t)X(t)w(t). \quad (2.4)$$

This equation is known as Langevin equation [76], where $X(t)$ is a stochastic variable having the initial condition $X(0) = X_0$ with probability one. The Langevin force $w(t) = dW(t)/dt$ is a fluctuating quantity having Gaussian distribution. Substituting $dW(t) = w(t)dt$ in (2.4), we get

$$dX(t) = f(t)X(t)dt + h(t)X(t)dW(t).$$

In the general form a stochastic differential equation is given by

$$dX(t) = f(t, X(t))dt + g(t, X(t))dW(t), \quad (2.5)$$

where $f(t, X(t)) \in \mathbb{R}$, and $g(t, X(t)) \in \mathbb{R}$ are sufficiently smooth functions. Based on (2.5), we can define a stochastic differential equation with the short-rate $r(t)$ as a stochastic variable as

$$dr(t) = f(t, r(t))dt + g(t, r(t))dW(t), \quad (2.6)$$

In the following subsections, we start by introducing, in chronological order, some of the classical models like the Vasicek model [115] and the Cox-Ingersoll-Ross (CIR) model [28], followed by more advanced and recent models.

2.1.1 Vasicek Model and Cox-Ingersoll-Ross Model

The Vasicek model is the earliest stochastic model of the term structure of interest rates. In the model, the instantaneous short-rate is assumed to follow a stochastic process known as the *Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process* [41], a form of Gaussian process described by [115]

$$dr(t) = (a - br(t))dt + \sigma dW(t), \quad r(0) = r_0, \quad (2.7)$$

which can also be represented as

$$dr(t) = b(\hat{a} - r(t))dt + \sigma dW(t),$$

where $r(t)$ is the short-rate, b is the speed of mean reversion, \hat{a} is the mean reversion level, σ is the short-rate volatility, and $a = b\hat{a}$. The Vasicek model is a mean-reverting model which means that over time the short-rate will converge to the mean reversion level \hat{a} with speed b . When the short-rate is high, the mean reversion process pulls it down, and likewise, when it is low, the process pushes it up to the mean reversion level. The model equation is linear and can be solved explicitly, the distribution of the short-rate is Gaussian, and both the expressions and the distributions of several useful quantities related to the interest-rate world are easily obtainable. These characteristics make the model attractive. However, the model has some drawbacks. For example, due to the assumption that the interest rates are distributed normally, rates can assume negative values with positive probability. The Cox-Ingersoll-Ross model, which takes the dynamics of r as the following square root process [28]

$$dr(t) = b(\hat{a} - r(t))dt + \sigma\sqrt{r(t)}dW(t), \tag{2.8}$$

overcomes this problem. The model assumes positive interest rates as the square root term does not allow negative values. The instantaneous rate, i.e., the short-rate, is characterized by the *noncentral chi-squared distribution* [106]. Moreover, this model maintains a certain degree of analytical tractability. However, it is less tractable than the Vasicek model. Therefore, the CIR model has both some advantages and disadvantages. Nevertheless, the major drawback of both models is that the model parameters are constant, so we can not fit them to the market structures like yield curves. To overcome this drawback, *exogenous* term structure models are usually considered. Such models are designed by modifying *endogenous* models like the Vasicek model. The basic strategy is to transform an endogenous model into an exogenous model by the inclusion of time-dependent parameters. The Hull-White model, an extension of the Vasicek model, and the Black-Karasinski model, analogously to the Exponential-Vasicek model, are prominent examples of exogenous models.

2.1.2 Hull-White model

The Hull-White model assumes that the instantaneous short-rate process evolves under the risk-neutral measure as [55]

$$dr(t) = (a(t) - b(t)r(t))dt + \sigma(t)dW(t), \tag{2.9}$$

which is an extension of the Vasicek model (2.7), where now the parameters $a(t)$, $b(t)$, $\sigma(t)$ are deterministic functions of time. Such a model can be fitted to the term structure of interest

rates and the term structure of *spot* or *forward volatilities*. However, the perfect fitting of the volatility term structure is problematic and must be dealt with care. There are two main reasons. First, according to [18], not all the volatilities quoted in the market are significant, some markets are less liquid, and the associated quotes might not be reliable. Second, the Hull-White model is calibrated based on today's (t_0) market data for bond prices $B(T)$. To project the parameters $b(t)$ and $\sigma(t)$ into the future (t_1), one could use either $B(T + (t_1 - t_0))$ or $B(T)$ [56]. In the first case, the shape of the parameters remains unchanged and does not cover seasonalities or expected changes like money market politics, while in the second case, we lose the information on the short end. In short, the future volatility structures implied by (2.9) are likely to be unrealistic, i.e., they do not agree to typical market shapes, which Hull and White themselves remarked [58]. Additionally, we have considered PRIIPs as test examples, and the PRIIPs regulation does not prescribe how to obtain these model parameters. Thus, considering the parameters $b(t)$ and $\sigma(t)$ constant should lead to more robust results than time-dependent parameters. We, therefore, use the following form of the Hull-White model throughout this thesis

$$dr(t) = (a(t) - br(t))dt + \sigma dW(t). \quad (2.10)$$

We call this model with constant mean reversion speed b and volatility σ the *robust one-factor Hull-White model*. However, our model order reduction approach can be extended to the more general case.

In this thesis, we use PDE-based methods to solve the underlying instruments. Therefore, in the following section, we derive the partial differential equation for the one-factor Hull-White model. Based on Ito's lemma [51, 119], we can derive a general PDE for any underlying instrument depending on the short-rate r .

Theorem 2.1.1. Ito's Lemma. [51] *Let $\xi(X(t), t)$ be a sufficiently smooth function and let the stochastic process $X(t)$ be given by (2.5), then with probability one,*

$$\begin{aligned} d\xi(X(t), t) = & \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial X(t)} f(X(t), t) + \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial X^2(t)} g^2(X(t), t) \right) dt \\ & + \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial X(t)} g(X(t), t) dW(t). \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

Consider a *risk-neutral portfolio* Π_t that depends on the short-rate r_t and consists of two interest rate instruments V_1 and V_2 with different maturities T_1 and T_2 respectively. Let there be Δ units of the instrument V_2 . For an infinitesimal time interval, the value change of the portfolio is $d\Pi_t = \Delta dV_2 - dV_1$. To avoid the *arbitrage*, we have to consider a risk-free rate [1], which gives

$$d\Pi_t = \Delta dV_2 + (V_1 - \Delta V_2) r dt - dV_1.$$

Based on Ito's lemma, we get

$$\begin{aligned} d\Pi_t &= (V_1 - \Delta V_2)r_t dt \\ &\quad - \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial r_t} f(r_t, t) + \frac{\partial V_1}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V_1}{\partial r_t^2} g^2(r_t, t) \right) dt + \frac{\partial V_1}{\partial r_t} g(r_t, t) dW(t) \right] \\ &\quad + \Delta \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_2}{\partial r_t} f(r_t, t) + \frac{\partial V_2}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V_2}{\partial r_t^2} g^2(r_t, t) \right) dt + \frac{\partial V_2}{\partial r_t} g(r_t, t) dW(t) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Let $\Delta = \left(\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial r_t} / \frac{\partial V_2}{\partial r_t} \right)$. Due to the zero net investment requirement, i.e., $d\Pi_t = 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \left[V_1 - \left(\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial r_t} / \frac{\partial V_2}{\partial r_t} \right) V_2 \right] r_t dt \\ &\quad - \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial r_t} f(r_t, t) + \frac{\partial V_1}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V_1}{\partial r_t^2} g^2(r_t, t) \right) dt + \frac{\partial V_1}{\partial r_t} g(r_t, t) dW(t) \right] \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial r_t} / \frac{\partial V_2}{\partial r_t} \right) \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_2}{\partial r_t} f(r_t, t) + \frac{\partial V_2}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V_2}{\partial r_t^2} g^2(r_t, t) \right) dt + \frac{\partial V_2}{\partial r_t} g(r_t, t) dW(t) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Eliminating the stochastic term, we get

$$\begin{aligned} &\left[V_1 - \left(\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial r_t} / \frac{\partial V_2}{\partial r_t} \right) V_2 \right] r_t dt \\ &= \left[\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V_1}{\partial r_t^2} g^2(r_t, t) - \left(\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial r_t} / \frac{\partial V_2}{\partial r_t} \right) \left(\frac{\partial V_2}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V_2}{\partial r_t^2} g^2(r_t, t) \right) \right] dt. \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging the terms, and using the notation $r = r_t$, we get

$$\frac{\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V_1}{\partial r^2} g^2(r, t) - r V_1}{\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial r}} = \frac{\frac{\partial V_2}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V_2}{\partial r^2} g^2(r, t) - r V_2}{\frac{\partial V_2}{\partial r}}.$$

Denoting the right side as $u(r, t)$

$$\frac{\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 V_1}{\partial r^2} g^2(r, t) - r V_1}{\frac{\partial V_1}{\partial r}} = u(r, t),$$

and using the notation $V = V_1$, we obtain the following PDE for any financial instrument V depending on r

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} g^2(r, t) \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r^2} - u(r, t) \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} - r V = 0. \quad (2.12)$$

In the case of the one-factor Hull-White model in (2.10), $g(r, t) = \sigma(t)$, and $-u(r, t) = (a(t) - b(t)r)$. Substituting $g(r, t)$ and $u(r, t)$, we get

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + (a(t) - b(t)r) \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2(t) \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r^2} - r V = 0, \quad (2.13)$$

then the robust one-factor Hull-White PDE is

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + (a(t) - br) \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r^2} - rV = 0. \tag{2.14}$$

The parameter $a(t)$ is calibrated using the market structures like yield curves. In Section 2.2, we present a detailed yield curve simulation along with the calibration of $a(t)$ in Section 2.3.

2.1.3 Black-Karasinski Model

Another prominent exogenous model is the Black-Karasinski model, analogous to the extension of the exponential Vasicek model. It overcomes the drawback of negative rates as the model considers the lognormal short-rate. The model assumes that the instantaneous short-rate process evolves as the exponential of an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process with time-dependent coefficients. The stochastic differential equation is given as [18]

$$d \ln(r(t)) = (a(t) - b(t) \ln(r(t))) dt + \sigma(t) dW(t), \tag{2.15}$$

where $a(t)$, $b(t)$, and $\sigma(t)$ are the deterministic functions of time that can be obtained by fitting the initial term structures of interest rates and market volatility curves. Nevertheless, in the current financial market, there are some hurdles in using lognormal models. Central banks typically use a monetary policy to manage interest rates and money supply to target economic growth and inflation levels. Over the past few years, central banks in Europe and Japan are imposing negative interest rates. The consequences of this are the lognormal models like the Black-Karasinski model are not suitable in the world of negative interest rates. Thus, in this thesis, we concentrate on the Hull-White model.

2.1.4 Two-Factor Hull-White Model

In the following, we introduce the two-factor Hull-White short-rate model. Before describing the actual model, it is necessary to understand the motivation behind the multi-factor models. We have seen in the previous subsections that the short-rate dynamics can characterize the market structures like yield curves. In affine one-factor models, the yield rates or the forward rates at two different tenor points (time points) are perfectly correlated, i.e., their correlation coefficient is one, which is unrealistic [13]. This means that a change to the interest rate curve at time t is transmitted equally through all maturities. In short, this perfect correlation only allows parallel shifts of the yield curves. However, interest rates are known to exhibit some non-perfect correlations. We often noticed the yield curve steepening where short-term rates are low and the long-term rates are high [18]. Thus, multi-factor models are usually used, which could provide better control over the representation of the market structures as more factors are incorporated. Also, for instruments like steepeners [2], where coupons depend

on the difference between two rates, we need to consider a multi-factor model like the two-factor Hull-White model. The two-factor model overcomes these drawbacks by extending the one-factor model by adding a stochastic disturbance to the drift term. In the two-factor Hull-White model, the short-rate r is assumed to satisfy the stochastic differential equation [57]

$$\begin{aligned} dr(t) &= (\theta(t) + u(t) - \alpha(t)r(t))dt + \sigma_1(t)dW_1(t), \\ du(t) &= -b(t)u(t)dt + \sigma_2(t)dW_2(t), \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

where $\alpha, b, \sigma_1, \sigma_2 > 0$ and W_1, W_2 are two Brownian motions under the risk neutral measure such that

$$dW_1(t)dW_2(t) = \gamma dt, \quad (2.17)$$

where $-1 \leq \gamma \leq 1$ is the correlation coefficient. In the two-factor Hull-White model, we consider model parameters $\alpha, b, \sigma_1, \sigma_2$ as constants similar to the argument presented for the one-factor Hull-White model. Thus, we use the following model throughout this thesis

$$\begin{aligned} dr(t) &= (\theta(t) + u(t) - \alpha r(t))dt + \sigma_1 dW_1(t), \\ du(t) &= -bu(t)dt + \sigma_2 dW_2(t), \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

which we call the *robust two-factor Hull-White model*. In the following, we derive the partial differential equation for the two-factor Hull-White model. First, we introduce the multidimensional Ito's lemma [51], based on which we later derive the PDE. Suppose we have n independent Brownian motions $W(t) = (W_i(t), i = 1, \dots, n, t \in \mathbb{R}^+)$ and n stochastic processes $X_i(t)$ with respect to $W_i(t)$ given by (2.6) then the multidimensional Ito's lemma is defined as follows.

Theorem 2.1.2. Ito's Lemma (Multidimensional) [51] *Let $X(t) = (X_1(t), X_2(t), \dots, X_n(t))$ be an n -dimensional stochastic process and let $\xi(x, t) : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ be the twice continuously differential function with a continuous partial time derivative, then $\xi(X(t), t)$ is an Ito's process whose k th component is given by*

$$d\xi_k(X(t), t) = \frac{\partial \xi_k}{\partial t} dt + \frac{\partial \xi_k}{\partial X_i} dX_i + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \xi_k}{\partial X_i \partial X_j} (dX_i)(dX_j), \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n, \quad (2.19)$$

where $dt dt = dt dW_i = dW_i dt = 0$, $dW_i dW_j = 0 \quad \forall i \neq j$, and $(dW_i)^2 = dt$.

Consider a financial instrument $V(t, r(t), u(t))$ contingent on the stochastic interest rate movement $r(t)$. By Ito's lemma

$$\begin{aligned} dV(t, r(t), u(t)) &= \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} dt + \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} dr + \frac{\partial V}{\partial u} du \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r^2} (dr)(dr) + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial u^2} (du)(du) + 2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r \partial u} (dr)(du) \right), \end{aligned}$$

We can determine the quadratic variation $(dr)(dr)$ of dr and the quadratic covariation $(dr)(du)$ of dr and du as

$$\begin{aligned} (dr)(du) &= -(\theta(t) + u - \alpha r(t))b(t)u(t)dt^2 + \sigma_2(\theta(t) + u - \alpha r(t))dW_2dt \\ &\quad - b\sigma_1u(t)dW_1dt + \sigma_1\sigma_2dW_1dW_2, \end{aligned}$$

where from Ito's lemma $dt^2 = dW_1dt = dW_2dt = 0$, and from (2.14) $dW_1dW_2 = \gamma dt$, which leads to

$$(dr)(du) = \gamma\sigma_1\sigma_2dt. \quad (2.20)$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} (dr)(dr) &= \sigma_1^2dt, \\ (du)(du) &= \sigma_2^2dt. \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

Substituting (2.20), (2.21), dr and du we get

$$\begin{aligned} dV &= \frac{\partial V}{\partial t}dt + \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} \left[(\theta(t) + u - \alpha r)dt + \sigma_1dW_1 \right] + \frac{\partial V}{\partial u} \left[(-bu + \sigma_2dW_2) \right] \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial u^2} + \gamma\sigma_1\sigma_2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r\partial u} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Considering an arbitrage-free market, the expected return of the underlying instrument under *an equivalent martingale measure* should equal the riskless interest rate [1, 75]. This applies conditions such that $E(dV(t, r(t), u(t))) = rV(t, r(t), u(t))dt$ and $E(dW_{1,2}) = 0$. Applying this no-arbitrage requirement leads to

$$rVdt = \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + (\theta(t) + u - \alpha r) \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} - bu \frac{\partial V}{\partial u} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial u^2} + \gamma\sigma_1\sigma_2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r\partial u} \right) dt.$$

The two-factor Hull-White PDE is then given as

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + (\theta(t) + u - \alpha r) \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} - bu \frac{\partial V}{\partial u} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial u^2} + \gamma\sigma_1\sigma_2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r\partial u} - rV = 0. \quad (2.22)$$

The deterministic function $\theta(t)$ is chosen to fit the simulated yield curves. The simulation of yield curves and the calibration of the parameter $\theta(t)$ based on these yield curves are presented in Sections 2.2 and 2.4, respectively.

2.2 Yield Curve Simulation

The PRIIP regulation demands to perform yield curve simulations for at least 10 000 times [34], and that the data set must contain at least 2 years of daily interest rates for an underlying instrument, or 4 years of weekly interest rates, or 5 years of monthly interest rates. We

construct a data matrix $D \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ of the collected historical interest rates data, where each row of the matrix forms a yield curve, and the column represents the m tenor points, which are the different contract lengths of an underlying instrument. For example, if we have collected the daily interest rate data at $m \approx 20$ tenor points in time over the past five years, then since a year has approximately 260 working days, one obtains $n \approx 1306$ observation periods.

The regulations demand to take the natural logarithm of the ratio between the interest rate at each observation period and the interest rate at the preceding period. To ensure that we can form the natural logarithm, we need that all elements of the data matrix D are positive which is achieved by adding a correction term. With \mathcal{W} the matrix of all ones, we set $\bar{D} = D + \gamma\mathcal{W}$, where γ is chosen so that all elements of matrix \bar{D} are positive. We are compensating the shift γ at the bootstrapping stage by subtracting it from the simulated rates. Then we calculate the log returns over each period and store them into a new matrix $\hat{D} = \hat{d}_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ as

$$\hat{d}_{ij} = \frac{\ln(\bar{d}_{ij})}{\ln(\bar{d}_{i-1,j})}.$$

We calculate the arithmetic mean μ_j of each column of the matrix \hat{D} ,

$$\mu_j = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{d}_{ij},$$

subtract μ_j from each element of the corresponding j th column of \hat{D} and store the obtained results in a matrix $\bar{\bar{D}}$ with entries $\bar{\bar{d}}_{ij} = \hat{d}_{ij} - \mu_j$. We then compute the singular value decomposition [43] of the matrix $\bar{\bar{D}}$ as

$$\bar{\bar{D}} = \Phi \Sigma \Psi^T,$$

where Σ is a diagonal matrix having singular values Σ_i arranged in descending order. The columns of Φ are the normalized left singular vectors and the columns of $\Phi \Sigma$ are known as *principal components*. The columns of Ψ are the right singular vectors or *principal directions* of the covariance matrix $\mathcal{C} = \bar{\bar{D}}^T \bar{\bar{D}}$.

The relative importance of the i th singular value is determined by the *relative energy*

$$\Xi_i = \frac{\Sigma_i}{\sum_{i=1}^m \Sigma_i},$$

where the *total energy* is given by $\sum_{i=1}^m \Xi_i = 1$. We then select the p right singular vectors

corresponding to the maximal p energies and construct a matrix

$$\bar{\Psi} = \begin{bmatrix} \psi_{11} & \cdots & \psi_{1p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \psi_{m1} & \cdots & \psi_{mp} \end{bmatrix}.$$

We project the matrix \bar{D} onto the matrix $\bar{\Psi}$ as

$$M_p = \bar{D} \cdot \bar{\Psi} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p},$$

and then calculate the matrix of returns $M_R = M_p \bar{\Psi}^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$. The regulations suggest selecting the first three ($p = 3$) right singular vectors. This process simplifies the statistical data \bar{D} and transforms m correlated tenor points into p uncorrelated principal components, reproducing the same data by simply reducing the total size of the model.

We then perform *bootstrapping*, where large numbers of small samples of the same size are drawn repeatedly from the original data set. According to the PRIIP regulations, for the yield curve simulation we have to perform a bootstrapping procedure for at least 10 000 times. The standardized KID also has to include the recommended *holding period*, i.e., the period between the acquisition of an asset and its sale. The time step in the simulation of yield curves is typically one observation period. If H is the recommended holding period in days, e.g., $H \approx 2600$ days, then there are H observation periods in the recommended holding period.

For each such observation period, we select a random row from the matrix M_R , i.e., altogether H random rows, and construct a matrix $[\chi_{ij}] \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times m}$ from these selected rows. Then we sum over the selected rows of the columns corresponding to the tenor point j , i.e.,

$$\bar{\chi}_j = \sum_{i=1}^h \chi_{ij}, \quad j = 1, \dots, m.$$

In this way, we obtain a row vector $\bar{\chi} = [\bar{\chi}_1 \ \bar{\chi}_2 \ \cdots \ \bar{\chi}_m] \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times m}$. The final simulated yield rate y_j at tenor point j is then the rate \bar{d}_{n_j} of the last observation period at the corresponding tenor point j , multiplied by the exponential of $\bar{\chi}_j$, adjusted for any shift γ used to ensure positive values for all tenor points, and adjusted for the forward rate so that the expected mean matches current expectations.

The forward rate between time points t_k and t_ℓ starting from a time point t_0 is given as

$$r_{k,\ell} = \frac{R(t_0, t_\ell)(t_\ell - t_0) - R(t_0, t_k)(t_k - t_0)}{t_\ell - t_k},$$

where t_k and t_ℓ are measured in years and $R(t_0, t_k)$ and $R(t_0, t_\ell)$ are the interest rates available from the data matrix for the time periods (t_0, t_k) and (t_0, t_ℓ) , respectively. Thus, the final

simulated yield rate between time points t_k and t_ℓ is given by

$$y(t_\ell) = \bar{d}_{k,\ell} \exp(\bar{\chi}_\ell) - \gamma + r_{k,\ell}, \quad \ell = 1, \dots, m, \quad (2.23)$$

and the simulated yield curve from the calculated simulated returns is given by

$$y = [y_1 \ y_2 \ \dots \ y_m].$$

We then perform the bootstrapping procedure for at least $s = 10\,000$ times and construct a simulated yield curve matrix

$$Y = \begin{bmatrix} y_{11} & \dots & y_{1m} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ y_{s1} & \dots & y_{sm} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times m}, \quad (2.24)$$

which is then used to calibrate the parameters $a(t)$ and $\theta(t)$.

2.3 Calibration of the Parameter $a(t)$

For a *zero-coupon bond* $B(t, T)$ maturing at time T , based on the Hull-White model, one obtains a closed-form solution, see [108], as

$$B(t, T) = \exp\{-r(t)\Gamma(t, T) - \Lambda(t, T)\}, \quad (2.25)$$

where $\kappa(t) = \int_0^t b(s) ds = bt$, since b is assumed constant,

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(t, T) &= \int_t^T e^{-\kappa(t)} dt, \\ \Lambda(t, T) &= \int_t^T \left[e^{\kappa(v)} a(v) \left(\int_v^T e^{-\kappa(z)} dz \right) - \frac{1}{2} e^{2\kappa(v)} \sigma^2 \left(\int_v^T e^{-\kappa(z)} dz \right)^2 \right] dv. \end{aligned}$$

Here we have again considered that σ is constant.

To perform the calibration, we use as input data i) the initial value of $a(0)$ at $t = 0$, ii) the zero-coupon bond prices, iii) the constant value of the volatility σ of the short-rate $r(t)$, and iv) the constant value b each for all maturities T_m , $0 \leq T_m \leq T$, where T_m is the maturity at the m th tenor point. Then we compute $\kappa(t)$ from $\frac{\partial}{\partial T} \kappa(T) = \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \int_0^T b(s) ds = b$ and use

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial T} \Gamma(0, T) = e^{-\kappa(T)}$$

to compute $\Gamma(t)$.

Then, for $0 \leq T_m \leq T$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial T} \Lambda(0, T) &= \int_0^T \left[e^{\kappa(v)} a(v) e^{-\kappa(T)} \right. \\
&\quad \left. - e^{2\kappa(v)} \sigma^2 e^{-\kappa(T)} \left(\int_v^T e^{-\kappa(z)} dz \right) \right] dv, \\
e^{\kappa(T)} \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \Lambda(0, T) &= \int_0^T \left[e^{\kappa(v)} a(v) - e^{2\kappa(v)} \sigma^2 \left(\int_v^T e^{-\kappa(z)} dz \right) \right] dv, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left[e^{\kappa(T)} \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \Lambda(0, T) \right] &= e^{\kappa(T)} a(T) - \int_0^T e^{2\kappa(v)} \sigma^2 e^{-\kappa(T)} dv, \\
e^{\kappa(T)} \left[e^{\kappa(T)} \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \Lambda(0, T) \right] &= e^{2\kappa(T)} a(T) - \int_0^T e^{2\kappa(v)} \sigma^2 dv, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left[e^{\kappa(T)} \left[e^{\kappa(T)} \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \Lambda(0, T) \right] \right] &= \frac{\partial a(T)}{\partial T} e^{2\kappa(T)} + 2a(T) e^{2\kappa(T)} \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \kappa(T) - e^{2\kappa(T)} \sigma^2, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial T} \left[e^{\kappa(T)} \left[e^{\kappa(T)} \frac{\partial}{\partial T} \Lambda(0, T) \right] \right] &= \frac{\partial a(T)}{\partial T} e^{2\kappa(T)} + 2a(T) e^{2\kappa(T)} b(T) - e^{2\kappa(T)} \sigma^2.
\end{aligned}$$

The simulated yield $y(T)$ at the tenor point T is given by [1]

$$y(T) = -\ln B(0, T), \quad (2.26)$$

and from (2.26) and (2.25) we obtain $\Lambda(0, T) = [y(T) - r(0)\Gamma(t)]$. In this way, for $a(t)$ we get the ordinary differential equation (ODE)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} a(t) e^{2\kappa(t)} + 2a(t) \cdot b \cdot e^{2\kappa(t)} - e^{2\kappa(t)} \sigma^2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left[e^{\kappa(t)} \left[e^{\kappa(t)} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (y(t) - r(0)\Gamma(0, t)) \right] \right],$$

which we solve numerically with the given initial conditions. If we approximate $a(t)$ by a piecewise constant function with values $a(i)$ which change at the tenor point i , then we obtain a linear system

$$L\alpha = F,$$

for the vector $\alpha = [a(i)]$, where L is a lower triangular matrix with non-zero diagonal elements. In [32] it is noted that the integral equation Λ is of the first kind with L_2 kernel and a small perturbation (noise) in the market data that are used to obtain the yield curves leads to large changes in the model parameter $a(t)$. This means that the problem to compute $a(t)$ from the data is an ill-posed problem and for this reason we determine the vector α via Tikhonov regularization as

$$\alpha_\mu^\delta = \operatorname{argmin} \|L\alpha - F^\delta\|^2 + \mu \|\alpha\|^2, \quad (2.27)$$

where α_μ^δ is an approximation to α , μ is the regularization parameter, $\delta = \|F - F^\delta\|$ is the noise level, and $\mu\|\alpha\|^2$ is a regularization term. We then solve the optimization problem (2.27) to obtain an approximation of the parameter $a(t)$ via the commercial software *UnRisk PRICING ENGINE* [79]. By providing the simulated yield curve, the UnRisk pricing function returns the calibrated parameter $a(t)$ for that yield curve. Based on $s = 10\,000$ different simulated yield curves, we obtain s different piecewise constant parameters $a_\ell(t)$, which change their values $\alpha_{\ell,i}$ only at the m tenor points. We incorporate these in a matrix

$$\mathcal{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{11} & \cdots & \alpha_{1m} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \alpha_{s1} & \cdots & \alpha_{sm} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.28)$$

2.4 Calibration of the Parameter $\theta(t)$

For a zero-coupon bond $B(t, T)$ maturing at time T , one obtains a closed form solution based on the two-factor Hull-White model, see [57], as

$$B(t, T) = \Gamma(t, T) \exp\{-r(t)\Lambda(t, T) - H(t, T)u\}, \quad (2.29)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda(t, T) &= \frac{1}{\alpha} \left[1 - e^{-\alpha(T-t)} \right], \\ H(t, T) &= \frac{1}{\alpha(\alpha - b)} e^{-\alpha(T-t)} - \frac{1}{b(\alpha - b)} e^{-b(T-t)} + \frac{1}{\alpha b}, \\ \ln \Gamma(t, T) &= \ln B(0, T) + \Lambda(t, T)F(0, T) + \Upsilon(0, t)\Lambda(t, T) + \int_0^t \Upsilon(0, \tau) d\tau - \int_0^t \Upsilon(\tau, T) d\tau, \end{aligned}$$

where $F(t, T)$ is the instantaneous *forward rate* for time T as seen at time t and Υ is

$$\Upsilon = \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2\Lambda(t, T)^2 + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_2^2H(t, T)^2 + \gamma\sigma_1\sigma_2\Lambda(t, T)H(t, T).$$

Finally, the $\theta(t)$ function is

$$\theta(t) = \frac{\partial F(0, t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \Upsilon(0, t)}{\partial t} + \alpha F(0, t) + \alpha \Upsilon(0, t). \quad (2.30)$$

To perform the calibration, we have considered parameters $\alpha, b, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, \gamma$ as known and constants for all maturities T_m , $0 \leq T_m \leq T$, where T_m is the maturity at the m th tenor point. We can determine the instantaneous forward rate using the simulated yield curve as [1]

$$F(t_0, T_\ell) = \frac{y(t_0, T_\ell)(T_\ell - T_0) - y(T_0, T_{\ell-1})(T_{\ell-1} - T_0)}{T_\ell - T_{\ell-1}}, \quad 0 \leq \ell \leq m,$$

where $T_0 = 0$ and $y(T_0, T_\ell)$ is the simulated yield rate. We then solve (2.30) to obtain an approximation of the parameter $\theta(t)$. If we approximate $\theta(t)$ by a piecewise constant function with values $\theta(i)$ which change at the tenor point i , then we obtain a linear system

$$L\theta = F, \tag{2.31}$$

for the vector $\theta = [\theta(i)]$, where L is a lower triangular matrix with non-zero diagonal elements, similar to the one-factor case. Thus, if the parameters $b, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, \gamma$ are known and constant, the drift parameter $\theta(t)$ again leads to this linear system of equations (2.31), which should be treated by the same techniques used for the one-factor Hull-White model. See [1, 32, 57, 79] for more details. In this work, we have used the commercial software *UnRisk PRICING ENGINE* for the parameter calibration [79]. For the calibration of the model parameters, the software provides two possibilities: (i) calibration of $\theta(t)$ according to the given yield curve, where all other parameter $\alpha, b, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, \gamma$ are given and constant. (ii) calibration of parameters $a(t), b(t), \sigma_1(t), \sigma_2(t), \gamma$ and $\theta(t)$ according to given market data of caps and swaptions, if considered time dependent. Since we have considered these parameters constant, based on $s = 10\,000$ different simulated yield curves, we obtain s different piecewise constant parameters $\theta_\ell(t)$, which change their values $\theta_{\ell,i}$ only at the m tenor points. We incorporate these in a matrix

$$\Theta = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_{11} & \cdots & \theta_{1m} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \theta_{s1} & \cdots & \theta_{sm} \end{bmatrix}. \tag{2.32}$$

Chapter 3

Numerical Methods

In this chapter, we describe numerical methods for short-rate partial differential equations. The one-factor Hull-White model is discretized using the finite difference method (FDM), while the finite element method (FEM) is used to solve the two-factor Hull-White model.

3.1 Finite Difference Method

The PDE obtained for the one-factor Hull-White model is a convection-diffusion-reaction type PDE [5]. Consider the robust Hull-White PDE given by (2.14)

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \underbrace{(a(t) - br_t) \frac{\partial V}{\partial r}}_{\text{Convection}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r^2}}_{\text{diffusion}} - \underbrace{rV}_{\text{reaction}} = 0.$$

In this work, we apply the finite difference method to solve this PDE. The convection term in the above equation may lead to numerically unstable results. Thus, we implement the so-called upwind scheme [52] to obtain a stable solution. We incorporate the semi-implicit scheme called the Crank-Nicolson method [114] for the time discretization.

3.1.1 Spatial Discretization

We define a discretization of the computational domain in sd spatial dimensions as

$$[u_k, v_k]^{sd} \times [0, T] = [u_1, v_1] \times \cdots \times [u_{sd}, v_{sd}] \times [0, T] = \left(\prod_{k=1}^{sd} [u_k, v_k] \right) \times [0, T],$$

where u and v are the cut off limits of the spatial domain. T denotes the final time of the computation. The corresponding indices are $i_k \in \{1, \dots, M_k\}$ for the spatial discretization with step size h and $n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ for the time discretization, $t_0 = 0, t_1, \dots, t_N = T, t_n = n\tau$, with time step τ .

Consider the following one-dimensional linear advection equation for a field $\zeta(x, t)$,

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (3.1)$$

describing a wave propagation along the x -axis with a velocity U . The first order upwind scheme of order $\mathcal{O}(h)$ is given by

$$\frac{\zeta_i^{n+1} - \zeta_i^n}{\tau} + U \frac{\zeta_i^n - \zeta_{i-1}^n}{h} = 0 \quad \text{for } U > 0 \quad (3.2a)$$

$$\frac{\zeta_i^{n+1} - \zeta_i^n}{\tau} + U \frac{\zeta_{i+1}^n - \zeta_i^n}{h} = 0 \quad \text{for } U < 0 \quad (3.2b)$$

Let us introduce,

$$U^+ = \max(U, 0), \quad U^- = \min(U, 0),$$

and

$$\zeta_x^- = \frac{\zeta_i^n - \zeta_{i-1}^n}{h}, \quad \zeta_x^+ = \frac{\zeta_{i+1}^n - \zeta_i^n}{h}.$$

Combining (3.2a) and (3.2b) in compact form, we obtain

$$\zeta_i^{n+1} = \zeta_i^n - \tau[U^+ \zeta_x^- + U^- \zeta_x^+]. \quad (3.3)$$

We have implemented the above defined upwind scheme for the convection term.

The diffusion term is discretized using the second order central difference scheme of order $\mathcal{O}(h)^2$ given by

$$\frac{\partial^2 \zeta}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\zeta_{i+1}^n - 2\zeta_i^n + \zeta_{i-1}^n}{h^2}. \quad (3.4)$$

3.1.2 Time Discretization

Consider a time-dependent PDE for a quantity ζ

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} + \mathcal{L}\zeta = 0, \quad (3.5)$$

where \mathcal{L} is the differential operator containing all spatial derivatives. Using the Taylor series expansion, we write

$$\zeta(t + \tau) = \zeta(t) + \tau \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} + \frac{\tau^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \zeta}{\partial t^2}.$$

Neglecting terms of order higher than one, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} = \frac{\zeta(t + \tau) - \zeta(t)}{\tau} + \mathcal{O}(\tau).$$

From (3.5), we get

$$\frac{\zeta(t + \tau) - \zeta(t)}{\tau} = -\mathcal{L}(t)\zeta(t), \quad (3.6)$$

and, in turn, the explicit time stepping scheme

$$\zeta(t + \tau) = \zeta(t) - \tau(\mathcal{L}(t)\zeta(t)).$$

For this explicit time-stepping scheme, it is not necessary to solve a system of linear equations. On the other hand, for the fully implicit time-stepping scheme

$$\frac{\zeta(t + \tau) - \zeta(t)}{\tau} = -\mathcal{L}(t + \tau)\zeta(t + \tau),$$

we have to solve the following system of linear equations

$$(1 + \tau\mathcal{L}(t + \tau))\zeta(t + \tau) = \zeta(t).$$

Let us introduce a new parameter Θ such that

$$\frac{\zeta(t + \tau) - \zeta(t)}{\tau} + (1 - \Theta)(\mathcal{L}(t)\zeta(t)) + \Theta(\mathcal{L}(t + \tau)\zeta(t + \tau)) = 0. \quad (3.7)$$

We can construct different time discretization schemes for different values of Θ . Setting $\Theta = 0$, we obtain a fully explicit scheme known as the forward Euler method, while considering $\Theta = 1$, we get a fully implicit scheme known as the backward Euler method. We set $\Theta = 1/2$ and obtain a semi-implicit scheme known as the Crank-Nicolson method [5], which is unconditionally stable and second order in time

$$\left(1 + \frac{1}{2}\tau\mathcal{L}(t + \tau)\right)\zeta(t + \tau) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}\tau\mathcal{L}(t)\right)\zeta(t). \quad (3.8)$$

3.1.3 Finite Difference Method for the one-factor Hull-White Model

The robust one-factor Hull-White model (2.14) is discretized by applying the finite difference method described above. As computational domain for the interest rate r we use an interval $[r_{low}, r_{up}]$, which according to [1] given by

$$r_{low} = r_s(T) - 7\sigma\sqrt{T}, \quad r_{up} = r_s(T) + 7\sigma\sqrt{T},$$

where $r_s(T)$ is the yield at the maturity T also known as a *spot rate*. We divide the spatial domain into M equidistant grid points $\{r(1), r(2), \dots, r(M)\}$, $r(i) = r(i - 1) + h$ with spacial step size h , and the time interval $[0, T]$ in N points $t_0 = 0, t_1, \dots, t_N = T$, $t_n = n\tau$, with time

step τ . Equation (2.14) can then be represented as,

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \mathcal{L}(t)V(t) = 0. \quad (3.9)$$

We specify the spatial discretization operator $\mathcal{L}(n)$, where the index n denotes the time-point. From (3.2) and (3.4), we get,

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{for } (a(n) - br_i) > 0 \\ & \mathcal{L}(n)V_i^n := \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 \frac{V_{i+1}^n - 2V_i^n + V_{i-1}^n}{h^2} + (a(n) - br_i) \frac{V_i^n - V_{i-1}^n}{h} - r_i V_i^n, \\ & \text{for } (a(n) - br_i) < 0 \\ & \mathcal{L}(n)V_i^n := \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 \frac{V_{i+1}^n - 2V_i^n + V_{i-1}^n}{h^2} + (a(n) - br_i) \frac{V_{i+1}^n - V_i^n}{h} - r_i V_i^n. \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

Similar to (3.7), going backwards in time and using backward finite difference quotients

$$\frac{V(t) - V(t - \tau)}{\tau} + (1 - \Theta)(\mathcal{L}(t)V(t)) + \Theta(\mathcal{L}(t - \tau)V(t - \tau)) = 0. \quad (3.11)$$

For $\Theta = 1/2$, we then have

$$\underbrace{\left(1 - \frac{1}{2}\tau\mathcal{L}(t - \tau)\right)}_{A(\rho_\ell(t)) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}} V(t - \tau) = \underbrace{\left(1 + \frac{1}{2}\tau\mathcal{L}(t)\right)}_{B(\rho_\ell(t)) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}} V(t), \quad (3.12)$$

where the matrices $A(\rho_s(t))$, and $B(\rho_s(t))$ depend on parameters $a(t)$, b and σ . We denote $\rho_s = \{a(t), b, \sigma\}$ as the s th group of these parameters. Here

$$A(\rho_s(t)) = I - \frac{\sigma^2\tau}{2h^2}J - \frac{\tau}{2h}(H^+G^- + H^-G^+) + R_o,$$

and

$$B(\rho_s(t)) = I + \frac{\sigma^2\tau}{2h^2}J + \frac{\tau}{2h}(H^+G^- + H^-G^+) - R_o,$$

where

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} -2 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 1 & -2 & 1 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 1 & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 1 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & -2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G^- &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & -1 & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} & G^+ &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & -1 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\
H^+ &= \begin{bmatrix} \max(a(n) - br(1)) & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \max(a(n) - br(2)) & 0 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & \max(a(n) - br(M)) \end{bmatrix} \\
H^- &= \begin{bmatrix} \min(a(n) - br(1)) & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \min(a(n) - br(2)) & 0 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & \min(a(n) - br(M)) \end{bmatrix} \\
R_o &= \begin{bmatrix} r(1) & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & r(2) & 0 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 & r(M) \end{bmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

This discretization is a parametric high dimensional model of the form

$$A(\rho_\ell(t))V^{n-1} = B(\rho_\ell(t))V^n, \quad (3.13)$$

with a given terminal vector V^T , and matrices $A(\rho_\ell) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$, and $B(\rho_\ell) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$. We solve this model by propagating backward in time. We call this the *full model* for the model reduction procedure in Chapter 4. Here again $\ell = 1, \dots, s = 10\,000$, m is the total number of tensor points, and we need to solve this system at each time step n with an appropriate boundary condition and a known terminal value for the underlying instrument. We consider the parameter $a(t)$ a piecewise constant function of time that changes its value only at m tensor points, as explained in Section 2.3. Altogether we have a parameter space \mathcal{P} of size $10\,000 \times m$ to which we apply model reduction.

3.2 Finite Element Method

We implement the finite element method to discretize the two-factor Hull-White PDE, which we can write as

$$\mathcal{D}(V)(r, u) = 0,$$

where \mathcal{D} denotes the differential operator involving spatial and temporal derivatives of V . When we insert an approximate solution V_h obtained over a finite discretized domain Ω into the PDE, it is unlikely that the equation will hold. That is, there exist some residual \mathcal{R} such that

$$\mathcal{D}(V_h)(r, u) = \mathcal{R}.$$

One can achieve an exact solution $V(r, u, t) = V_h(r, u, t)$ if the residual vanishes, i.e., $\mathcal{R} = 0$. However, in a general case, such a solution does not exist as the approximate solution's function space is a subset of the exact solution's function space. Therefore, one usually tries to fulfill the residual criteria by some weighted or averaged linearly independent weight functions \mathcal{W}_i such that

$$\int_{\Omega} \mathcal{W}_i(r, u) \mathcal{D}(V_h)(r, u) d\Omega = 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, n,$$

where \mathcal{W}_i are the weight functions or also known as test functions and $d\Omega = drdu$. This integral form of the equation is also called the *weak form* [91].

3.2.1 Weak Form

In the first step, we determine this integral equation that defines the element matrices for the two-factor Hull-White PDE. From (2.22), the robust two-factor Hull-White model is

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + (\theta(t) + u - \alpha r) \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} - bu \frac{\partial V}{\partial u} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_2^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial u^2} + \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r \partial u} - rV = 0.$$

Consider a discretization domain with N_e elements and M nodes. The time domain is discretized into N time points, $t_0 = 0, t_1, \dots, t_N = T$, where $t_n = n\tau$ with time step τ . Omitting the subscript of the approximate solution, the weak form of the PDE with the implicit time stepping reads for any weight function \mathcal{W} as, see also [1],

$$\begin{aligned} & \int \mathcal{W}^T \frac{V^n - V^{n-1}}{\tau} drdu + \int \mathcal{W}^T \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial r \partial u} \right) \right. \\ & \left. + \left(\frac{1}{2} \sigma_2^2 \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial u^2} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial r \partial u} \right) \right] drdu \\ & + \int \mathcal{W}^T \left[(\theta^{n-1} + u - \alpha r) \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} - bu \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right] drdu - \int \mathcal{W}^T r V^{n-1} drdu = 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int \mathcal{W}^T \frac{V^n - V^{n-1}}{\tau} drdu + \int \mathcal{W}^T \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right) \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{\partial}{\partial u} \left(\frac{1}{2} \sigma_2^2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} \right) \right] drdu \\
& + \int \mathcal{W}^T \left[(\theta^{n-1} + u - \alpha r) \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} - bu \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right] drdu - \int \mathcal{W}^T r V^{n-1} drdu = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

By applying the product rule of differentiation, the second order derivatives can be replaced by first order derivatives

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} \right) &= \mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial r^2} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}^T}{\partial r} \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r}, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial u} \left(\mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right) &= \mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial u^2} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}^T}{\partial u} \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u}, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right) &= \mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial r \partial u} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}^T}{\partial r} \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u}, \\
\frac{\partial}{\partial u} \left(\mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} \right) &= \mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial r \partial u} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}^T}{\partial u} \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r},
\end{aligned}$$

which gives

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{W}^T \frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial r^2} &= \frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}^T}{\partial r} \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} \right], \\
\mathcal{W}^T \frac{1}{2} \sigma_2^2 \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial u^2} &= \frac{1}{2} \sigma_2^2 \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial u} \left(\mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}^T}{\partial u} \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right], \\
\mathcal{W}^T \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial r \partial u} &= \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}^T}{\partial r} \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right], \\
\mathcal{W}^T \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial^2 V^{n-1}}{\partial r \partial u} &= \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}^T}{\partial u} \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} \right].
\end{aligned} \tag{3.14}$$

Substituting (3.14) into the integral equation gives the weak form of the two-factor Hull-White model

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int \mathcal{W}^T \frac{V^n - V^{n-1}}{\tau} drdu - \int \left[\frac{\partial \mathcal{W}^T}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right) \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{\partial \mathcal{W}^T}{\partial u} \left(\frac{1}{2} \sigma_2^2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} \right) \right] drdu \\
& + \int_S \mathcal{W}^T \left(\frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right) n_r dS \\
& + \int_S \mathcal{W}^T \left(\frac{1}{2} \sigma_2^2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} \right) n_u dS \\
& + \int \mathcal{W}^T \left[(\theta^{n-1} + u - \alpha r) \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} - bu \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right] drdu - \int \mathcal{W}^T r V^{n-1} drdu = 0,
\end{aligned} \tag{3.15}$$

where the first terms on the right hand side of (3.14) under the integral are replaced by integrals over the boundary of the computational domain $S = \partial\Omega$ using Green's theorem [107], i.e.,

$$\int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} \right) dr du = \int_S \mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} n_r dS.$$

These surface integrals vanish as we choose homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions. The authors of [11] remarked that while solving the underlying instrument using the two-factor Hull-White model, the homogenous Neumann boundary conditions deliver the best results. The value of the normal derivative for the Neumann boundary condition is known and given as [1]

$$\lambda_r \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} n_r + \lambda_u \frac{\partial V}{\partial u} n_u = f.$$

For $\lambda_r = \lambda_u$, the expression reduces to

$$\lambda_r \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} = f, \tag{3.16}$$

where $\partial V/\partial n$ is the derivative normal to the boundary. The inclusion of this boundary condition is accomplished by the surface integral. From (3.15) and (3.16),

$$\int \mathcal{W}^T \left(\frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} n_r + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} n_u \right) ds = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \int \mathcal{W}^T \frac{\partial V}{\partial n} ds = \int \mathcal{W}^T f ds.$$

For the homogeneous Neumann boundary condition, $f = 0$, the surface integral vanishes. To overcome the instabilities that may occur due to convection domination, we use the streamline upwind Petrov Galerkin (SUPG) method [122]. The fundamental idea of this approach is to add extra diffusion in the direction of the streamline by replacing the weight function \mathcal{W} by $\mathcal{W} + \delta_e v \nabla \mathcal{W}$, where $v = [\theta(t) + u - \alpha r, -bu]$ and $\delta_e = h_e/2|v|$. The characteristic element size h_e can be easily calculated in two dimensions as follows [122]

$$h_e = \min \left(\frac{2A^{(e)}}{L^{(e)}} \right),$$

where $A^{(e)}$ is the area of the element and the $L^{(e)}$ denotes the edge length of an element. This change in the weight function creates an additional term in the convection part as

$$\sum_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{\Omega} \delta_e v \nabla \mathcal{W} \left[(\theta^{n-1} + u - \alpha r) \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial r} - bu \frac{\partial V^{n-1}}{\partial u} \right] dr du,$$

which has the typical form of a diffusion term. Here the parameters δ_e depend on the size of the elements and the convection coefficients, so the artificial diffusion is higher in convection-dominated regions and smaller in regions where diffusion dominates. The approach is well established in the literature, for more details see [1, 52, 122, 123].

3.2.2 Shape Functions

In the following, we define weight functions. There are different methods to solve a PDE depending on the choices of weight functions. These methods are the collocation method, the sub-domain method, the least-square method, and the Galerkin method [91, 121]. Out of these methods, Galerkin method is the most popular approach and used in this thesis. The fundamental idea of Galerkin method is to express an approximate solution as a linear combination of the basis functions $\{N_i\}_{i=1}^M$, see also [60, 91, 123],

$$V(r, u) = \sum_{i=1}^M V_i N_i(r, u),$$

where V_i are the unknowns to be computed and the summation is performed over all grid nodes M . In the Galerkin method, the weight functions are nothing but the basis functions N_i , which are also called shape functions. These affine linear functions interpolate the solution between the discrete values obtained at the mesh nodes. The shape functions can be chosen quite freely, but they must be appropriate for interpolation. In practical applications, linear shape functions or piecewise polynomials of low order are usually used. In the following, we derive linear shape functions on triangular elements. For our computations, we have used a structured, two-dimensional, triangular grid with graded higher resolution in both directions near the values of interest rates r and u . The computational domain is discretized into N_e elements having M nodes. The elements are located in such a manner that there are no empty spaces between them and they do not overlap

$$\Omega = \bigcup_{i=1}^{N_e} E_i \quad \text{such that} \quad \forall i \neq j \quad \text{Int}(E_i) \cap \text{Int}(E_j) = 0,$$

where $\text{Int}(E)$ is the set of all points in the element E , except that are located at the surface. The following section illustrates the two-dimensional linear triangular shape functions in detail. The two-dimensional linear triangular element, as shown in Fig. 3.1, can be represented as a linear polynomial of x and y

$$V(x, y) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 x + \beta_3 y. \tag{3.17}$$

We can use the nodal values

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{(e)}(x, y) &= \beta_1^{(e)} + \beta_2^{(e)} X_i + \beta_3^{(e)} Y_i, \\ V_j^{(e)}(x, y) &= \beta_1^{(e)} + \beta_2^{(e)} X_j + \beta_3^{(e)} Y_j, \\ V_k^{(e)}(x, y) &= \beta_1^{(e)} + \beta_2^{(e)} X_k + \beta_3^{(e)} Y_k, \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3.1: Linear triangular element with i, j, k nodes

to determine the coefficients $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ by solving a linear system of equations

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & X_i & Y_i \\ 1 & X_j & Y_j \\ 1 & X_k & Y_k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1^{(e)} \\ \beta_2^{(e)} \\ \beta_3^{(e)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} V_i^{(e)} \\ V_j^{(e)} \\ V_k^{(e)} \end{bmatrix}.$$

The solution of this linear system gives

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_1^{(e)} &= \frac{1}{2A^{(e)}} \left((X_j Y_k - X_k Y_j) V_i^{(e)} + (X_k Y_i - X_i Y_k) V_j^{(e)} + (X_i Y_j - X_j Y_i) V_k^{(e)} \right), \\ \beta_2^{(e)} &= \frac{1}{2A^{(e)}} \left((Y_j - Y_k) V_i^{(e)} + (Y_k - Y_i) V_j^{(e)} + (Y_i - Y_j) V_k^{(e)} \right), \\ \beta_3^{(e)} &= \frac{1}{2A^{(e)}} \left((X_k - X_j) V_i^{(e)} + (X_i - X_k) V_j^{(e)} + (X_j - X_i) V_k^{(e)} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where $A^{(e)}$ is the area of the element

$$A^{(e)} = \frac{1}{2} \det \begin{bmatrix} 1 & X_i & Y_i \\ 1 & X_j & Y_j \\ 1 & X_k & Y_k \end{bmatrix}.$$

The shape functions N_i, N_j, N_k can then be obtained by substituting the values of $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ in (3.17). The elemental unknown quantity using shape functions can be represented as

$$V(x, y) = N_i^{(e)} V_i^{(e)} + N_j^{(e)} V_j^{(e)} + N_k^{(e)} V_k^{(e)}, \quad (3.18)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} N_i^{(e)} &= \frac{1}{2A^{(e)}} \left((X_j Y_k - X_k Y_j) + (Y_j - Y_k)x + (X_k - X_j)y \right) = \frac{1}{2A^{(e)}} (u_i + v_i x + w_i y), \\ N_j^{(e)} &= \frac{1}{2A^{(e)}} \left((X_k Y_i - X_i Y_k) + (Y_k - Y_i)x + (X_i - X_k)y \right) = \frac{1}{2A^{(e)}} (u_j + v_j x + w_j y), \\ N_k^{(e)} &= \frac{1}{2A^{(e)}} \left((X_i Y_j - X_j Y_i) + (Y_i - Y_j)x + (X_j - X_i)y \right) = \frac{1}{2A^{(e)}} (u_k + v_k x + w_k y). \end{aligned}$$

$N = [N_i, N_j, N_k]$ is the row vector containing the element shape functions. Each shape function has a value one at its designated node and a value zero for the remaining two nodes. Also, the sum of all three shape functions is always equal to one. Substituting these shape functions as weight functions into the weak form of the PDE (3.15) leads to a sparse linear system of equations having parameter dependent matrices. Substituting the unknown quantity V as

$$V(r, u) = N^{(e)} V^{(e)},$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\underbrace{\int_{\Omega} N^T N drdu}_{C^{(e)}} \right] \frac{V^{(e)n} - V^{(e)n-1}}{\tau} - \left[\underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial N^T}{\partial r} \frac{\partial N}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_2^2 \frac{\partial N^T}{\partial u} \frac{\partial N}{\partial u} \right) drdu}_{K_1^{(e)}} \right] V^{(e)n-1} \\ & - \left[\underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{1}{2} \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial N^T}{\partial r} \frac{\partial N}{\partial u} + \gamma \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \frac{\partial N^T}{\partial u} \frac{\partial N}{\partial r} \right) drdu}_{K_2^{(e)}} \right] V^{(e)n-1} \\ & + \left[\underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \left((\theta^{n-1} + u - \alpha r) N^T \frac{\partial N}{\partial r} - bu N^T \frac{\partial N}{\partial u} \right) drdu}_{M_1^{(e)}} \right] V^{(e)n-1} \\ & - \left[\underbrace{\int_{\Omega} (r N^T N) drdu}_{M_2^{(e)}} \right] V^{(e)n-1} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

We can write this equation in more compact form

$$C^{(e)} \frac{V^{(e)n} - V^{(e)n-1}}{\tau} - \underbrace{(K_1^{(e)} + K_2^{(e)})}_{K^{(e)}} V^{(e)n-1} - \underbrace{(M_1^{(e)} + M_2^{(e)})}_{M^{(e)}} V^{(e)n-1} = 0,$$

which further leads to

$$\left[C^{(e)} + \left(\tau (K^{(e)} + M^{(e)}) \right) \right] V^{(e)n-1} = C^{(e)} V^{(e)n}, \quad (3.19)$$

where $C^{(e)}$ is called an element capacitance matrix, $K^{(e)}$ is an element stiffness matrix, and $M^{(e)}$ is an element mass matrix. An equation of the form (3.19) can be derived for each element. If the computational domain is divided into N_e elements, the global coefficient matrix of the whole system must be assembled from the coefficient matrices of the single elements. See [1, 60] for assembly and global matrix formation. The assembly of elemental matrices generates a system of linear equations called the *full model*, which we further use for the model order reduction and is given as

$$A(\rho_\ell(t))V^{n-1} = B(\rho_\ell(t))V^n, \quad (3.20)$$

with matrices $A(\rho_\ell) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$, and $B(\rho_\ell) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$. $\rho = \{\alpha, b, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, \gamma, \theta(t)\}$ is the group of model parameters. We solve this model by propagating backward in time. Here again $\ell = 1, \dots, s = 10\,000$, m is the total number of tensor points, and we need to solve this system at each time step n with an appropriate boundary condition and a known terminal value for the underlying instrument. Altogether we have a parameter space \mathcal{P} of size $10\,000 \times m$ to which we apply model reduction.

Chapter 4

Model Order Reduction

Model order reduction has become a popular tool in numerical analysis to solve complex high-dimensional problems [7, 105]. It delivers a low dimensional approximation of the high dimensional system. Such simplifications are necessary and beneficial in order to perform simulations within an acceptable amount of time but with a reliable outcome. However, it is less familiar in computational finance. There are few studies that apply MOR to solve computationally expensive problems in finance [20, 80, 99, 100]. Most of these studies use MOR to solve either option pricing models or speed up financial model calibration. Nonetheless, the implemented model order reduction is a new and intriguing method for financial risk analysis. This chapter presents the model order reduction approach for solving the parametric full order models described in Chapter 3. We explain the background necessary for the model order reduction and present the proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) approach.

The POD approach was first introduced in [74] for analysis of turbulent flows and is closely related to the methods used in other fields such as Karhuen-Loéve expansion in stochastic modeling and the principal component analysis in statistics. POD computes a basis that provides a low dimensional representation of a high dimensional system. The basis vectors are computed empirically using sampled data collected by solving the high dimensional model, typically using the method of snapshots [109]. In order to generate the parametric reduced model, these snapshots are computed by solving the full model for some pre-selected training parameter groups. In this chapter, we first describe the method of snapshots for the computation of the POD basis, then Section 4.1 presents a classical greedy sampling approach to obtain the pre-selected training parameter set. To overcome the drawbacks of the classical greedy sampling, Section 4.2 also illustrates an adaptive greedy sampling approach.

Once the parametric reduced model is achieved, the MOR technique described in this work can be portrayed in a black-box fashion, which is explained in Section 5.5. Additionally, the particular numerical method used for the discretization of the PDE is most often not relevant to the model order reduction procedure. Thus, the approach presented in this thesis can be implemented for both one-factor and multi-factor models. We also present an error

analysis of the developed model order reduction framework in Chapter 5 and the sensitivity analysis for the numerical errors in Section 5.4.

The standard approach for reducing the full model is to project the model onto a smaller subspace. To perform the parametric model reduction for systems (3.13) or (3.20), we employ the Galerkin projection onto a low dimensional subspace via

$$\bar{V}^n = QV_d^n, \quad (4.1)$$

where the columns of $Q = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_d] \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times d}$ represent the reduced basis with $d \ll M$, V_d^n is a vector of reduced coordinates, and $\bar{V}^n \in \mathbb{R}^M$ is the solution at the n th time step obtained using the reduced model. For the Galerkin projection we require that the residual of the reduced state

$$p^n(V_d^n, \rho_\ell) = A(\rho_\ell)QV_d^{n-1} - B(\rho_\ell)QV_d^n \quad (4.2)$$

is orthogonal to the reduced basis matrix Q , i.e.,

$$Q^T p^n(V_d^n, \rho_\ell) = 0, \quad (4.3)$$

so that by multiplying $p^n(V_d^n, \rho_\ell)$ with Q^T , we get

$$\begin{aligned} Q^T A(\rho_\ell)QV_d^{n-1} &= Q^T B(\rho_\ell)QV_d^n, \\ A_d(\rho_\ell)V_d^{n-1} &= B_d(\rho_\ell)V_d^n, \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

where $A_d(\rho_\ell) \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ and $B_d(\rho_\ell) \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ are the parameter dependent reduced matrices. We obtain the Galerkin projection matrix Q in (4.1) based on the proper orthogonal decomposition approach, which generates an optimal order orthonormal basis Q in the least square sense that is independent of the parameter space \mathcal{P} and we do this by the method of snapshots. The snapshots are nothing but the state solutions obtained by solving the full model for selected training parameter groups. Assume that we have a training parameter set of parameter groups $[\rho_1, \dots, \rho_k] \in [\rho_1, \rho_s]$. We compute the solutions of the full model for this training set and combine them in a snapshot matrix $\hat{V} = [V(\rho_1), V(\rho_2), \dots, V(\rho_k)] \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times k}$. The proper orthogonal decomposition of snapshots \hat{V} can be defined in terms of a system minimization problem that computes

$$\text{POD}(\hat{V}) = \underset{Q}{\operatorname{argmin}} \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \|V_i - QQ^T V_i\|^2,$$

to find an orthogonal matrix $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times d}$. The solution to this minimization problem can be determined using the *singular value decomposition* (SVD) of a snapshot matrix. The SVD gives the rank of a matrix, i.e., the number of non-zero singular values of \hat{V} is the rank of the

matrix. Let $\min(M, k) = k$ be the rank of a matrix, then its truncated SVD reads

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{V} &= \Phi \Sigma \Psi^T, \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^k \Sigma_i \phi_i \psi_i^T,\end{aligned}$$

where ϕ_i and ψ_i are the left and right singular vectors of the matrix \hat{V} respectively, and Σ_i are the singular values $\Sigma_1 \geq \Sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \Sigma_k \geq 0$ arranged in descending order along the diagonal of a matrix $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k}$. The truncated SVD computes only the first k columns of the matrix Φ . The optimal projection subspace Q then consists of d left singular vectors ϕ_i known as *POD modes*. The dimension d of the subspace Q is chosen such that we get a good approximation of the snapshot matrix. According to [89], large singular values correspond to the main characteristics of the system, while small singular values give only small perturbations of the overall dynamics. The relative importance of the i th POD mode of the matrix \hat{V} is determined by the *relative energy* Ξ_i of that mode

$$\Xi_i = \frac{\Sigma_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k \Sigma_i}. \quad (4.5)$$

If the sum of the energies of the generated modes is 1, then these modes can be used to reconstruct a snapshot matrix completely [118]. In general, the number of modes required to generate the complete data set is significantly less than the total number of POD modes [87]. Thus, a matrix \hat{V} can be accurately approximated by using POD modes whose corresponding energies sum to almost all of the total energy. Thus, we choose only d out of k POD modes to construct $Q = [\phi_1 \dots \phi_d]$ which is a parameter independent projection space. We choose only d out of k POD modes to construct $Q = [\phi_1 \dots \phi_d]$ which minimizes the projection error (5.24)

$$\epsilon_{\text{POD}} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k \|V_j - \sum_{k=1}^{\ell} (V_j \phi_k) \phi_k\|^2 = \sum_{\ell=d+1}^k \Sigma_{\ell}^2.$$

We describe the procedure of selecting the dimension d of the reduced basis in Algorithm 10. The detailed error analysis of the model order reduction is explained in Subsection 5.2.

We summarize the parametric POD procedure in Algorithm 1, where we denote by $V(\rho_i)$ the solution of the full model for a parameter group ρ_i , by \hat{V} the snapshot matrix, by Φ (Ψ) the matrix of left (right) singular vectors, associated with the diagonal matrix of singular values Σ , and ϵ_{tol}^d denotes the user-defined tolerance.

Algorithm 1 (Parametric POD).

Input: Parameter groups $\rho_s = \{a(t), b, \sigma\}$, d , number of samples k , tolerance ϵ_{tol}^d .

Output: Projection matrix Q .

Choose sample parameter groups ρ_1, \dots, ρ_k .

FOR $i = 1$ to k .

Solve the full order model for the parameter group ρ_i and determine $V(\rho_i)$.

END

Construct a snapshot matrix $\hat{V} = [V(\rho_1), \dots, V(\rho_k)]$.

Compute leading singular values and vectors of \hat{V} using truncated SVD $\hat{V} = \Phi \Sigma \Psi^T$.

FOR $j = 1, \dots, \text{length}(\Sigma)$

Compute $\epsilon_{\text{POD}} = \sum_{\ell=j+1}^k \Sigma_{\ell}^2$.

IF $\epsilon_{\text{POD}} < e_{\text{tol}}^d$

$d = j$

Break

END IF

END.

$Q = [\phi_1 \cdots \phi_d]$.

It is evident that the quality of the reduced model strongly depends on the selection of parameter groups ρ_1, \dots, ρ_k that are used to compute the snapshots. Hence it is essential to introduce an efficient sampling technique for the parameter space. We could consider standard sampling techniques, like uniform sampling or random sampling [62]. However, these techniques may neglect vital regions within the parameter space. As an alternative, a greedy sampling method has been suggested in the framework of model order reduction, see [4, 47, 85].

4.1 Greedy Sampling

Greedy algorithms were first introduced as optimization techniques [30]. Their popularity increased in many fields because, even though they do not necessarily find a globally optimal solution, they succeed in obtaining local optima in a relatively short time. In model order reduction, the greedy algorithm iteratively selects the best possible parameter groups and constructs the reduced basis. The idea is to select the parameter groups at which the error between the reduced model and the full model is maximal. At each greedy iteration, the method seeks a parameter group where the reduced model solution is the worst for the existent reduced basis. Thus, adding the full model solution for the worst parameter group to the

snapshot matrix will ultimately improve the quality of the reduced basis for the next iteration. Let ϵ_{RM} be the relative error between the full model and the reduced model given as

$$\epsilon_{\text{RM}} = \frac{\|V - \bar{V}\|}{\|V\|}, \quad (4.6)$$

where V is the solution obtained using the full model and \bar{V} is the result obtained using the reduced model. At each greedy iteration $i = 1, \dots, I_{\text{max}}$, the greedy sampling algorithm selects the optimal parameter group ρ_I that maximizes the relative error ϵ_{RM}

$$\rho_I = \underset{\rho \in \mathcal{P}}{\operatorname{argmax}} \epsilon_{\text{RM}}.$$

The greedy algorithm then iterates for a certain number of iterations I_{max} or until the tolerance threshold set for the relative error is matched. The above procedure indicates that we have to compute the relative error for each parameter group within the parameter space \mathcal{P} to locate the optimal parameter group ρ_I . Since the computation of the relative error requires the full model solution, the process becomes extremely computationally costly. Therefore, the classical greedy sampling algorithm is generally trained on some randomly chosen pre-defined parameter subset $\hat{\mathcal{P}} \subset \mathcal{P}$, instead of the entire parameter space \mathcal{P} . Starting with some initial reduced basis Q_0 , the algorithm searches the optimal parameter group through a parameter set \mathcal{P} as follows:

```

FOR  $i = 1, \dots, I_{\text{max}}$ 
    Draw random parameter groups from the parameter space  $\mathcal{P}$  and construct  $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ .
    Compute the relative error for each parameter group within  $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ .
    Obtain  $\rho_I = \underset{\rho \in \mathcal{P}}{\operatorname{argmax}} \epsilon_{\text{RM}}$ .
    Update the reduced basis  $Q$ .
END FOR

```

Even though this approach is simple and effective, the procedure has some computational drawbacks. At each iteration, the algorithm chooses the optimal parameter group from the set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$. If the cardinality of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ is c , then the relative error has to be computed c times per iteration, which is still computationally costly as the relative error entails the full model solution. Therefore, the error estimator has to be cheap and not dependent on the full model solution. Usually, the relative error is replaced by error estimators, like a residual error $\|p(V, \rho)\|$. It is well established in the literature that the residual error can be used to

estimate the relative error [15, 16, 92]. For the systems of linear equations, it holds that [15],

$$1 \leq \frac{\|A(\rho)\| \epsilon_{\text{RM}}}{\|p(V, \rho)\|} \leq k,$$

$$\frac{1}{k} \leq \frac{\epsilon_{\text{RM}}}{\|A^{-1}(\rho)\| \|p(V, \rho)\|} \leq 1,$$

where $k = \|A(\rho)\| \|A^{-1}(\rho)\|$. Thus, if $\|A(\rho)\|$ or $\|A^{-1}(\rho)\|$ are known, according to [15], the quantities $\|p(V, \rho)\| / \|A(\rho)\|$ and $\|A^{-1}(\rho)\| \cdot \|p(V, \rho)\|$ can be considered as estimates of ϵ_{RM} , and we have the bounds

$$\frac{\|p(V, \rho)\|}{\|A(\rho)\|} \leq \epsilon_{\text{RM}} \leq \|A^{-1}(\rho)\| \cdot \|p(V, \rho)\|.$$

This significant result allows solving the local minimization of the error using an error estimator based on the residual. Let $\varepsilon = \|p(V, \rho)\|$ be the error estimator, i.e., in our case the norm of the residual. At each iteration $i = 1, \dots, I_{\text{max}}$, the classical greedy sampling algorithm chooses the parameter group as the maximizer

$$\rho_I = \underset{\rho \in \mathcal{P}}{\operatorname{argmax}} \varepsilon(\rho). \quad (4.7)$$

This optimization problem is then solved using a direct search over a pre-defined set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$. The procedure for the classical greedy approach is summarized in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 (Classical greedy sampling).

Input: Maximum number of iterations I_{max} , maximum number of parameter groups c , parameter space \mathcal{P} , tolerance ε_{tol} .

Output: Galerkin projection matrix Q .

Choose first parameter group ρ_1 from \mathcal{P} .

Solve the full order model for the parameter group ρ_1 and store the results in V_1 .

Compute a truncated SVD of the matrix V_1 , construct Q_1 , and generate a reduced model.

Randomly select a set of c parameter groups $\hat{\mathcal{P}} = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \dots, \rho_c\} \subset \mathcal{P}$.

FOR $i = 2$ to I_{max}

FOR $j = 1$ to c

Solve the reduced model for parameter group ρ_j with reduced basis Q_{i-1} .

Compute the error estimator $\varepsilon(\rho_j)$.

END

Compute $\rho_I = \underset{\rho \in \hat{\mathcal{P}}}{\operatorname{argmax}} \varepsilon(\rho)$.

IF $\varepsilon(\rho_I) \leq \varepsilon_{tol}$, then $Q = Q_{i-1}$, STOP.

Simulate the full model for the parameter group ρ_I and store the result in V_i .

Construct a snapshot matrix \hat{V} by concatenating the solutions V_ℓ for $\ell = 1, \dots, i$.

Compute a truncated SVD of \hat{V} , construct Q_i , and generate a new reduced model.

END

The algorithm is initiated by selecting a parameter group ρ_1 from the parameter set \mathcal{P} and computing a reduced basis Q_1 as described in Algorithm 1. It is necessary to note that the choice of a parameter group to obtain the initial reduced basis Q_1 does not affect the final result. One can initiate the greedy sampling algorithm with any parameter group. Nonetheless, for the simplicity of computations, we select the first parameter group ρ_1 from the parameter space \mathcal{P} to obtain Q_1 . Furthermore, a pre-defined parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ of cardinality c has been chosen randomly from the set \mathcal{P} . At each point of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$, the algorithm determines a reduced model with reduced basis Q_1 and then computes error estimator values, $\varepsilon(\rho_j)_{j=1}^c$. The parameter group in $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ at which the error estimator is maximal is then selected as the optimal parameter group ρ_I . Then the full model is simulated for this parameter group and the snapshot matrix \hat{V} is updated. Finally, a new reduced basis is obtained by computing a truncated singular value decomposition of the updated snapshot matrix, as in Algorithm 1. These steps are then repeated for I_{max} iterations or until the maximal value of the error estimator is lower than the specified tolerance ε_{tol} .

4.1.1 Drawbacks

There are certain drawbacks associated with the classical greedy sampling approach. The algorithm computes an inexpensive a posteriori error estimator for the reduced model to locate the optimal parameter groups. This error estimator is based on the residual norm, which scales with the dimension of the full model. With an increase in dimension M , it is not computationally reasonable to calculate the error estimator values for the entire parameter space just to train the algorithm. To address this, the classical greedy sampling technique locates the optimal parameter groups from the randomly chosen pre-defined parameter subset $\hat{\mathcal{P}} \subset \mathcal{P}$. Random sampling is designed to represent the whole parameter space \mathcal{P} , but there is no guarantee that $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ will reflect the complete space \mathcal{P} , since the random selection may neglect parameter groups corresponding to the most significant error. These observations motivate us to design a new criterion for the selection of the subset $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$. This thesis establishes an adaptive greedy sampling approach that utilizes an optimized search based on surrogate modeling to obtain the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$.

Another drawback of the classical greedy sampling technique is that we have to specify the maximum error estimator tolerance ε_{tol} . The error estimator usually depends on some error bound, which may not be tight or may not exist. To overcome this drawback, following ideas in [85], we establish a strategy to construct an approximate model for the relative error as a function of the error estimator and we use this approximate model to control the convergence of the greedy sampling algorithm.

4.1.2 Computational Cost

In the case of the classical greedy sampling approach, the algorithm solves c reduced models and one full model at each greedy iteration. It also computes a truncated SVD of the updated snapshot matrix with each proceeding iteration. Let t_{RM} be the time required to solve one reduced model, t_{FM} the computational time required for one full model, and t_{SVD} the time required to obtain a truncated SVD of the snapshot matrix. The total computational time T_Q^{CG} required to obtain the reduced basis after i steps of the greedy algorithm in the case of the classical greedy sampling approach can be given as

$$T_Q^{CG} \approx \left[c \times t_{RM} + (t_{FM} + t_{SVD}) \right] \times i. \quad (4.8)$$

4.2 Adaptive Greedy Sampling Method

To overcome the drawbacks of the classical greedy sampling approach, we derived and implemented the adaptive sampling approach which selects the parameter groups adaptively at each iteration of the greedy procedure, using an optimized search based on surrogate modeling. The surrogate model constructs an approximate model for the desired simulation output, i.e., in our case, the error estimator. Then the surrogate model is trained on some error estimator values. This training data is obtained by solving the reduced model for some random parameter groups. Subsequently, we can deploy this trained surrogate model to perform simulations instead of the original model. Since the single evaluation of the surrogate model is faster than the original model, performing thousand of evaluations for the given high dimensional parameter space is no longer a problem. In short, the surrogate modeling methods make those expensive computations economical.

We construct a surrogate model $\bar{\varepsilon}$ of the error estimator to approximate the error estimator ε over the entire parameter space. Further, we use this surrogate model to construct the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}} = \{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_c\}$, which can be used to locate the optimal parameter group, similar to the classical greedy sampling. Figure 4.1 shows the general idea behind the surrogate modeling. Instead of taking a costly simulation path (dashed line), the surrogate model allows us to take a cheaper path (solid line) and computes the output faster. To train the surrogate model, we solve the reduced model only for c_k parameter groups and obtain the

Figure 4.1: Use of a surrogate model to replace costly original model simulations:
 $- - \rightarrow$: Expensive, since it involves many simulations of an original model.
 \rightarrow : Cheap, since training and employing a surrogate model.

error estimator values. The remaining error estimator values corresponding to the remaining parameter groups are then obtained using the trained surrogate model. In the following, we present a methodology to construct a surrogate model.

4.2.1 Surrogate Modeling

There are different choices to build a surrogate model: regression models [62], decision trees [88], machine learning and artificial neural networks [38, 62], and kriging models [65]. In this thesis, we concentrate on regression models. Regression models are popular statistical models for data analysis because of their desired properties, such as unbiasedness and minimum variance. The models use an ordinary least square estimator to determine the regression coefficients, which may suffer from multicollinearity. Multicollinearity refers to a situation in which a set of model parameters are highly linearly dependent, or the sample size is smaller than the number of parameters. To overcome this problem, two types of approaches are widely used.

The first approaches are the regularization techniques, where the model parameters are applied with certain constraints. Ridge and the lasso methods are two prominent regularization techniques [62]. The second approach is the dimensionality reduction methods such as the principal component regression [70] and the partial least square regression. The dimensionality reduction decomposes the model parameters into orthogonal directions, and only use some of them for modeling. These methods often have smaller variances than their counterparts, and thus are widely used. In this work, we use the principal component regression

technique for constructing a surrogate model for the error estimator.

The detailed adaptive greedy sampling algorithm utilizing the surrogate model is presented in Section 4.2.2. The first stage of the adaptive greedy sampling algorithm computes the error estimator over a randomly selected parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$ of cardinality c_0 . The algorithm uses these error estimator values $\{\varepsilon_i\}_{i=1}^{c_0}$ to build a surrogate model $\bar{\varepsilon}_0$. We solve this surrogate model for the entire parameter space and locates the c_k parameter groups corresponding to the c_k maximal values of the surrogate model. We construct a new parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{\rho_1; \dots; \rho_{c_k}\}$ composed of these c_k parameter groups. Once again, for each parameter group within the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$, the algorithm simulates the reduced models, computes the error estimator values $\{\varepsilon_i\}_{i=1}^{c_k}$, and generates a new surrogate model $\bar{\varepsilon}_k$. This process repeats itself for $k = 1, \dots, K$ iterations until the total number of parameter groups reaches c . Finally, the optimal parameter group ρ_I is the one that maximizes the error estimator within the parameter set

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}} = \hat{\mathcal{P}}_0 \cup \hat{\mathcal{P}}_1 \cup \hat{\mathcal{P}}_2 \cup \dots \cup \hat{\mathcal{P}}_K.$$

Thus, at the k th iteration, a surrogate model $\bar{\varepsilon}_k$ is constructed that approximates the error estimator over the entire parameter space \mathcal{P} . We define the surrogate model in the following. Suppose $\hat{\varepsilon} = [\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_{c_k}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{c_k \times 1}$ is the vector of error estimator values at the k th iteration. Since the parameters b, σ in the robust one-factor Hull-White model and the parameters $b, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, \alpha$ in the robust two-factor Hull-White model are assumed constant, we built the surrogate models with parameters $a(t)$ or $\theta(t)$ only. However, for the simplicity of notation, we use ρ to represent the parameters for the further calculations. Let $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k = [\rho_1; \dots; \rho_{c_k}] \in \mathbb{R}^{c_k \times m}$ be the matrix composed of c_k parameter vectors at the k th iteration. The rows of the matrix $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$ represent c_k parameter vectors, while the m columns represent m tenor points for the parameter vectors $a(t)$ or $\theta(t)$. We can fit a simple multiple regression model as

$$\hat{\varepsilon} = \hat{\mathcal{P}}_k \cdot \eta + err, \quad (4.9)$$

where $\eta = [\eta_1, \dots, \eta_m]^T$ is an array containing regression coefficients and err is an array of residuals. The least square estimate of η is obtained as

$$\hat{\eta} = \underset{\eta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\hat{\varepsilon} - \hat{\mathcal{P}}_k \cdot \eta\|_2^2 = \underset{\eta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\hat{\varepsilon} - \sum_{i=1}^m \rho_i \eta_i\|_2^2.$$

If c_k is not much larger than m , then the model may give weak predictions due to the risk of over-fitting for the parameter groups which are not used in model training. Also, if c_k is smaller than m , then the least square approach cannot produce a unique solution, restricting the use of the simple linear regression model. We may face this problem during the first few iterations of the adaptive greedy sampling algorithm, as we will have few error estimator values to build a reasonably accurate model. Thus, to overcome these problems, we implemented

the so called principal component regression technique that is based on principal component analysis.

The PCR technique is a dimension reduction technique in which m explanatory variables are replaced by p linearly uncorrelated variables called principal components. The dimension reduction is achieved by considering only a few relevant principal components. The PCR approach helps to reduce the problem of estimating m coefficients to the more simpler problem of determining p coefficients. In the following, we describe the method to construct a surrogate model at the k th iteration in detail.

Before performing the principal component analysis, we center both the response vector $\hat{\varepsilon}$ and the data matrix $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$. The PCR starts by performing a PCA of the matrix $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$. PCA is usually explained via an eigendecomposition of the covariance matrix. However, it can also be performed via a singular value decomposition of the data matrix [10]. For this, we compute an SVD

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k = \hat{\Phi} \hat{\Sigma} \hat{\Psi}^T,$$

$\hat{\Phi}$, and $\hat{\Psi}$ are the matrices composed of left and right singular vectors. The $\hat{\Sigma}$ contains the singular values. Then the principal components are the columns of the matrix $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k \hat{\Psi}$, and $\hat{\psi}_i \in \hat{\Psi}$ are the principal component directions. In [9] it is suggested that the first three or four principal components are enough to analyze the yield curve changes. Let $Z = \hat{\mathcal{P}}_k \hat{\Psi}_p = [\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k \hat{\psi}_1, \dots, \hat{\mathcal{P}}_k \hat{\psi}_p]$ be the matrix containing the first p principal components. We regress $\hat{\varepsilon}$ on these principal components via

$$\hat{\varepsilon} = Z\Omega + err,$$

where $\Omega = [\omega_1, \dots, \omega_p]^T$ is the vector containing the regression coefficients obtained using the principal components. The least square estimate for Ω is given as

$$\hat{\Omega} = \underset{\Omega}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\hat{\varepsilon} - Z\Omega\|_2^2 = \underset{\omega}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\hat{\varepsilon} - \sum_{i=1}^p z_i \omega_i\|_2^2.$$

We obtain the PCR estimate $\eta_{PCR} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ of the regression coefficients η as

$$\eta_{PCR} = \hat{\Psi}_p \hat{\Omega}$$

Finally, the value of the surrogate model for any parameter vector $a_\ell = [a_{\ell,1}, \dots, a_{\ell,m}]$ is

$$\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho_\ell) = \eta_1 a_{\ell,1} + \dots + \eta_m a_{\ell,m},$$

and similarly for any parameter vector $\theta_\ell = [\theta_{\ell,1}, \dots, \theta_{\ell,m}]$ is

$$\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho_\ell) = \eta_1 \theta_{\ell,1} + \dots + \eta_m \theta_{\ell,m}.$$

We can now use this surrogate model for the adaptive greedy sampling approach. The quality of this surrogate model depends on the selection of the principal components p . Thus, this thesis presents a procedure based on the error analysis to select the most relevant principal components. There are two errors associated with the principal component regression model, i.e., a projection error due to the principal component analysis and an error of prediction of the surrogate model. We could determine the projection error associated with the PCA in a similar way to the proper orthogonal decomposition, while the mean squared error of prediction (MSEP) or its square root is used to assess the quality of the regression model. The detailed error analysis is presented in Chapter 5. The total sampling error is given by (5.35)

$$\epsilon_{s\text{amp}} = \epsilon_{\text{PCA}} + \text{MSEP}_{K-\text{CVadj}}.$$

Using this error estimator and the procedure explained above, Algorithm 3 presents the methodology to construct a surrogate model using PCR.

Algorithm 3 (Surrogate model using PCR).

Input: Vector $\hat{\epsilon} = [\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_{c_k}]^T$, $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k = [\rho_1; \dots; \rho_{c_k}] \in \mathbb{R}^{c_k \times \bar{m}}$, number of principal components p .

Output: Vector of regression coefficients η .

Standardize $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$ and $\hat{\epsilon}$ with zero mean and variance one.

Compute the SVD $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k = \hat{\Phi} \hat{\Sigma} \hat{\Psi}$.

Let $\hat{\Sigma} = [\hat{\Sigma}_1, \dots, \hat{\Sigma}_k]$.

FOR $j = 1, \dots, \text{length}(\text{diag}(\hat{\Sigma}))$

 Compute (5.35) $\epsilon_{s\text{amp}} = \epsilon_{\text{PCA}} + \text{MSEP}_{K-\text{CVadj}}$.

 IF $\epsilon_{s\text{amp}} < \epsilon_{\text{tol}}^{\text{samp}}$

$p = j$

 Break

 END IF

END.

Construct the matrix $Z = \hat{\mathcal{P}}_k \hat{\Psi}_p = [\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k \hat{\psi}_1, \dots, \hat{\mathcal{P}}_k \hat{\psi}_p]$ composed of principal components.

Compute the least square regression using the principal components as independent variables: $\hat{\Omega} = \underset{\Omega}{\text{argmin}} \|\hat{\epsilon} - Z\Omega\|_2^2$.

Compute the PCR estimate $\eta_{\text{PCR}} = \hat{\Psi}_p \hat{\Omega}$ of the regression coefficients η .

4.2.2 Adaptive Greedy Sampling Algorithm

The adaptive greedy sampling algorithm 5 utilizes the designed surrogate model to locate optimal parameter groups adaptively at each greedy iteration $i = 1, \dots, I_{max}$. The first few steps of the algorithm resemble the classical greedy sampling approach. First the parameter group ρ_1 is selected from the parameter space \mathcal{P} and the reduced basis Q_1 is constructed. Furthermore, the algorithm randomly selects c_0 parameter groups and constructs a temporary parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0 = \{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_{c_0}\}$. For each parameter group in the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$, the algorithm determines a reduced model and computes an array of corresponding residual errors $\hat{\varepsilon}_0 = \{\varepsilon(\rho_1), \dots, \varepsilon(\rho_{c_0})\}$. Then a surrogate model for the error estimator $\bar{\varepsilon}$ is constructed based on the estimator values $\{\varepsilon(\rho_j)\}_{j=1}^{c_0}$, as discussed in Subsection 4.2.1. The obtained surrogate model is then simulated for the entire parameter space \mathcal{P} . Furthermore, we locate c_k parameter groups corresponding to the first c_k maximal values of the surrogate model. We then construct a new parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_{c_k}\}$ composed of these c_k parameter groups.

The algorithm determines a reduced model for each parameter group within the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$ and obtains an array of error estimator values $\hat{\varepsilon}_k = \{\varepsilon(\rho_1), \dots, \varepsilon(\rho_{c_k})\}$. Furthermore, we concatenate the set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$ and the set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$ to form a new parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}} = \hat{\mathcal{P}}_k \cup \hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$. Let $e_{sg} = \{\hat{\varepsilon}_0 \cup \dots \cup \hat{\varepsilon}_k\}$ be the set composed of all the error estimator values available at the k th iteration. The algorithm then uses this error estimator set e_{sg} to build a new surrogate model. The quality of the surrogate model increases with each iteration as we get more error estimator values. This process is repeated until the cardinality of the set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ reaches c , giving

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}} = \hat{\mathcal{P}}_0 \cup \hat{\mathcal{P}}_1 \cup \hat{\mathcal{P}}_2 \cup \dots \cup \hat{\mathcal{P}}_K.$$

Finally, the optimal parameter group ρ_I which maximizes the error estimator (4.7) is extracted from the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$. The full model is then solved for the optimal parameter group to update the snapshot matrix \hat{V} . Finally, a truncated singular value decomposition of the snapshot matrix is computed, and the first d left singular vectors are used to construct a new reduced basis Q_i . Note that typically it is not necessary to obtain a very accurate sampling using the designed surrogate model. Sampling the full model in the neighborhood of the parameter group with maximal error is sufficient to obtain good results. The pseudocode for the adaptive greedy sampling approach is presented in Algorithm 5. Starting from selecting the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$ to the construction of a new reduced basis Q , this complete process is repeated for I_{max} iterations or until the convergence.

Convergence criteria for the Adaptive Greedy Algorithm

In the classical greedy sampling approach, we used the residual error to observe the convergence of the algorithm, which estimates the relative error between the full model and the reduced model. However, in the adaptive greedy POD algorithm, we use an approxi-

mate model $\hat{\epsilon}_{\text{RM}}$ for the relative error ϵ_{RM} as a function of the residual error ϵ to monitor the convergence. This is more accurate than using only the residual error as a convergence criterion.

At each greedy iteration, the algorithm solves one full model for the optimal parameter group ρ_I to update the snapshot matrix and construct a new reduced basis. We can utilize this information for the construction of an approximate relative error model. We solve two reduced models for the optimal parameter group, one before and another after updating the reduced basis ($Q_{\text{bef}}, Q_{\text{aft}}$), and obtain respective error estimator values $\epsilon^{\text{bef}}(\rho_I)$ and $\epsilon^{\text{aft}}(\rho_I)$. Then we calculate the relative errors $\epsilon_{\text{RM}}^{\text{bef}}, \epsilon_{\text{RM}}^{\text{aft}}$ between the full model and the two reduced models constructed before and after updating the reduced basis. Here superscripts bef and aft denote the before and after updating the reduced basis. In this way, we get a set of error values E_p at each greedy iteration that we can use to construct an approximate model for the relative error based on the error estimator.

$$E_p = \{(\epsilon_{\text{RM},1}^{\text{bef}}, \epsilon_1^{\text{bef}}) \cup (\epsilon_{\text{RM},1}^{\text{aft}}, \epsilon_1^{\text{aft}}), \dots, (\epsilon_{\text{RM},i}^{\text{bef}}, \epsilon_i^{\text{bef}}) \cup (\epsilon_{\text{RM},i}^{\text{aft}}, \epsilon_i^{\text{aft}})\}. \quad (4.10)$$

We then construct an approximate model for the relative error based on the error estimator as

$$\log(\hat{\epsilon}_{\text{RM},i}) = \gamma_i \log(\epsilon) + \log\tau. \quad (4.11)$$

Setting $\mathcal{Y} = \log(\hat{\epsilon}_{\text{RM}})$, $\mathcal{X} = \log(\epsilon)$ and $\hat{\tau} = \log(\tau)$ we get

$$\mathcal{Y} = \gamma_e \mathcal{X} + \hat{\tau},$$

where γ_e is the slope of the linear model and $\hat{\tau}$ is the intercept with the logarithmic axis $\log(y)$. The algorithm 4 shows an approximate model for the relative error to monitor the convergence of the adaptive greedy algorithm.

After each greedy iteration, we get more data points in the error set E_p , which increases the accuracy of the error model, provided that the linear model assumption is validated. In Chapter 6, we illustrate with the obtained results that this linear model assumption is sufficient to achieve an acceptable approximate relative error model. We then use this error model in the adaptive greedy sampling to monitor the convergence of the algorithm.

Algorithm 4 (An approximate model for the relative error to monitor the convergence of the adaptive greedy algorithm).

Input: Optimal parameter group ρ_I , reduced basis Q_1

Output: An approximate relative error model $\hat{\epsilon}_{\text{RM}}$.

FOR $i = 2, \dots, I_{\text{max}}$

Solve the full model for ρ_I and store results in V_i .

Solve the reduced model for ρ_I using Q_{i-1} and store result in \bar{V}_i .

Compute $\epsilon_{\text{RM},i}^{\text{bef}}$ and ϵ_i^{bef} using the reduced model obtained with Q_{i-1} .

Construct a snapshot matrix \hat{V} by concatenating the solutions V_ℓ for $\ell = 1, \dots, i$.

Compute a truncated SVD of the matrix \hat{V} and construct Q_i (See Algorithm 1).

Generate a new reduced model using Q_i .

Solve the reduced model for ρ_I and store results in \bar{V}_{i+1} .

Compute $\epsilon_{\text{RM},i}^{\text{aft}}$ and ϵ_i^{aft} using the reduced model obtained with Q_i .

Construct error set $E_p = \{(\epsilon_{\text{RM},1}^{\text{bef}}, \epsilon_1^{\text{bef}}) \cup (\epsilon_{\text{RM},1}^{\text{aft}}, \epsilon_1^{\text{aft}}), \dots, (\epsilon_{\text{RM},i}^{\text{bef}}, \epsilon_i^{\text{bef}}) \cup (\epsilon_{\text{RM},i}^{\text{aft}}, \epsilon_i^{\text{aft}})\}$.

Construct an approximate relative error model using error set E_p : $\log(\hat{\epsilon}_{\text{RM},i}) = \gamma_i \log(\epsilon) + \log \tau$.

END FOR

The table shows list of symbols used in Algorithms 4 and 5. Considering the adaptive

Table 4.1: List of symbols used in Algorithm 4 and 5

ρ	group of model parameters $\{\theta(t), \alpha, b, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, \gamma\}$;
c_k	number of parameters selected adaptively based on surrogate modeling;
V	solution obtained by solving a full model;
c_0	Number of randomly selected parameter groups to initiate the algorithm;
ϵ	error estimator;
ϵ^k	set comprised of error estimator values at k th iteration;
e_{sg}	set composed of all error estimator values at the k th iteration;
$\bar{\epsilon}$	surrogate error model;
$\hat{\mathcal{P}}$	parameter set used to obtain the optimal parameter group;
$n(\hat{\mathcal{P}})$	cardinality of the set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$;
ρ_I	optimal parameter group which maximizes the error estimator;
ϵ_{RM}	relative error between a reduced model and a full model;
\bar{V}	solution obtained using a reduced model;
\hat{V}	snapshot matrix;
E_p	error set;
$\hat{\epsilon}_{\text{RM}}$	error model as an approximate error for the exact error ϵ_{RM} ;
$e_{\text{tol}}^{\text{max}}$	tolerance for the relative error, greedy iterations terminates if $\bar{\epsilon}_{\text{RM}} < e_{\text{tol}}^{\text{max}}$;
γ_e	slope of the error model;
$\hat{\tau}$	intersection with the logarithmic axis $\log(y)$.

greedy algorithm runs for I_{max} iterations, a large portion of the computational cost associated with the algorithm arises from the full model simulations for $(I_{max}+1)$ times. The second most expensive step is computing the reduced model solutions and their residual errors for $(c_0 + k \times n(\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k) + 2) \times I_{max}$ times, where c_0 reduced model computations to initiate the algorithm, $k \times n(\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k)$ to construct surrogate models, and two more computations for an approximate relative error model. Compared to these two aforementioned tasks, the construction of the principal component regression model for kI_{max} times is negligible. The adaptive greedy sampling approach is summarized in Algorithm 5.

Algorithm 5 (Adaptive greedy sampling algorithm).

Input: Maximal number of iterations I_{max} , maximal number of parameter groups c , number of adaptive candidates c_k , parameter space \mathcal{P} , tolerance e_{tol}^{max} .

Output: Q .

Choose first parameter group ρ_1 from \mathcal{P} .

Simulate the full model for the parameter group ρ_1 and store the results in V_1 .

Compute a truncated SVD of the matrix V_1 , construct Q_1 and generate a reduced model.

FOR $i = 2, \dots, I_{max}$

Randomly select a set of parameter groups $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0 = \{\rho_1, \rho_2, \dots, \rho_{c_0}\} \subset \mathcal{P}$.

FOR $j = 1, \dots, c_0$

Solve the reduced model for parameter group ρ_j with reduced basis Q_{i-1} .

Compute the error estimator $\varepsilon(\rho_j)$.

END

Let $\hat{\varepsilon}_0 = \{\varepsilon(\rho_1), \dots, \varepsilon(\rho_{c_0})\}$ be error estimators for $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$.

Let $k = 1$ and $e_{sg} = \hat{\varepsilon}_0$.

WHILE $n(\hat{\mathcal{P}}) < c$

Construct a surrogate model $\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho)$ using the values e_{sg} .

Compute the values $\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho)$ of the surrogate model over \mathcal{P} .

Determine first c_k maximal values of $\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho)$ and parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k = \{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_{c_k}\}$.

For $x = 1, \dots, n(\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k)$

Solve the reduced model for parameter group ρ_x .

Compute the error estimator $\varepsilon(\rho_x)$.

END

Let $\hat{\varepsilon}_k = \{\varepsilon(\rho_1), \dots, \varepsilon(\rho_{c_k})\}$ be the error estimators for $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$.

Update $e_{\text{sg}} = \{\hat{\varepsilon}_0 \cup \dots \cup \hat{\varepsilon}_k\}$.

Construct new parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}} = \hat{\mathcal{P}}_0 \cup \hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$.

$k = k + 1$.

END

Find $\rho_I = \underset{\rho \in \hat{\mathcal{P}}}{\operatorname{argmax}} \varepsilon(\rho)$.

IF $i > 2$ and $\hat{\varepsilon}_{\text{RM},i} \leq e_{\text{tol}}^{\text{max}}$, set $Q = Q_{i-1}$, STOP.

Solve the full model for ρ_I and store results in V_i .

Solve a reduced model for ρ_I using Q_{i-1} and store result in \bar{V}_i .

Compute $\varepsilon_{\text{RM},i}^{\text{bef}}$ and $\varepsilon_i^{\text{bef}}$ using the reduced model obtained with Q_{i-1} .

Construct a snapshot matrix \hat{V} by concatenating the solutions V_ℓ for $\ell = 1, \dots, i$.

Compute a truncated SVD of the matrix \hat{V} and construct Q_i (See Algorithm 1).

Generate a new reduced model using Q_i .

Solve the reduced model for ρ_I and store results in \bar{V}_{i+1} .

Compute $\varepsilon_{\text{RM},i}^{\text{aft}}$ and $\varepsilon_i^{\text{aft}}$ using the reduced model obtained with Q_i .

Construct error set $E_p = \{(\varepsilon_{\text{RM},1}^{\text{bef}}, \varepsilon_1^{\text{bef}}) \cup (\varepsilon_{\text{RM},1}^{\text{aft}}, \varepsilon_1^{\text{aft}}), \dots, (\varepsilon_{\text{RM},i}^{\text{bef}}, \varepsilon_i^{\text{bef}}) \cup (\varepsilon_{\text{RM},i}^{\text{aft}}, \varepsilon_i^{\text{aft}})\}$.

Construct an approximate relative error model using error set E_p : $\log(\hat{\varepsilon}_{\text{RM},i}) =$

$\gamma_i \log(\varepsilon) + \log \tau$.

END

4.2.3 Computational Cost

The adaptive greedy approach at each iteration conducts the following steps to obtain a reduced basis. It is initiated by solving c_0 reduced models to obtain the residual errors $\{\varepsilon_j\}_{j=1}^{c_0}$. These error estimator values are used to construct a surrogate model that locates c_k parameter groups. The process is repeated until the total cardinality of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ reaches c , i.e., for k iterations.

Let t_{ρ_I} be the computing time required to locate the optimal parameter group ρ_I by constructing a surrogate model. t_{ρ_I} is nothing but the time required to complete a while loop outline in Algorithm 5. We call this while loop a surrogate model loop. The surrogate model loop starts by constructing a surrogate model using the error estimator values available within the set e_{sg} . Let the time require to build one surrogate model is t_{SM} . Then the constructed surrogate model is solved for the entire parameter space. We denote the computing time to solve the surrogate model by t_{SM}^{ev} . Furthermore, at each iteration of the surrogate model loop, we have to solve c_k reduced models for c_k parameter groups. Thus, the computing time t_{ρ_I} can be given as

$$t_{\rho_I} = k(c_k \times t_{RM} + t_{SM} + t_{SM}^{ev}),$$

where t_{RM} denotes the time required to solve one reduced model. Once the optimal parameter group is procured, the algorithm solves one full model for the optimal parameter group, updates the snapshot matrix, and computes a truncated singular value decomposition of the updated snapshot matrix. Finally, an error model \bar{e}_{RM} is built to monitor the convergence of the greedy algorithm. Therefore, the total computational time required to complete an adaptive greedy process can be given as

$$T_Q^{AG} \approx \left[c_0 \times t_{RM} + \underbrace{k(c_k \times t_{RM} + t_{SM} + t_{SM}^{ev})}_{t_{\rho_I}} + t_{FM} + t_{SVD} + 2t_{RM}^{aft,bef} + t_{EM} \right] \times i, \quad (4.12)$$

where t_{EM} is the time required to build an error model and the term $2t_{RM}^{aft,bef}$ shows the computational time needed to solve the reduced model after and before updating the reduced basis.

Chapter 5

Error Analysis

This chapter presents a detailed error analysis for the model order reduction framework designed in chapter 4. In most cases, the exact solutions of mathematical models are unknown, and they incorporate some modeling errors. We have no other way to use differential equations in mathematical modeling but to compute their approximate solutions and analyze them. However, the approximate solution contains some numerical errors. It is necessary to reduce these numerical errors as much as possible to improve the level of accuracy of the numerical solutions. A mathematical model defined here is a partial differential equation with appropriate boundary conditions and a known terminal condition. To solve this system, we have designed an approximate solution by discretizing the PDE. The approximation error associated with this process is called a discretization error. Furthermore, to reduce the computational cost and time, the model order reduction approach based on the proper orthogonal decomposition method has been implemented. This method solves the full model for some training parameters to obtain a reduced basis. Finally, the FM is projected onto the RB to get the reduced model. The POD method links with the projection error, which depends on the excluded singular values while generating the RB. To know how well the reduced model approximates the full model, we have to determine a model order reduction error. In this work, the training parameters are chosen based on either the classical greedy sampling or the adaptive greedy sampling approaches. Thus, we have to consider a sampling error associated with the sampling algorithms as well.

Figure 5.1 shows the model hierarchy to obtain the reduced model with associated errors in each stage. Usually, the formulated mathematical model is not an exact representation of the underlying physical phenomenon. The physical process being modeled may be overly complex, which requires many simplifying assumptions. In such situations, it will be impractical to create an exact mathematical model. Hence, the resulting model may be a simplified version of the underlying physical process that creates the modeling error. However, it is not easy to compute and quantify the modeling error, maybe because of a lack of sufficient knowledge or uncertainty in the physical phenomenon. In most cases, it is computationally convenient and

enough to consider the simplified model. Thus, in this thesis, we assume the solution of the partial differential equation as the *true solution*, i.e., the modeling error ϵ_m has been neglected. Let V be the exact solution for the mathematical model \mathcal{M} . Let V_h be the solution obtained

Figure 5.1: A model hierarchy showing errors arising in the analysis of the mathematical model.

using the discretized model \mathcal{M}_h with the mesh size h . Then the approximate solution V_h encompasses the discretization error

$$\epsilon_h = \frac{\|V - V_h\|}{\|V\|}. \quad (5.1)$$

Furthermore, the reduced model \mathcal{M}_h^d of dimension d is obtained. Let the \bar{V} be the result obtained from the reduced model. The reduced model error can be then given as

$$\epsilon_{\text{RM}} = \frac{\|V_h - \bar{V}\|}{\|V_h\|}. \quad (5.2)$$

The result obtained using the reduced model encloses the total numerical error, and based on that, we can write the final output equation with numerical errors

$$\|V - \bar{V}\| \approx \|V - V_h\| + \|V_h - \bar{V}\|. \quad (5.3)$$

The reduced model is obtained based on the proper orthogonal decomposition approach, which induces a projection error ϵ_{POD} . The total model order reduction error ϵ_d is then the sum of a projection error ϵ_{POD} , and a reduced model error ϵ_{RM}

$$\epsilon_d \approx \epsilon_{\text{RM}} + \epsilon_{\text{POD}}.$$

We have used a sampling approach to select the most relevant parameters, which produces a reasonably accurate reduced basis. These sampling algorithms contribute to an additional sampling error. Thus, the total simulation error ϵ_T can be estimated by the discretization error ϵ_h , a sampling error ϵ_{samp} and the model order reduction error ϵ_d as

$$\epsilon_T \approx \epsilon_m + \epsilon_h + \epsilon_{\text{RM}} + \epsilon_{\text{POD}} + \epsilon_{\text{samp}}. \quad (5.4)$$

We aim to achieve the reduced model and solve the financial instrument for the entire parameter space such that the total error is minimized. Let the total error be the cost function to be minimized, which mainly depends on the grid size h , the reduced dimension d , and the quality of training parameters c used to obtain the reduced basis. A general strategy to obtain a better approximate solution is by steady refinement of the model parameters that control these numerical errors. In this work, we optimize these variables by minimizing the associated errors. The discretization error can be reduced by the proper choice of the mesh size h . Likewise, the model order reduction error can be controlled by choosing a proper reduced dimension d , while the sampling error is mitigated by the proper choice of the training parameters c . We aim to obtain these cost parameters such that the total error is reduced and less than the user-defined tolerance e_{tol} i.e.,

$$\min_{\{h,d,c\}} \epsilon_h + \epsilon_d + \epsilon_{\text{samp}}, \quad (5.5)$$

$$\epsilon_T \leq e_{\text{tol}}.$$

Another important issue is to know the contribution and the effect of each defined error on the total error (5.3). Sensitivity analysis enables identifying the errors that have the most significant influence on the model output. It provides useful insight into which numerical error contributes most to the variability of the model output. Such information will help to improve the model by selecting the appropriate grid size h , the reduced dimension d , and the optimal sampling parameters c . The sensitivity approach presented in Subsection 5.4 ranks the numerical errors according to their contribution to the total error and helps efficiently allocate the computational resources. The extra computational effort can be spent on the cost parameters most sensitive to the final output at the expense of the computational cost required to obtain the least sensitive parameters.

5.1 Discretization of a PDE

For the discretization of a PDE, we use a finite dimension grid $\left(\prod_{k=1}^{sd} [r_k, u_k]\right) \times [0, T]$ in sd spatial dimensions and one temporal dimension. The simulation time $[0, T]$ is divided into N equal intervals, $[t^n, t^{n-1}]$ where $n = 1, \dots, N$. We have used the Crank–Nicolson method for the one-factor Hull-White model and the implicit time-stepping scheme for the two-factor Hull-White model. Three numerical errors occur due to the discretization of a PDE, and solving the system of linear equations are the round-off error, iterative error, and discretization error. Round-off error can be mitigated easily by using more digits in the computation. The iteration error can often be reduced by simply running additional iterations or monitoring convergence of the solution residuals. The discretization error is the most challenging aspect of the numerical error to analyze, which is comparatively more significant than others. In this work, we neglect the round-off error and the iteration error. To obtain an optimal solution of the discrete model, one must determine the best suitable time step and the grid size. We construct an adaptive time-stepping scheme to achieve the optimal time step, which solves the model at the desired accuracy but with low computational cost while the grid size is selected such that the discretization error is less than a specified user-defined tolerance.

5.1.1 Time Discretization

Adaptive time-stepping is beneficial for the efficient and accurate solution of the equation. The error associated with the time discretization can be controlled by varying the time step τ . We have used the Richardson extrapolation-based adaptive time-stepping approach to obtain the solution with minimum computational efforts subjected to the prescribed tolerance e_{tol}^t [111, 112]. The approximation method used to solve (3.13) or (3.20) should compute a solution at each time step such that the error is less than the prescribed tolerance.

We have a PDE of the form

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = L(r, u)V,$$

where $L(r, u)$ is a linear differential operator containing all spatial derivatives. The idea is to obtain the optimal time step τ_{opt} such that it minimizes the relative error between the exact solution V and the solution obtained using the time step τ_{opt}

$$\epsilon_t = \|V - V_h(\tau_{opt})\|.$$

Assuming the numerical method used is of order p in time, the exact value of the PDE V , and the approximated value $V_h(\tau)$ with the time step τ , the error for the approximation is given as [111]

$$V = V_h(\tau) - C\tau^{p+1} - \mathcal{O}(\tau^{p+2}).$$

By neglecting higher order terms, we can determine the value of the constant C as

$$C = \frac{V_h(\tau) - V}{\tau^{p+1}}. \quad (5.6)$$

Let $V_h(K\tau)$ be the solution obtained using the time step $K\tau$

$$V = V_h(K\tau) - CK^{p+1}\tau^{p+1} - \mathcal{O}(\tau^{p+2}). \quad (5.7)$$

Substituting (5.7) into (5.6), and neglecting the higher order terms, we get

$$\begin{aligned} C &= \frac{V_h(\tau) - V_h(K\tau) + CK^{p+1}\tau^{p+1}}{\tau^{p+1}} \\ C &= \frac{V_h(K\tau) - V_h(\tau)}{\tau^{p+1}(K^{p+1} - 1)}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.8)$$

We calculate τ_{opt} such that the relative error ϵ_t is less than the user-defined tolerance

$$\epsilon_t = \|V - V_h(\tau_{opt})\| \leq e_{tol}^t,$$

where

$$V_h(\tau_{opt}) = V + C\tau_{opt}^{p+1} + \mathcal{O}(\tau_{opt}^{p+2}).$$

Thus, we get the relative error estimate $\hat{\epsilon}_t$ by substituting C as

$$\|V - V_h(\tau_{opt})\| \approx \left(\frac{\tau_{opt}}{\tau}\right)^{p+1} \frac{\|V_h(\tau) - V_h(K\tau)\|}{K^{p+1} - 1} = \hat{\epsilon}_t.$$

To determine the optimal step size we set

$$\hat{\epsilon}_t = e_{tol}^t,$$

which yields

$$\tau_{opt} \approx \tau \left[\frac{e_{tol}^t (K^{p+1} - 1)}{\|V_h(\tau) - V_h(K\tau)\|} \right]^{1/p+1}. \quad (5.9)$$

Since the roundoff or iterative convergence errors that arise while solving the system of linear equations are negligible compared to the discretization error, we can neglect them [71]. We have used the Crank–Nicolson method for the one-factor Hull-White model, a second-order method in time, i.e., $p = 2$. On the other hand, the implicit method used for the two-factor Hull-White model is a first-order method in time, i.e., $p = 1$. The adaptive time-stepping strategy aims to find the time step that will achieve the desired accuracy at a relatively low cost [6, 31]. Thus, we have to determine the largest possible time step that satisfies (5.9). An automatic time step control can be executed as shown in Algorithm 6. The step size

controller is designed on the assumption that the largest possible step size should be selected. Based on the optimal time step τ_{opt} (5.9), there are two scenarios for step size controller. If $\tau_{opt} > \tau$, we can say that the tolerance e_{tol}^t is satisfied, and no further step size adaptation is required. However, if $\tau_{opt} < \tau$, we cannot say that the tolerance is satisfied, and we have to subdivide the current step size into K sub-levels as

$$K = \text{round}\left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{opt}}\right).$$

Thus, we run the step size controller until the optimal step size τ_{opt} becomes larger than the step size τ .

Algorithm 6 (Automatic time step control).

Input: Full model \mathcal{M}_h , maximum time step τ_{max} , e_{tol}^t , K , p .

Output: τ_{opt} .

Solve the full model with the time step τ_{max} and store the result in $V_h(\tau_{max})$.

$\tau_{opt} = 0, \tau = 1$.

WHILE $\tau_{opt} < \tau$

Compute a smaller step size $\tau = \tau_{max}/K$.

Solve the full model with the time step τ and store the result in $V_h(\tau)$.

Compute an optimal time step $\tau_{opt} \approx \tau \left[\frac{e_{tol}^t(K^{p+1}-1)}{\|V_h(\tau) - V_h(K\tau)\|} \right]^{1/p+1}$.

Increment $K = \text{round}(\tau/\tau_{opt}) + 1$.

END.

Set $\tau_{opt} = \tau$.

The algorithm calculates τ_{opt} at each iteration and checks whether it is greater than τ . It is important to note that we have designed this algorithm to select the time step such that all key time points are achievable, i.e., coupon dates, put dates, or valuation dates.

5.1.2 Spatial Discretization

The largest numerical error while solving the full model is the error related to the resolution of the spatial grid called discretization error. To decrease this discretization error and gain confidence in the accuracy of results, mesh refinement studies are usually performed. The basic idea is to solve the model progressively on finer meshes and compare results. A discretization error estimate can be used to monitor the model's steady refinement and identify

the desired refinement grid sizes. The flowchart 5.2 shows the adaptive refinement scheme. In this work we define a discretization error estimator based on estimating the exact solution

Figure 5.2: Mesh refinement method

for the differential equation, which is higher-order accurate than the underlying numerical solution [97]. We implemented the Richardson extrapolation approach that estimates the mathematical model’s exact solution using the formal rate of convergence of a discretization method and two or three different solutions on systematically refined meshes [98]. One would argue that the computation of multiple simulations in the asymptotic range of the full model increases the computational burden. However, the main advantage of the Richardson approach is that it can be used as a post-processing technique and can be applied to any discretization method (e.g., finite element or finite difference). It estimates the total error, including locally generated errors and those transported from other regions of the domain. Also, the method can be used for a local quantity or a derived system response quantity. Given these advantages, the Richardson extrapolation approach has been implemented for different applications in the literature [3, 69, 86].

Consider a discretization error as

$$\epsilon_h = |V_h - V|, \tag{5.10}$$

where V is the exact solution of the mathematical model and V_h is a solution obtained on a

grid spacing h using a discretized model. In the case of a two-dimensional system

$$h = \left[\frac{1}{E} \sum_{i=1}^E A_i^{(e)} \right]^{1/2},$$

where E is the number of elements, and $A_i^{(e)}$ is the area of i th element. For the smooth solution with no discontinuities, we can expand the numerical solution V_h using either Taylor or power series expansion

$$V_h = V + \xi_p h^p + \xi_{p+1} h^{p+1} + \xi_{p+2} h^{p+2} + \dots,$$

which leads to the discretization error

$$\epsilon_h = |V_h - V| = \xi_p h^p + \xi_{p+1} h^{p+1} + \xi_{p+2} h^{p+2} + \dots = \sum_{p=P_f} \xi_p h^p = \xi_{p_f} h^{p_f} + \text{H.O.T.},$$

where p_f is the formal order of accuracy determined by the preferred discretization scheme and is the first term's power in the series and H.O.T. denotes neglected higher order terms. Neglecting the higher order terms, the discretization error estimate is given by

$$\bar{\epsilon}_h \approx \xi_{p_f} h^{p_f} + \mathcal{O}(h^{p_f+1}).$$

To accurately estimate the discretization error $\bar{\epsilon}_h$, the H.O.T. exclusion introduces the assumption that the numerical solutions are asymptotic. Richardson extrapolation also demands that all other sources of numerical errors (e.g., round-off error, iterative convergence errors) are negligible compared to the discretization error [71].

Consider a grid refinement index g as the ratio of coarse to fine mesh size. It is recommended to use the grid refinement ratio between 1.5 to 2 as it allows to distinguish the discretization error from other error sources [22].

$$g = \frac{h_{\text{coarse}}}{h_{\text{fine}}} > 1.$$

Let $h_{\text{fine}} = h$, and $h_{\text{coarse}} = gh$. According to the power series, the discretized solutions obtained for two mesh sizes are

$$V_h = V + \xi_p h^p + \xi_{p+1} h^{p+1} + \xi_{p+2} h^{p+2} + \dots, \quad (5.11)$$

and

$$V_{gh} = V + \xi_p g^p h^p + \xi_{p+1} g^{p+1} h^{p+1} + \xi_{p+2} g^{p+2} h^{p+2} + \dots \quad (5.12)$$

Subtracting (5.12) from (5.11), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
V\left(\frac{g^p - 1}{g^p}\right) &= V_h - \frac{V_{gh}}{g^p} + \xi_{p+1}h^{p+1}(g-1) + \dots, \\
V &= \frac{g^p V_h - V_{gh}}{g^p - 1} + \frac{\xi_{p+1}h^{p+1}g^p(g-1)}{g^p - 1} + \dots, \\
V &= \frac{g^p V_h - V_{gh} + V_h - V_h}{g^p - 1} + \frac{\xi_{p+1}h^{p+1}g^p(g-1)}{g^p - 1} + \dots, \\
V &= V_h + \frac{V_h - V_{gh}}{g^p - 1} + \frac{\xi_{p+1}h^{p+1}g^p(g-1)}{g^p - 1} + \dots.
\end{aligned}$$

Neglecting the higher order terms, the Richardson extrapolation estimate of the exact solution is

$$V = V_h + \frac{V_h - V_{gh}}{g^p - 1} + \mathcal{O}(h^{p+1}), \quad (5.13)$$

and substituting (5.13) in (5.10), we get the discretization error estimator as, see [97],

$$\bar{\epsilon}_h = |V_h - V| = \left| \frac{V_h - V_{gh}}{g^p - 1} \right|. \quad (5.14)$$

To access the confidence in the discretization error estimate (5.14), it is necessary to define the observed order of accuracy \hat{p} [97]. The requirement of the reliability of the discretization error estimate is that the solutions are in the asymptotic range. To demonstrate that the asymptotic range for different solutions has been achieved, we must have at least three different discretized solutions with three different mesh sizes. We further calculate the observed order using these discretized solutions over a range of meshes. According to [22], when the observed order of accuracy is equal to the formal order of accuracy, we can have a high degree of confidence in the error estimator. We can determine the observed order of accuracy as follows. Consider three different mesh sizes h_1 , h_2 and h_3 such that

$$g_{12} = \frac{h_2}{h_1} > 1 \quad g_{23} = \frac{h_3}{h_2} > 1.$$

Let $h_1 = h$ then $h_2 = g_{12}h$ and $h_3 = g_{23}g_{12}h$. According to the power series

$$V_1 = V + \xi_p h^p + \xi_{p+1} h^{p+1} + \dots, \quad (5.15)$$

$$V_2 = V + \xi_p g_{12}^p h^p + \xi_{p+1} g_{12}^{p+1} h^{p+1} + \dots, \quad (5.16)$$

$$V_3 = V + \xi_p (g_{23}g_{12})^p h^p + \xi_{p+1} (g_{23}g_{12})^{p+1} h^{p+1} + \dots, \quad (5.17)$$

Subtracting (5.15) from (5.16) and (5.16) from (5.17) and setting $\hat{p} \approx p$

$$V_3 - V_2 = \xi_{\hat{p}} h^{\hat{p}} (g_{23}^{\hat{p}} g_{12}^{\hat{p}} - g_{12}^{\hat{p}}) + \mathcal{O}(h^{\hat{p}+1}), \quad (5.18)$$

$$V_2 - V_1 = \xi_{\hat{p}} h^{\hat{p}} (g_{12}^{\hat{p}} - 1) + \mathcal{O}(h^{\hat{p}+1}). \quad (5.19)$$

Dividing (5.18) by (5.19) and neglecting higher order terms

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{V_3 - V_2}{V_2 - V_1} &= \frac{g_{23}^{\hat{p}} g_{12}^{\hat{p}} - g_{12}^{\hat{p}}}{g_{12}^{\hat{p}} - 1}, \\ \frac{V_3 - V_2}{g_{23}^{\hat{p}} - 1} &= g_{12}^{\hat{p}} \left(\frac{V_2 - V_1}{g_{12}^{\hat{p}} - 1} \right). \end{aligned}$$

We can determine \hat{p} by a direct substitution iterative process as follows

$$\hat{p}_{k+1} = \frac{\ln \left[(g_{12}^{\hat{p}_k} - 1) \left(\frac{V_3 - V_2}{V_2 - V_1} \right) + g_{12}^{\hat{p}_k} \right]}{\ln(g_{12} g_{23})}, \quad (5.20)$$

where an initial guess for \hat{p} can be used as the formal order of accuracy. The following simple algorithm 7 shows the procedure to compute the observed order of accuracy. It converges once the change in two subsequent \hat{p}_{k+1} and \hat{p}_k is not significant.

Algorithm 7 (Algorithm to estimate the observed order of accuracy).

Input: $V_1, V_2, V_3, \hat{p}_1 = p_f$.

Output: \hat{p} .

Set $\hat{p}_1 = p_f$.

$\Delta V = (V_3 - V_2)/(V_2 - V_1)$.

$k = 1$.

WHILE $\Delta \hat{p} < 10^{-3}$

 Compute (5.20): $\hat{p}_{k+1} = \ln \left[(g_{12}^{\hat{p}_k} - 1) \Delta V + g_{12}^{\hat{p}_k} \right] / \ln(g_{12} g_{23})$.

$\Delta p = \hat{p}_{k+1} - \hat{p}_k$.

END

Set $\hat{p} = \hat{p}_k$

Substituting $p = \hat{p}$ and $g = g_{12}$ in (5.14) leads to a discretization error estimate [97]

$$\bar{\epsilon}_h = \frac{1}{(g_{12}^{\hat{p}} - 1)} \left| \frac{V_1 - V_2}{V_1} \right|. \quad (5.21)$$

When the observed order of accuracy \hat{p} matches the formal order of accuracy p_f , we have high confidence that this error estimate is accurate. However, it is more common to witness that the observed order of accuracy does not match the formal order of accuracy [86]. In such cases, the error estimator is not much reliable. It may be due to the failure of obtaining the solutions within asymptotic range or the lack of additional information. Also, the implemented boundary conditions and the terminal/initial conditions change the observed order of accuracy. However, we can fix this problem by converting the error estimator into an *epistemic uncertainty* estimator [97]. Epistemic uncertainties are different from random or aleatory uncertainties, as epistemic uncertainties arise due to the lack of knowledge. A grid convergence index (GCI) measures how far the computed value is away from the asymptotic numerical value. Roache initially developed the GCI for uniform reporting of grid convergence studies [94], which was later evolved into a discretization uncertainty estimator by computational fluid dynamics community like AIAA [22, 27, 95]. The GCI converts the error estimate into an error or uncertainty band, which is appropriate when one does not have a high degree of confidence in the error estimate. A small value of the GCI indicates that the computation is within the asymptotic range [96]. The GCI for the fine grid solution is given as [94]

$$\text{GCI} = \frac{F_s}{g_{12}^{\hat{p}} - 1} \left| \frac{V_1 - V_2}{V_1} \right|, \quad (5.22)$$

where F_s is the factor of safety and given as:

- $F_s = 3$ if the observed order of accuracy is calculated using two different solutions.
- $F_s = 1.25$ if the observed order of accuracy is calculated using three different solutions and when the formal order agrees with the observed order within 10%.

We cannot ensure whether the estimated exact solution by Richardson extrapolation truly matches the exact solution of mathematical model. Thus, it is beneficial to use the factor of safety to avoid the failure of the designed error estimator, as described above. For the first case, one cannot guaranty that the solutions obtained with only two grid sizes are within the asymptotic range. Thus, it is recommended to use the GCI with caution. If the solutions are far from the asymptotic range, then all approaches for the discretization error estimators are unreliable. Thus, [97] suggests using the factor of safety as 3. In the second case, if the formal order of accuracy matches the observed order of accuracy, then it is recommended to use the factor of safety as 1.25, as it will have minimal effect on the estimator. In this thesis, when \hat{p} agrees p_f within 10%, then the factor of safety of 1.25 is used.

Algorithm 8 shows the steps to obtain the suitable full model dimension. The algorithm is initiated by reasonably moderate grid size h_1^{init} . We construct two new grid sizes h_2, h_3 based on the grid refinement ratios g_{12}, g_{23} . Furthermore, a full model is solved for h_1, h_2, h_3 to determine the observed order of accuracy \hat{p} . Once we calculate \hat{p} , the algorithm computes

the discretization error estimator $\bar{\epsilon}_h$ and checks it against the user-defined tolerance e_{tol}^h . The algorithm converges if $\bar{\epsilon}_h < e_{tol}^h$ else, it refines h_1 , and the process repeats itself until the convergences. If the convergence does not achieve, it stops after K iterations, and the last grid size is used to construct the full model.

Algorithm 8 (Algorithm to select the full model dimension).

Input: Initial step size h_1^{init} , e_{tol}^h , $g_{12}, g_{23} > 1.3$.

Output: h_1 .

Set $h_1 = h_1^{init}$.

FOR $i = 1, \dots, K$

Solve the full model with a grid size h_1 and store the result in V_1 .

Compute $h_2 = g_{12}h_1$ and $h_3 = g_{23}g_{12}h_1$

Solve the full model with h_2 and h_3 and store the results in V_2 and V_3 respectively.

Calculate \hat{p} using Algorithm 6.

Compute the discretization error estimator given by (5.21) $\bar{\epsilon}_h = \frac{1}{(g_{12}^{\hat{p}} - 1)} \left| \frac{V_1 - V_2}{V_1} \right|$.

IF $\bar{\epsilon}_h < e_{tol}^h$

break.

END.

Refine the mesh and choose a finer grid size h_1 .

END.

5.2 Model Order Reduction Error

We have implemented the snapshot-based proper orthogonal decomposition method for model order reduction of an underlying PDE. POD method represents the PDE solution in the space spanned by reduced basis. The reduced basis is obtained by a linear combination of the snapshots generated by solving the full model for some training parameters.

Let \mathcal{X} be the Hilbert space given with an inner product $(\cdot, \cdot)_{\mathcal{X}}$ and a norm $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{X}}$. Let $V_1, V_2, \dots, V_k \in \mathcal{X}$ be the snapshots obtained by solving a full model. We consider

$$\mathcal{V} = \text{span}\{V_1, \dots, V_k\},$$

as a span of the snapshots $\{V_j\}_{j=1}^k$, provided at least one of them is non-zero. Let $\{\phi_i\}_{i=1}^d$ denote the orthonormal basis of \mathcal{V} with $d = \dim(\mathcal{V})$. The goal of the proper orthogonal decomposition is to identify the most important characteristics of an ensemble of snapshots by computing the optimal orthonormal basis. Now we can represent each member of the snapshot as

$$V_j = \sum_{i=1}^d (V_j, \phi_i) \mathcal{X} \phi_i, \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, k. \quad (5.23)$$

The proper orthogonal decomposition approach obtains the reduced basis such that for every $\ell \in \{1, \dots, d\}$, the mean square error between the snapshot V_j and the corresponding ℓ th partial sum of (5.23) is minimized on average

$$\min_{\{\phi_i\}_{i=1}^{\ell}} \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k \left\| V_j - \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} (V_j, \phi_i) \mathcal{X} \phi_i \right\|^2,$$

where

$$(\phi_i, \phi_j) = \delta_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i = j, \\ 0, & \text{if } i \neq j. \end{cases} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq \ell, 1 \leq j \leq i.$$

We can obtain the reduced basis $\{\phi_i\}_{i=1}^d$ by computing a truncated singular value decomposition of the snapshot matrix \hat{V} [43]

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{V} &= \sum_{i=1}^k \Sigma_i \phi_i \psi_i^T, \\ \hat{V} &= \Phi \Sigma \Psi^T. \end{aligned}$$

Now let $\Sigma_1 \geq \Sigma_2 \geq \dots \Sigma_k > 0$ denote the singular values, and $\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the left singular vectors of \hat{V} . The reduced basis Q then consists of d left singular vectors. The dimension d of the subspace Q is then chosen such that it minimizes the projection error ϵ_{POD} associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition decomposition [68]

$$\epsilon_{\text{POD}} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k \left\| V_j - \sum_{k=1}^d (V_j \phi_k) \phi_k \right\|^2 = \sum_{\ell=d+1}^k \Sigma_{\ell}^2. \quad (5.24)$$

This error characterizes the ability of the snapshot data to be represented in a low dimensional space. A goal of the reduced modeling is to select the best suitable snapshots and to reduce the POD error. We use this error estimator ϵ_{POD} to choose the dimension d of the reduced basis in Algorithm 10. Furthermore, in order to test how well the reduced model approximates

the full model, we define an error between the full model and the reduced model

$$\epsilon_{\text{RM}} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^N \|V_n - \bar{V}_n\|_2^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^N \|V_n\|_2^2}}, \quad (5.25)$$

where V is the solution obtained using the full model and \bar{V} is the result obtained using the reduced model. To minimize the model order reduction error, we required to obtain the optimal reduced basis. A quality of the reduced basis Q depends on the generated snapshots $\hat{V} = [V_1(\rho_1), v_2(\rho_2), \dots, V_k(\rho_k)]$, which depend on the training parameter set $\{\rho_1, \rho_2, \dots, \rho_k\}$. In Chapter 4, we have established the classical greedy sampling approach and the adaptive greedy sampling approach to locate the training parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ efficiently. This training parameter set is used to locate the optimal parameter group ρ_I . Furthermore, one full model is solved for ρ_I at each iteration i and the obtained solution is stored in $V_i(\rho_I) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times T}$ to update the snapshot matrix $\hat{V} = [V_\ell(\rho_I)]_{\ell=1}^i$ as

$$\hat{V}_\ell = [V_1(\rho_I^1), V_2(\rho_I^2), \dots, V_\ell(\rho_I^\ell)] \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times (T \times i)} \quad \ell = 1, \dots, i,$$

where T is the maturity of the underlying instrument. The process of updating the snapshot matrix is repeated either for I_{max} iterations or until the convergence. The convergence criteria for both the classical and adaptive greedy sampling algorithms are explained in Chapter 4. Now we consider

$$\mathcal{V}_\ell = \text{span}\{V_1(\rho_I^1), V_2(\rho_I^2), \dots, V_\ell(\rho_I^\ell)\},$$

as a span of these snapshots and obtain the reduced basis by computing its truncated singular value decomposition. At each greedy iteration, a new reduced basis Q_I is obtained of dimension d . The projection error associated with the POD is nothing but the sum of the square of neglected singular values. Since we have selected the first d left singular vectors to construct a reduced basis, the neglected singular values $\Sigma_{d+1}, \dots, \Sigma_{i \times T}$ contribute to the POD error. Therefore, the projection error based on (5.24) is

$$\epsilon_{\text{POD}}^{\text{AG,CG}} = \frac{1}{i \times T} \sum_{i=1}^{i \times T} \|V_i(\rho_I) - \sum_{k=1}^d (V_i(\rho_I) \phi_k) \phi_k\|_2^2 = \sum_{\ell=d+1}^{i \times T} \Sigma_\ell^2. \quad (5.26)$$

This error estimator shows that the quality of the reduced model depends on the number of left singular vectors used to construct a reduced basis, i.e., the dimension d . We use the projection error ϵ_{POD} along with the reduced model error ϵ_{RM} to choose the best possible reduced dimension d in Algorithm 10.

We have used a posteriori residual error estimator (4.7) $\epsilon = \|p(\cdot, \rho)\|$ to monitor the convergence of the classical greedy sampling algorithm and to terminate the training procedure. On the other hand, to get a more robust convergence criterion, the adaptive sampling uses

an approximate model of the reduced model error as a function of the residual error. In the adaptive greedy sampling approach, the algorithm constructs an error model $\hat{\epsilon}_{\text{RM}}$ based on the available data E_p from the residual errors $\{\epsilon_I^{\text{aft,bef}}\}_{I=1}^{I_{\text{max}}}$ and the reduced model errors $\{\epsilon_{\text{RM},i}^{\text{aft,bef}}\}_{i=1}^{I_{\text{max}}}$ and uses this error model to monitor the convergence of the algorithm. We have considered the linear model (4.11) to present the relation between the relative error and the residual error

$$\begin{aligned}\log(\hat{\epsilon}_{\text{RM},i}) &= \gamma_i \log(\epsilon) + \log\tau, \\ \mathcal{Y} &= \gamma_e \mathcal{X} + \hat{\tau},\end{aligned}$$

where the slope γ_e and the intercept $\hat{\tau}$ can be easily calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_e &= \frac{N_e \sum_{i=1}^{N_e} (\mathcal{X}\mathcal{Y}) - \sum_{i=1}^{N_e} \mathcal{X} \sum_{i=1}^{N_e} \mathcal{Y}}{N_e \sum_{i=1}^{N_e} (\mathcal{X}^2) - (\sum_{i=1}^{N_e} \mathcal{X})^2}, \\ \hat{\tau} &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_e} \mathcal{Y} - \gamma_e \sum_{i=1}^{N_e} \mathcal{X}}{N_e},\end{aligned}$$

where N_e is the length of the error set E_p . We can decide if the linear model consideration is sufficient or not by determining how well the model fits the actual data. To assess the quality of the model, one computes the R-squared value [21], which measures goodness-of-fit for linear regression models. The R-squared value always lies between 0 to 1 and is defined as the explained variation divided by the total variation in the model. That means a high R-squared value indicates that the designed model explains the variations in the output quite well. Therefore, we can say that the higher the R-squared, the better the model fits the data. However, before assessing numerical measures of goodness-of-fit, like R-squared, we should evaluate the residuals. Residual values are especially useful in regression procedures because they indicate the extent to which a model accounts for the variation in the observed data. Smaller residual values represent a better fit. The residuals between the predicted value $\hat{\mathcal{Y}}_i$ and the actual value \mathcal{Y}_i can be given as $|\mathcal{Y}_i - \hat{\mathcal{Y}}_i|$, where $i = 1, \dots, N_e$. Based on these residual values, we can define the sum of squared residual errors (SSE) that measures the discrepancy between the data and an approximate model

$$\text{SSE} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_e} (\mathcal{Y}_i - \hat{\mathcal{Y}}_i)^2.$$

Then the R-squared value can be calculated as, see [21],

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\text{SSE}}{\text{TSS}}, \quad (5.27)$$

where TSS denotes the total sum of squares. Let $\bar{\mathcal{Y}} = \frac{1}{N_e} \sum_{i=1}^{N_e} \mathcal{Y}_i$ be the mean of the observed

data. Then the TSS is

$$\text{TSS} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_e} (\mathcal{Y}_i - \bar{\mathcal{Y}})^2.$$

R-squared and residual plots are used in Chapter 6 to justify the use of a linear model for constructing an approximate model for the relative error.

Computational Complexity

The amount of resources required to run an algorithm is the computational complexity of that algorithm. In general, when one talks about computational complexity, one considers either time complexity or space complexity. The time complexity measures the time taken by an algorithm to execute, while the space complexity measures the amount of working storage an algorithm needs. In the classical and adaptive greedy sampling, the algorithm has to compute a singular value decomposition of the snapshot matrix at each iteration. The SVD of any matrix of order $m \times n$ is typically computed numerically in two steps. First, the matrix is reduced to be a bidiagonal matrix, which takes $\mathcal{O}(mn^2)$ floating-point operations. The second step is to compute the SVD of the reduced bidiagonal matrix [67]. The second step takes $\mathcal{O}(n)$ iterations, each costing $\mathcal{O}(n)$ floating-point operations. Therefore, the overall computational complexity of an SVD is

$$\mathcal{O}(mn^2) + \mathcal{O}(n) = \mathcal{O}(mn^2).$$

The computational complexity associated with a singular value decomposition of the matrix $\hat{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times (T \times i)}$ is then

$$\mathcal{O}(M(T \times i)^2) = \mathcal{O}(MT^2i^2).$$

After i iterations, the computational complexity due to the series of SVDs for the snapshot matrix will be

$$\mathcal{O}\left(\sum_{\ell=1}^i M \times (T \times \ell)^2\right) = \mathcal{O}(MT^2i^3).$$

We can see that the complexity increases substantially with each proceeding iteration, which motivates us to implement a truncated SVD approach. Recent studies have shown that the randomized algorithms yield an incredible speed up to implement a truncated SVD in some applications [37, 50].

Randomized Singular Value Decomposition

A growing area of research, randomized numerical linear algebra (RandNLA), couples probability theory with numerical linear algebra to develop fast, randomized algorithms with theoretical guarantees that such algorithms are, in some sense, a good approximation of some

full computation. It is proposed to compute a truncated singular value decomposition using randomized algorithms in the following two steps [50]. First, it starts by computing an approximate basis $G \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times k}$ with k orthonormal columns for the range of \hat{V} such that

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{V} &\approx GG^T\hat{V}, \\ \|\hat{V} - GG^T\hat{V}\| &< \epsilon_{tol},\end{aligned}$$

where $k < T \times i$ and ϵ_{tol} is some specified tolerance. Furthermore, in the second step, we use this matrix G to compute the truncated singular value decomposition of the matrix \hat{V} . Let $\tilde{V} = G^T\hat{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times (T \times i)}$ be a smaller matrix than \hat{V} , and its singular value decomposition reads

$$\tilde{V} = G^T\hat{V} = \tilde{\Phi}\tilde{\Sigma}\tilde{\Psi}^T.$$

As we compute the singular value decomposition of the reduced matrix \tilde{V} instead of the full matrix \hat{V} , we achieve our necessary speedup. Multiplying both sides by G , we get

$$\begin{aligned}GG^T\hat{V} &= G\tilde{\Phi}\tilde{\Sigma}\tilde{\Psi}^T, \\ \hat{V} &\approx G\tilde{\Phi}\tilde{\Sigma}\tilde{\Psi}^T.\end{aligned}\tag{5.28}$$

Considering $\Phi = G\tilde{\Phi}$, we obtain our left singular vector matrix, which we can use to obtain a reduced basis. We achieve the necessary speedup because the matrix \tilde{V} is smaller than the matrix \hat{V} . We can achieve practically even more speedup by incorporating the economy-sized (compact) singular value decomposition of the matrix \tilde{V} .

The economy-size decomposition removes extra rows or columns of zeros from the diagonal matrix of singular values and the columns in either $\tilde{\Phi}$ or $\tilde{\Psi}$. Removing these zeros and columns can improve execution time and reduce storage requirements without compromising the accuracy of the decomposition. The singular value decomposition gives the rank of a matrix. The number of nonzero singular values of a matrix $\tilde{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times T \times i}$ is the rank of the matrix \tilde{V} . Let the rank of \tilde{V} be $k = \min(k, (T \times i))$, then its compact SVD reads

$$\tilde{V} = \tilde{\Phi}\tilde{\Sigma}\tilde{\Psi}^T,$$

where the compact SVD generates a matrix $\tilde{\Sigma}$ of size $k \times k$ and has only non-zero singular values, as $k < T \times i$. The left and right singular vector matrices are $\tilde{\Phi} \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k}$, and $\tilde{\Psi} \in \mathbb{R}^{(T \times i) \times k}$. Thus, the desired left singular matrix is $\Phi = G\tilde{\Phi} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times k}$, which we use to obtain the reduced basis Q . We obtain the orthonormal matrix G with as few columns as possible such that

$$\|\hat{V} - GG^T\hat{V}\| < \epsilon_{tol}$$

where ϵ_{tol} is some tolerance and $\|\cdot\|$ is the L2-norm. The range of G is a k dimensional subspace that represents most of the action of \hat{V} , and we select k as small as possible. We

can use the singular value decomposition to decide the dimension k . Let Σ_j be the j th singular value of the matrix \hat{V} . For each $j \geq 0$

$$\min_{\text{rank}(GG^T\hat{V}) \leq j} \|\hat{V} - GG^T\hat{V}\| = \Sigma_{j+1},$$

where the columns of G are k dominant singular vectors of \hat{V} . The number of singular values of \hat{V} that exceeds the tolerance ε_{tol} makes the minimum rank k . It is recommended to assume that the desired rank k is specified in advance to simplify the computations. We can use the residual error $\|\hat{V} - GG^T\hat{V}\|$ inexpensively to build the basis matrix G incrementally. The randomized SVD uses randomness to solve this fixed-rank problem, i.e., to determine the matrix G .

Suppose we draw k Gaussian random vectors $\hat{G} = [\hat{g}_1, \dots, \hat{g}_k] \in \mathbb{R}^{(T \times i) \times k}$ and compute the products

$$\begin{aligned} y_\ell &= \hat{V}\hat{g}_\ell & \ell &= 1, \dots, k, \\ Y &= \hat{V}\hat{G}. \end{aligned}$$

Owing to the randomness, the random vectors \hat{g}_k are likely to be in a general linear position. In particular, [50] noted that the random vectors form a linearly independent set, and no combinations fall in the null space of \hat{V} . Therefore, we can say that the set of sample vectors $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_k\}$ are also linearly independent and spans the range of \hat{V} . Now, we can compute the orthonormal basis of $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times k}$, which is nothing but our desired matrix G . We can obtain G using a Gram–Schmidt like Algorithm or QR factorization. Halko et al. in [50] showed an approach to determine G adaptively using the residual error $\|(I - GG^T)\hat{V}\|$. We can obtain some information about this error by calculating $\|(I - GG^T)\hat{V}\hat{g}_i\|$. For k Gaussian random vectors, [50] gives an posterior error estimator as

$$\|\hat{V} - GG^T\hat{V}\| \leq 10\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \max_{i=1, \dots, k} \|(I - GG^T)\hat{V}\hat{g}_i\|. \quad (5.29)$$

This error estimate can be combined with any method for constructing an approximate basis for the range of Y . See [50] for more details. We obtain the matrix such that the residual error $\|\hat{V} - GG^T\hat{V}\|$ is less than or equal to some user-specified tolerance ε_{tol} .

The adaptive algorithm 9 combined with Gram-Schmidt orthonormalization is given below. It initiates by drawing k Gaussian random vectors of length $T \times i$ and computes the orthonormal set of vectors $\{g_1, \dots, g_k\}$ that makes the matrix G . At each iteration i , the algorithm computes $\|y_i\| = \|(I - GG^T)\hat{V}\hat{g}_i\|$, and from (5.29), after k iterations, if the largest value in the set $\{\|y_i\|\}_i^{i+k}$ is less than $\varepsilon_{tol}/(10\sqrt{2/\pi})$, we break the loop. We call this algorithm as *GSorth()* in the greedy and adaptive greedy sampling processes.

Algorithm 9 (Algorithm to obtain the orthonormal matrix G).

Input: Snapshot matrix \hat{V} , tolerance ε and a maximum number of iterations n .

Output: G .

Function: $GSorth()$

Draw Gaussian random vectors $\{\hat{g}_i\}_{i=1}^k$.

FOR $i = 1, \dots, k$

$$y_i = \hat{V}\hat{g}_i.$$

END

Initiate empty G matrix $G_0 = []$.

FOR $j = 1, \dots, n$

$$\text{Compute } y_j = (I - G_{j-1}G_{j-1}^T)y_j.$$

$$g_j = y_j / \|y_j\|.$$

$$G_j = [G_{j-1} \ g_j].$$

Draw a new Gaussian random vector \hat{g}_{j+k} .

$$\text{Compute } y_{j+k} = (I - G_jG_j^T)\hat{V}\hat{g}_{j+k}.$$

FOR $i = j + 1, j + 2, \dots, (j + k - 1)$

$$y_i = y_i - g_j(g_j, y_i)$$

END

IF $\max\{\|y_j\|, \|y_{j+1}\| \dots, \|y_{j+k}\|\} < \epsilon / (10\sqrt{2/\pi})$

BREAK.

END IF

END

$$G = G_j.$$

We use the randomized singular value decomposition in the greedy sampling approach to determine the reduced basis, as shown in Algorithm 10. Suppose we have snapshots $V_1(\rho_1), \dots, V_\ell(\rho_\ell)$ obtained using either the classical or adaptive greedy sampling approaches at i th iteration, where $\ell = 1, \dots, i$. The algorithm constructs a snapshot matrix \hat{V} composed of these snapshots. It then selects k Gaussian random vectors and obtains the matrix G , using the function $GSorth()$.

Algorithm 10 (Algorithm to obtain a reduced basis using a randomized singular value decomposition).

Input: Snapshot matrix \hat{V} , e_{tol}^d , Snapshots $V_1(\rho_1), \dots, V_\ell(\rho_\ell)$ available at i th iteration.

Output: Q .

Construct a snapshot matrix $\hat{V} = \{V(\rho_\ell)\}_\ell^i$ at i th iteration.

Obtain G using 'GSorth' function defined in Algorithm 9.

Compute $\tilde{V} = G^T \hat{V}$.

Compute a compact singular value decomposition of $\tilde{V} = \tilde{\Phi} \tilde{\Sigma} \tilde{\Psi}$.

Set $\Phi = G \tilde{\Phi}$.

Choose a parameter group ρ_{test} for testing.

Solve the full model for ρ_{test} and store result in V .

$\Sigma = [\Sigma_1, \dots, \Sigma_k]$.

FOR $j = 1, \dots, \text{length}(\text{diag}(\Sigma))$

 Compute $\epsilon_{POD} = \sum_{\ell=j+1}^k \Sigma_\ell^2$.

 Solve the reduced model for ρ_{test} for store result in \bar{V} .

 Compute ϵ_{RM}

 Compute $\epsilon_d = \epsilon_{RM} + \epsilon_{POD}$.

 IF $\epsilon_d < e_{tol}^d$

$d = j$

 Break

 END IF

END.

$Q = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_d]$.

A low dimensional matrix \tilde{V} is constructed using the newly obtained G with only k columns. The algorithm computes a compact singular value decomposition of \tilde{V} and sets $\Phi = G \tilde{\Phi}$ to obtain a reduced basis Q . Finally, the dimension of a reduced basis is selected that minimizes the projection error and the reduced model error.

5.3 Sampling Error

We have designed a surrogate model to locate the training parameters based on the principal component regression. There are two errors associated with the principal component regression model, i.e., a projection error due to the principal component analysis and an error of prediction of the surrogate model. We could determine the projection error associated with the PCA in a similar way to the proper orthogonal decomposition, while the mean squared error of prediction (MSEP) or its square root is used to access the quality of the regression model [82].

Let us first discuss the projection error. PCA reduces the problem of estimating m coefficients to the more straightforward problem of determining p coefficients by selecting a few relevant principal components. It is a technique for projecting multidimensional data onto a low dimensional subspace with minimal loss of variance. We determine the projection error associated with the PCA in a similar sense to the POD. At the k th iteration we have a data matrix $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k = [\rho_1; \dots; \rho_{c_k}]$ composed of c_k parameter groups. To build the surrogate model, we compute an SVD of the matrix $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$

$$\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k = \hat{\Phi} \hat{\Sigma} \hat{\Psi}^T,$$

where columns of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k \hat{\Psi}$ are principal components. We use only first p principal components to construct a fairly accurate surrogate model. Similar to (5.24), the projection error associated to PCA if only p principal components are used is

$$\epsilon_{\text{PCA}} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \|\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k(:, j) - \sum_{k=1}^p (\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k(:, j), \phi_k) \phi_k\|^2 = \sum_{\ell=p+1}^m \hat{\Sigma}_\ell^2. \quad (5.30)$$

In order to obtain a satisfactory regression model, we aim to reduce the projection error and select the principal components accordingly.

In the following, we discuss the mean squared error of prediction, which estimates the quality of the regression model, i.e., the surrogate model. The error estimators for surrogate models are analyzed on the independent test data. It may happen that the test set is not large enough, as in our case, during the start of the greedy iteration. If c_k is not much larger than m , then the model may give weak predictions due to the risk of over-fitting for the parameter groups which are not used in model training. In such situations, the error estimators are designed on the learning data where leave-one-out cross-validation is an elegant choice. As we have a data set with c_k observations, the leave-one-out cross-validation approach trains the model on $c_k - 1$ data points, and test data contains one observation. We repeat this process for c_k times and compute the mean square error. The major advantage of this approach is that it has far less bias as we use the entire data for training. However, the computational cost of one full leave-one-out cross-validation is high, and it may produce inconsistent and varying results

[120]. Additionally, it tends to have high variance and generates very different estimates if repeated estimates with different initial samples of data from the same distribution.

K-fold cross-validation is an alternative advocated to circumvent these drawbacks [40]. This technique involves randomly dividing the data set into K subsets known as *folds* of approximately equal size. One fold is kept for testing, and the model is trained on the remaining $K - 1$ folds. The process repeats for K iterations each time with $K - 1$ folds as the training set and the K th fold as a test set. As we repeat process K times, we get K errors per each fold, which are then used to compute the mean square error of prediction. The K-fold cross-validation is computationally efficient than the leave-one-out cross-validation as we repeat the process only for K iterations instead of c_k iterations.

Let $L = [\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k, \hat{\varepsilon}] \in \mathbb{R}^{c_k \times (m+1)}$ be a learning data matrix consisting of c_k parameter groups and error estimator values at k th iteration of the adaptive greedy algorithm. Here $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k = [\rho_1; \dots; \rho_{c_k}] \in \mathbb{R}^{c_k \times m}$ and $\hat{\varepsilon} = [\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_{c_k}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{c_k \times 1}$. Let the dataset L be partitioned into K groups or folds L_1, \dots, L_K such that $L_i \cap L_j = \emptyset$ for any $i \neq j$. Without the loss of generality, we suppose that c_k is a multiple of K where c_k denotes the size of dataset L . The size of each fold is then c_k/K . We train our surrogate model $\bar{\varepsilon}$ on $L \setminus L_K$, i.e., all data available in the matrix L except in L_K , while the data set L_K is used as a test set. After K iterations, we take the sum of errors and calculate its mean to get the $\text{MSEP}_{K\text{-CV}}$. The K-fold cross-validation error is given as [82]

$$\text{MSEP}_{K\text{-CV}} = \frac{1}{c_k} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\substack{i \in L_K \\ i=1}}^{c_k/K} (\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho_i) - \varepsilon_i)^2, \quad (5.31)$$

where the inner sum is calculated over the K th fold. The bias of $\text{MSEP}_{K\text{-CV}}$ is $\mathcal{O}(K-1)^{-1}c_k^{-1}$ [40]. In K-fold cross-validation, the surrogate model is trained on $L \setminus L_K$ data instead of all L . It can be expected that this surrogate model may be inferior as compared to the model trained on all data L . Thus, it is suggested to use the adjusted K-fold cross-validation to avoid this problem. The adjustment is [82]

$$\text{MSEP}_{adj.} = \text{MSEP}_{app.} - \frac{1}{c_k} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{1}{K} \sum_{\substack{i \notin L_K \\ i=1}}^{c_k - c_k/K} (\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho_i) - \varepsilon_i)^2, \quad (5.32)$$

where $\text{MSEP}_{app.}$ is called the apparent MSEP or mean squared error of calibration (MSEC), which uses the whole learning data L as a test set. This means we first train the surrogate model over the set and use the same set to compute the errors. The apparent MSEP is given as

$$\text{MSEP}_{app.} = \frac{1}{c_k} \sum_{i=1}^{c_k} (\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho_i) - \varepsilon_i)^2. \quad (5.33)$$

The second term of (5.32) is calculated as follows. In contrast to (5.31), instead of testing the model trained on the excluded data set L_k , we test it on the training data set $L \setminus L_k$ itself. After K iterations, we compute the mean by dividing the sum of K errors by c_k , which is nothing but the second term of (5.32). The adjustment is then the difference between the apparent error and the error calculated by training and testing the model on the $L \setminus L_K$ data. In short, this adjustment considers the errors associated with the K folds, which are not used for the training purpose during the K -fold cross-validation.

Thus, the adjusted K -fold cross validation error estimate is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MSEP}_{K-CVadj.} &= \text{MSEP}_{K-CV} + \text{MSEP}_{adj.}, \\ &= \frac{1}{c_k} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{\substack{i \in L_K \\ i=1}}^{c_k/K} (\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho_i) - \varepsilon_i)^2 + \frac{1}{c_k} \sum_{i=1}^{c_k} (\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho_i) - \varepsilon_i)^2 - \frac{1}{c_k} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{1}{K} \sum_{\substack{i \notin L_K \\ i=1}}^{c_k-c_k/K} (\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho_i) - \varepsilon_i)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (5.34)$$

We can now define the total sampling error associated with the PCR technique as a summation of the projection error and the adjusted K -fold cross-validation error

$$\epsilon_{samp} = \epsilon_{\text{PCA}} + \text{MSEP}_{K-CVadj.}. \quad (5.35)$$

Algorithm 11 presents a methodology to obtain a suitable surrogate model that minimizes the sampling error. It starts by computing a projection error ϵ_{PCA} associated with the principal component analysis. The surrogate model $\bar{\varepsilon}$ is then constructed using $j = p$ principal components. To assess the quality of the surrogate model, we determine the cross-validation error. The data set L is divided into K folds. We train the designed surrogate model on all data available in the matrix L except in L_k . Furthermore, the algorithm evaluates the surrogate model on the omitted data L_k , then computes errors, and subsequently determines the K -fold cross-validation error. MSEP_{K-CV} is then adjusted and added to ϵ_{PCA} to get the sampling error ϵ_{samp} . If the sampling error is less than the user-defined tolerance e_{tol}^{samp} , then the algorithm terminates. Finally, we use the surrogate model built using $j = p$ principal components, where the algorithm has been terminated. The procedure for the construction of a surrogate model is explained in Subsection 4.2.1.

Algorithm 11 (Algorithm to estimate the sampling error).

Input: $L = [\hat{P}_k, \hat{\varepsilon}]$, e_{tol}^{samp} , K .

Output: ϵ_{samp} (5.35).

Compute an SVD of the matrix $\hat{P}_k = \hat{\Phi} \hat{\Sigma} \hat{\Psi}^T$

Let $\hat{\Sigma} = [\hat{\Sigma}_1, \dots, \hat{\Sigma}_k]$.

FOR $j = 1, \dots, \text{length}(\text{diag}(\hat{\Sigma}))$

Compute $\epsilon_{\text{PCA}} = \sum_{\ell=j+1}^k \hat{\Sigma}_\ell^2$.

Build a surrogate model $\bar{\varepsilon}$ using $p = j$ principal components.

Divide L into K random folds.

FOR $k = 1, \dots, K$

Train the surrogate model on $L \setminus L_k$ data.

Solve the trained model on L_k data set.

Compute squared errors $\sum_{i \in L_k}^{c_k/K} (\bar{\varepsilon}(\rho_i) - \varepsilon_i)^2$.

END

Compute (5.31) $\text{MSEP}_{K\text{-CV}}$.

Compute (5.33) MSEP_{app} .

Compute (5.32) MSEP_{adj} .

Compute (5.34) $\text{MSEP}_{K\text{-CV}adj}$.

Compute (5.35) $\epsilon_{samp} = \epsilon_{\text{PCA}} + \text{MSEP}_{K\text{-CV}adj}$.

IF $\epsilon_{samp} < e_{tol}^{samp}$

$p = j$

Break

END IF

END.

5.4 Sensitivity Analysis

In the previous sections, we addressed the errors $\epsilon_h, \epsilon_{\text{POD}}, \epsilon_{\text{RM}}, \epsilon_{\text{samp}}$ associated with each stage of the model order reduction approach. This section presents a sensitivity analysis for these errors that provides quantitative information regarding relative contribution of each error to the model output. Sensitivity analysis can be helpful in various situations, including forecasting as well as identifying where improvements or adjustments are needed in a process [24]. Such information helps to improve the model output by selecting the appropriate grid size h , the reduced dimension d , and the optimal sampling parameters c . The sensitivity indices rank the numerical errors according to their contribution to the total error. We can use this ranking to allocate the computational resource efficiently. More computational resources could be provided to the most sensitive parameters [71].

In general, there are two types of sensitivity analysis, i.e., local and global [14, 24]. The local sensitivity analysis evaluates changes in the output with respect to the variations in a single factor by keeping other factors constant [61]. Such sensitivity is often evaluated through gradients or partial derivatives of the output functions at these factors. The main limitation of the local sensitivity analysis is that it evaluates the factors one at a time and does not consider the interactions and simultaneous changes in all factors [102]. Global sensitivity analysis overcomes this drawback by quantifying the importance of all factors and their interactions to the model output. It provides an overall influence of factors on the output as opposed to a local view of partial derivatives as in local sensitivity analysis.

It is easy and computationally feasible to compute the local sensitivity of deterministic errors such as discretization error by computing the norm of the first-order factor in Taylor series expansion or the partial derivative using finite differences [24]. For stochastic errors like sampling error, it is more appropriate to compute the change in output with respect to the variations in inputs [71]. However, this creates a difficulty in comparing the relative contributions of the deterministic errors versus stochastic errors. Thus, it is necessary to propose an approach that can be applied to both types of errors.

There are different local and global sensitivity analysis methods, such as the one-at-a-time (OAT) approach [14], the automatic differentiation technique (AD) [26], variance-based sensitivity analysis (Sobol’s method) [78, 102], and Fourier amplitude sensitivity analysis (FAST) [81]. The local sensitivity analysis approaches like OAT and AD calculates the first-order partial derivatives of the outputs with respect to small changes in the inputs. In AD, a computationally efficient computer code automatically evaluates the partial derivatives and can be applied without having detailed knowledge of the algorithm implemented in the model. However, the technique may be limited to specific computer languages and requires specific libraries, and the accuracy for sensitivity results is conditioned on the numerical method used in the AD software.

Both Sobol’s method and FAST are variance-based sensitivity analysis techniques capable

of computing first-order (local) and global sensitivity indices. The main difference between these two approaches is the underlying algorithm in multidimensional integration of sensitivity indices. The FAST approach uses a pattern search technique based on sinusoidal function, while the Sobol approach uses a Monte Carlo technique to determine the sensitivities. The disadvantage of the FAST approach is that it demands specific sampling and may perform poorly for discrete inputs and models with discontinuities. Among the discussed techniques, Sobol's method is one of the most powerful techniques being model-independent and robust, which considers interactions between different input factors. However, it may become computationally intensive if there are many input factors as it uses Monte Carlo techniques. In our case, the number of input factors (numerical errors) is small, which ease the computational burden. Moreover, [71] showed that the variance-based sensitivity analysis approach could be applied considering both deterministic and stochastic numerical errors. Thus, in this work, we use Sobol's method to perform the sensitivity analysis.

Consider a model output Y depending on some input factors (X_1, \dots, X_p)

$$Y = f(X_1, \dots, X_p).$$

Now, the variance based first order effect of X_i is [78]

$$\text{Var}_{X_i} \left(\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i) \right), \quad i = 1, \dots, p, \quad (5.36)$$

where X_i is the i th factor and $X_{\sim i}$ is the $p - 1$ dimensional space composed of all factors except X_i . The inner expectation operator means that the mean of Y is taken over all possible values of $X_{\sim i}$ while the factor X_i is kept fixed. $\text{Var}_{X_i}(\cdot)$ shows that the variance is taken over all possible values of X_i . Using the law of total variance, we can write [83]

$$\text{Var}(Y) = \text{Var}_{X_i} \left(\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i) \right) + \mathbb{E}_{X_i} \left(\text{Var}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i) \right), \quad (5.37)$$

by normalizing

$$1 = \frac{\text{Var}_{X_i} \left(\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i) \right)}{\text{Var}(Y)} + \frac{\mathbb{E}_{X_i} \left(\text{Var}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i) \right)}{\text{Var}(Y)}, \quad (5.38)$$

where the first order (local) sensitivity index for the factor X_i is given by the first term of (5.38)

$$S_i = \frac{\text{Var}_{X_i} \left(\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i) \right)}{\text{Var}(Y)}. \quad (5.39)$$

S_i is a normalized index as $\text{Var}_{X_i} \left(\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i) \right)$ varies from 0 to $\text{Var}(Y)$ and measures the first order effect of X_i on the output Y . $\mathbb{E}_{X_i} \left(\text{Var}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i) \right)$ is the residual [102]. It is necessary to note that the low value of the first-order sensitivity index does not mean that

the factor is not important. It might make a more significant contribution to the output by interactions with other factors. Thus, the total sensitivity index is necessary to define, which considers the main effect of the factor and the effect of its interactions with other factors on the output. In the sensitivity analysis framework, functional decomposition of the total variance $\text{Var}(Y)$ is referred to as functional analysis of variance (ANOVA) and given as [110]

$$\text{Var}(Y) = \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Var}_i(Y) + \sum_{i<j}^p \text{Var}_{ij}(Y) + \cdots + \text{Var}_{1\dots p}(Y), \quad (5.40)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}_i(Y) &= \text{Var}_{X_i} \left(\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i) \right), \\ \text{Var}_{ij}(Y) &= \text{Var}_{X_i, X_j} \left(\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i, j}}(Y|X_i, X_j) \right) - \text{Var}_i(Y) - \text{Var}_j(Y), \\ \text{Var}_{ijk}(Y) &= \text{Var}_{X_i, X_j, X_k} \left(\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i, j, k}}(Y|X_i, X_j, X_k) \right) - \text{Var}_i(Y) - \text{Var}_j(Y) - \text{Var}_k(Y) \\ &\quad - \text{Var}_{ij}(Y) - \text{Var}_{ik}(Y) - \text{Var}_{jk}(Y), \\ &\vdots \\ \text{Var}_{1, \dots, p} &= \text{Var}(Y) - \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Var}_i(Y) - \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq p} \text{Var}_{ij}(Y) - \cdots - \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < \dots < i_{p-1} \leq p} \text{Var}_{i_1, \dots, i_{p-1}}. \end{aligned}$$

The first-order sensitivity index (5.39) can be obtained from the first p terms of the decomposition (5.40) as

$$S_i = \frac{\text{Var}_i(Y)}{\text{Var}(Y)}.$$

The other terms of the decomposition can be interpreted as the higher-order sensitivity indices. The second-order index S_{ij} represents the effect of interactions of factors X_i and X_j on the output

$$S_{ij} = \frac{\text{Var}_{ij}(Y)}{\text{Var}(Y)},$$

and so on until order p . Therefore, for p factors, we have $2^p - 1$ sensitivity indexes. Based on the decomposition (5.40), [54, 103] introduced the so-called total sensitivity indices or total effects as

$$S_{T_i} = S_i + \sum_{j \neq i} S_{ij} + \sum_{j \neq i, k \neq i, j < k} S_{ijk} + \cdots = \sum_{\ell \# i} S_\ell,$$

where $\#i$ denotes all the indices associated with the factor X_i . The total sensitivity is derived using the expressions (5.40) as, see [102],

$$S_{T_i} = 1 - \frac{\text{Var}_{X_{\sim i}}(\mathbb{E}_{X_i}(Y|X_{\sim i}))}{\text{Var}(Y)}.$$

Using the law of total variance, similar to (5.37), we can write the total variance of Y by exchanging X_i and $X_{\sim i}$ as

$$\text{Var}(Y) = \text{Var}_{X_{\sim i}}\left(\mathbb{E}_{X_i}(Y|X_{\sim i})\right) + \mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}\left(\text{Var}_{X_i}(Y|X_{\sim i})\right). \quad (5.41)$$

Dividing (5.41) by $\text{Var}(Y)$

$$1 = \frac{\text{Var}_{X_{\sim i}}\left(\mathbb{E}_{X_i}(Y|X_{\sim i})\right)}{\text{Var}(Y)} + \frac{\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}\left(\text{Var}_{X_i}(Y|X_{\sim i})\right)}{\text{Var}(Y)},$$

and rewriting

$$S_{T_i} = 1 - \frac{\text{Var}_{X_{\sim i}}\left(\mathbb{E}_{X_i}(Y|X_{\sim i})\right)}{\text{Var}(Y)} = \frac{\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}\left(\text{Var}_{X_i}(Y|X_{\sim i})\right)}{\text{Var}(Y)}.$$

Calculation of Sobol Indices

The methodology to determine the local and global Sobol indices with a single simulation is presented in [102]. Consider two independent sampling matrices \bar{X} and \hat{X} to compute the values of the output Y corresponding to different input factors X_1, \dots, X_p .

$$\bar{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{X}_{11} & \cdots & \bar{X}_{1p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \bar{X}_{n1} & \cdots & \bar{X}_{np} \end{bmatrix}_{n \times p}, \quad \hat{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{X}_{11} & \cdots & \hat{X}_{1p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \hat{X}_{n1} & \cdots & \hat{X}_{np} \end{bmatrix}_{n \times p},$$

where n is the sample size and the p is the number of input factors. Then each row of the matrices \bar{X} and \hat{X} is one parameter sample set. We introduce a new matrix $\bar{X}_{\hat{X}}^i$ whose columns are from the matrix \bar{X} except the i th column which is from the matrix \hat{X}

$$\bar{X}_{\hat{X}}^i = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{X}_{11} & \bar{X}_{12} & \cdots & \hat{X}_{1i} & \cdots & \bar{X}_{1p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \bar{X}_{n1} & \bar{X}_{n2} & \cdots & \hat{X}_{ni} & \cdots & \bar{X}_{np} \end{bmatrix}_{n \times p}.$$

Based on these matrices \bar{X} , \hat{X} , and $\bar{X}_{\hat{X}}^i$, we determine the local sensitivity and the global sensitivity indices as follows. We can write a variance of Y as [83]

$$\text{Var}(Y) = \mathbb{E}(Y^2) - \mathbb{E}^2(Y). \quad (5.42)$$

Applying (5.42) to $\text{Var}_{X_i}(\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i))$, we get

$$\text{Var}_{X_i}(\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i)) = \int \mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}^2(Y|X_i)dX_i - \left(\int \mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i)dX_i \right)^2.$$

From [101]

$$\begin{aligned} \int \mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}^2(Y|X_i)dX_i &= \int \int f(\hat{X}_1, \dots, \hat{X}_p) \times f(\bar{X}_1, \dots, \hat{X}_i, \dots, \bar{X}_p)d\hat{X}d\bar{X}_{\sim i}, \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\ell=1}^n f(\hat{X})_{\ell} f(\bar{X}_{\hat{X}}^i)_{\ell}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.43)$$

and

$$\left(\int \mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i)dX_i \right)^2 = f^2(X) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\ell=1}^n f(\bar{X})_{\ell} f(\hat{X})_{\ell}. \quad (5.44)$$

Using (5.43) and (5.44), we can define the local sensitivity index as [102]

$$S_i = \frac{\text{Var}_{X_i}(\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i))}{\text{Var}(Y)} = \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{\ell=1}^n f(\hat{X})_{\ell} (f(\bar{X}_{\hat{X}}^i)_{\ell} - f(\bar{X})_{\ell})}{\text{Var}(Y)}.$$

We can derive the global sensitivity index S_{T_i} in a similar sense to the local sensitivity index [63, 102]

$$S_{T_i} = \frac{\mathbb{E}_{X_{\sim i}}(\text{Var}_{X_i}(Y|X_{\sim i}))}{\text{Var}(Y)} = \frac{\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{\ell=1}^n (f(\bar{X})_{\ell} - f(\bar{X}_{\hat{X}}^i)_{\ell})^2}{\text{Var}(Y)},$$

where $f(\bar{X})$, $f(\hat{X})$, and $f(\bar{X}_{\hat{X}}^i)$ are the model output results using the parameter sample values from matrices \bar{X} , \hat{X} , and $\bar{X}_{\hat{X}}^i$, respectively.

The independent distribution of each numerical error is determined as follows. The discretization error ϵ_h depends on the grid size h used to construct the full model. We sample different grid sizes with an appropriate grid refinement ratio and construct different full models. We further calculate the discretization error associated with each model and use generated samples to construct the distribution for ϵ_h .

Similar to the discretization error, the projection error ϵ_{POD} and the reduced model error ϵ_{RM} can be regulated by varying the reduced dimension d . We have to solve the full model for some training parameter groups to construct the snapshot matrix in order to generate a reduced basis. Before obtaining the distributions of the projection error and the reduced model error, the full model dimension and the number of training parameters are fixed. We construct the reduced models with different reduced dimensions and obtain the corresponding errors ϵ_{POD} , and ϵ_{RM} . These error samples are then used to construct the desired distributions.

The training parameters used to construct the surrogate model govern its quality. We randomly sample the parameter groups that initiate the adaptive greedy algorithm (parameter

set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$) and also vary the cardinality of set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ to understand the changes in the sampling error. The first few samples of the sampling error are obtained by randomly sampling the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$ while keeping the cardinality of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ constant. Later on, the cardinality of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ is varied while $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$ is fixed by specifying the particular seed number.

The obtained samples are then randomly separated into two matrices \bar{X} , and \hat{X} . Each column of the matrices \bar{X} or \hat{X} represents the distribution of one numerical error, while each row of matrices makes a set of model factors, i.e., in this case, the numerical error $\{\epsilon_h, \epsilon_{\text{POD}}, \epsilon_{\text{RM}}, \epsilon_{\text{samp}}\}$. The total error (5.3) presented in Chapter 5 is then used as a model output to perform the sensitivity analysis based on the generated sample data.

5.5 Model Hierarchy: Stopping Criteria

The task of this thesis is to calculate the financial risk associated with the invested product. Underlying risk factors such as interest rates have a direct influence on the invested asset. Interest rate risk arises when unanticipated developments shift the yield curve or change its shape. Thus, to calculate the financial risk, the instrument is evaluated for several thousand different simulated yield curves. One can consider these simulated yield curves as different scenarios. The financial instruments are evaluated via the dynamics of short-rate models \mathcal{M} , based on the convection-diffusion-reaction partial differential equations, e.g., (2.14) or (2.22). The choice of the short-rate model depends on the underlying financial instrument. The model hierarchy simplifies the process of obtaining a reduced model and is depicted in Fig. 5.3.

It starts by discretizing the partial differential equation using either the finite difference method or the finite element method. The discretized model is known as the full model \mathcal{M}_h . To obtain a reduced model \mathcal{M}_h^d , one has to compute a reduced basis. To do so, the proper orthogonal decomposition approach along with the classical or adaptive greedy sampling has been used. Finally, the full model is projected onto the reduced basis to get the reduced model. The above-described steps finally lead to the desired reduced model. However, it may happen that the user does not have enough knowledge or background about these methods to obtain the optimal reduced model. Thus, the user prefers an automatic approach that produces a reduced model whose error is below the user-defined tolerance. We describe the methodology to obtain a reduced model as a black box for which the user only requires to provide inputs and gets the desired output. The black box method automatically selects the partial differential equation according to the underlying financial instrument, generates the discretized model, obtains the training parameters, generates the desired reduced basis, and produces a reduced model with the desired user-defined tolerance. Yield curves and a financial instrument are fed as inputs to the black box, which outputs the scenario results. The procedure is illustrated in Fig. 5.3. This approach also yields well-defined stopping

Figure 5.3: Model hierarchy for model order reduction

criteria for the selection of scenarios to generate a reduced model.

Assume a parameter space $\mathcal{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{N} \times m}$ (of scenarios \mathcal{N}) for which the underlying financial instrument is to be solved using an appropriate short-rate model, \mathcal{M} . Let $\ell \in \mathcal{P} \subset \mathcal{N}$ be the number of training parameters selected using a sampling algorithm. Now, these ℓ parameters are used to obtain the reduced model \mathcal{M}_h^d with the total error $\epsilon_T \leq \epsilon_h + \epsilon_d + \epsilon_{samp}$.

Remark 5.5.1. *The stopping criteria to evaluate an underlying financial instrument with \mathcal{N} scenarios states that when $\epsilon_T \leq e_{tol}$, where e_{tol} is the user-defined tolerance, only ℓ scenarios need to be evaluated using the full model \mathcal{M}_h , while the remaining $\mathcal{N} - \ell$ scenarios can be evaluated using the reduced model \mathcal{M}_h^d .*

We solve ℓ scenarios using the full model \mathcal{M}_h to obtain the reduced basis and the remaining

scenarios $\mathcal{N} - \ell$ using the reduced model \mathcal{M}_h^d . The results obtained for all scenarios are then sorted into favorable V_{fav} , moderate V_{mod} , and unfavorable V_{unfav} performance scenarios.

Chapter 6

Applications and Results

We tested the developed model order reduction framework for two different numerical examples. The first numerical example is of a floater instrument with caps and floors. We solved this instrument using the robust one-factor Hull-White model. To test the methodology for more complicated instruments, we considered a steepener with caps and floors. A steepener is an instrument whose coupons depend on the difference between two reference interest rates, which demands to consider a multi-factor model. Therefore, in this thesis, we solve the steepener instrument using the robust two-factor Hull-White model.

All computations are carried out on a PC with 4 cores and 8 logical processors at 2.90 GHz (Intel i7 7th generation). We used MATLAB R2018a for the yield curve simulations, FDM, FEM, and the model reduction. The numerical method for the yield curve simulations is tested with real market based historical data. Market data are available from market data providers like Thomson Reuters, Bloomberg, and several others. We obtained this data from MathConsult within their UnRisk Omega datasets [79]. The daily interest rate data are collected at 21 tenor points in time over the past 5 years, where each year has 260 working days, so there are 1300 observation periods. We have used the inbuilt UnRisk tool for the parameter calibration, which is well integrated with Mathematica (version used: Mathematica 11.3). Further, we used calibrated parameters for the construction of Hull-White models.

6.1 Floater with Caps and Floors

A floater with caps and floors is considered as a test example with properties depicted in Table 6.1. A floater is an instrument whose coupons are given by some standard index like *Euribor* or *Libor*, which is known as a reference rate. In our example, the underlying currency is Euro, and the reference rate is *Euribor*. We solved this instrument using the robust one-factor Hull-White model. The full model is obtained by discretizing the PDE using FDM explained in Section 3.1. The reduced model is then generated using the proper orthogonal decomposition approach along with the classical and adaptive greedy sampling techniques.

Table 6.1: Numerical Example of a floater with caps and floors.

Coupon frequency	quarterly
Cap rate, C_R	2.25 % p.a.
Floor rate, F_R	0.5 % p.a.
Currency	EURO
Maturity	10 years
Nominal amount	1.0
b	0.015
σ	0.006

The interest rates are capped at $C_R = 2.25\%$ p.a. and floored at $C_F = 0.5\%$ p.a. with the reference rate as Euribor3M. The coupon rates can be written as

$$coup = \min(2.25\%, \max(0.5\%, \text{Euribor3M})) \quad (6.1)$$

Note that the coupon rate $coup^{(n)}$ at time t_n is set in advance as the coupon rate at t_{n-1} .

We have computed the model parameters as explained in Section 2.3. The yield curve simulation is the first step to compute the model parameters. Based on the procedure described in Section 2.2, we have performed the bootstrapping process for the recommended holding period and the intermediate holding period of ten and five years, respectively. The

Figure 6.1: 10 000 simulated yield curves obtained by bootstrapping after five years (left) and ten years (right) in the future for the floater instrument.

collected historical data has 21 tenor points and 1306 observation periods as follows (D: Day, M: Month, Y: Year):

$$m =: \{1D, 3M, 6M, 1Y, 2Y, 3Y, \dots, 10Y, 12Y, 15Y, 20Y, 25Y, 30Y, 40Y, 50Y\}$$

$$n =: \{1306 \text{ daily interest rates at each tenor point}\}$$

The 10 000 simulated yield curves in 5 and 10 years in the future are presented in Fig. 6.1. For the floater example, we need parameter values only until the 10Y tenor point (maturity of the floater). Henceforth, we consider the simulated yield curves with only the first 13 tenor points. The calibration generates the real parameter space of dimension $\mathbb{R}^{10000 \times 13}$ for the parameter $a(t)$. We considered the constant volatility $\sigma = 0.006$ and the constant mean reversion $b = 0.015$. All variable parameters are assumed to be piecewise constants between the tenor points $(0 - 3M, 3M - 6M, 6M - 1Y, 1Y - 2Y, 2Y - 3Y, \dots, 9Y - 10Y)$. The calibration generates a parameter space \mathcal{P} of order $10\,000 \times m$ for which we now solve the one-factor Hull-White model.

The finite difference method explained in Section 3.1.3 is implemented for the PDE (2.14). Rewriting (3.13), for a given final value of V at the last tenor point, we obtain

$$A(\rho_\ell(t))V^{n-1} = B(\rho_\ell(t))V^n.$$

To solve this equation, we applied homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions of the form

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial r}|_{r_{low}} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial V}{\partial r}|_{r_{up}} = 0, \quad (6.2)$$

where the computational domain for a spatial dimension r is restricted as described in Section 3.1.3 with $r_{low} = -0.1$ and $r_{up} = 0.1$. We can apply the first boundary condition in (6.2) by updating the first and the last rows (A_1 and A_M) of the matrix $A(\rho_\ell)$ which yields

$$A_1 = (-1, 1, 0, \dots, 0) \text{ and } A_M = (0, \dots, 0, 1, -1).$$

The second Neumann boundary condition can be applied by changing the last entry of the vector BV^n to zero. Starting at $t = T$ with the known terminal condition $V(T)$ as the principal amount, at each time step, we solve the system of linear equations (3.13). We used the N time points (measured in days) starting from $t = 0$ until maturity T , i.e., in our case, the number of days until maturity are assumed to be $3600 \approx 10Y$ with an interval $\tau = 10$. We determine the time step τ using Algorithm 6, ensuring that all key dates are achievable, i.e., coupon dates, or valuation dates. The tolerance e_{tol}^t of 10^{-3} is used to obtain this best suitable time step τ .

Note that we need to update the value of the grid point $r(i)$ every three months as the coupon frequency is quarterly by adding coupon f^n based on the coupon rate given by (6.1). To calculate the value at the intermediate holding period, we calculate the fair value of the floater and add it to the accreted coupons. We divided the spatial domain into M equidistant grid points $\{r(1), r(2), \dots, r(M)\}$. To determine the full model dimension M , we used Algorithm 8. The quality of the full model is judged by computing the discretization error as explained in Subsection 5.1.2. Figure 6.2 shows the discretization error along with

the grid convergence index calculated using (5.22). We can see that the discretization error

Figure 6.2: The discretization error estimator and the grid convergence index vs the full model size for the floater instrument.

decreases with increasing full model dimension. The computation of the discretization error estimator requires three different solutions of the full model for three different grid sizes. It is necessary to have these solutions in the asymptotic range for which the grid convergence index should be low. The observed order of accuracy \hat{p} is in the range of 2.0162 to 2.3402 with an average of 2.0402. Since \hat{p} is calculated using three different grid sizes, the factor of safety $F_s = 1.25$ has been used. For the full model with $M = 800$, GCI is of order 10^{-4} , $\hat{p} = 2.0242$ and the discretization error $\epsilon_h = 3.926 \times 10^{-4}$ is less than the user-defined tolerance $e_{tol}^h = 5 \times 10^{-4}$. Therefore, this full model of order $M = 800$ is then used for the model order reduction.

6.1.1 Model Order Reduction

We have implemented the parametric model reduction approach for the floater example, as discussed in Section 4 using both the classical and the adaptive greedy sampling algorithms.

Classical Greedy Sampling

At each iteration of the classical greedy sampling approach, the algorithm constructs a reduced basis via Algorithm 2. We have specified a maximum number of 40 pre-defined candidates to construct a set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ and a maximum number of iterations $I_{max} = 10$. The progression of the maximal and average residuals with each iteration of the greedy algorithm is presented in Fig. 6.3. It is observed that the maximal residual error typically decreases in the process and the

Figure 6.3: Evolution of maximal and average residuals in each iteration of classical greedy algorithm for the floater instrument.

proposed greedy algorithm efficiently locates the optimal parameter groups and constructs the desired reduced basis Q .

Furthermore, we tested the effect of change in the cardinalities of the set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$. The proposed algorithm is applied with three different cardinalities of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$: $|\hat{\mathcal{P}}_1| = 20$, $|\hat{\mathcal{P}}_2| = 30$, $|\hat{\mathcal{P}}_3| = 40$.

Figure 6.4: Evolution of maximal and average residuals with varying cardinality of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ of classical greedy algorithm for the floater instrument.

Note that we have constructed $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ by randomly selecting the parameter groups from the parameter space \mathcal{P} . Figure 6.4 shows the plot of the maximal residual against the number

of iterations for three different cardinalities. It is evident that with an increasing number of candidates, the maximal residual error decreases and the decrease is sufficient for a cardinality 40 of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$.

The algorithm then located the optimal parameter groups and obtained the reduced basis. The dimension of the reduced basis is chosen using Algorithm 10. The projection error ϵ_{POD} associated with the reduced basis is calculated using (5.26) and plotted in Fig. 6.5. It can be observed that the projection error decreases with increasing reduced dimension d . The figure also shows that the error ϵ_{POD} is rapidly and monotonously decreasing, which drops to 3.89×10^{-5} with just $d = 10$. Thus, the reduced basis consisted of the first ten singular vectors is used for further computations. Figure 6.5 also illustrates the plot of relative error between

Figure 6.5: Floater instrument: Classical Greedy Sampling: Projection error associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition (left), and a plot of the relative error between the full model and the reduced model obtained using the classical greedy sampling approach (right).

the full model and the reduced model. The reduced model error ϵ_{RM} decreases with increasing reduced dimension and is 3.8145×10^{-4} for the reduced dimension $d = 10$. Then the total model order reduction error ϵ_d is $\epsilon_{\text{RM}} + \epsilon_{\text{POD}} = 3.8145 \times 10^{-4} + 3.89 \times 10^{-5} = 4.20 \times 10^{-4}$, which is less than the user-specified tolerance $e_{\text{tol}}^d = 5 \times 10^{-4}$. Therefore, this reduced model can be further used to calculate the performance scenarios.

The classical greedy sampling used the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ of cardinality 40 to locate the optimal parameter groups. As explained in Subsection 4.1.1, there is a specific drawback of the classical greedy approach. Since $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ is chosen randomly, the approach might neglect the vital parameter groups within the parameter space. We noticed that with our obtained results as well, which is pictured perfectly in Fig. 6.6.

Figure 6.6 illustrates the relative error between the full model and the reduced model for two different parameter groups. During our tests we noticed that there are some parameter groups (e.g., ρ_{238}) for which the reduced model gives unsatisfactory results. One can observe that the reduced model for the parameter group ρ_{238} (dashed line) shows inferior results as

Figure 6.6: Drawback of the classical greedy sampling for the floater instrument.

compared to the reduced model for the parameter group ρ_{786} (solid line). Even an increase in the reduced dimension d does not improve the quality of the result substantially.

This reveals that the selection of trial candidates by random sampling may neglect parameter groups corresponding to the significant error.

To overcome this drawback, we have also implemented the adaptive greedy sampling approach for the floater example.

Adaptive Greedy Sampling

The adaptive greedy sampling approach is based on the surrogate modeling that efficiently locates the training parameters. The surrogate model is built using the principal component regression technique in Subsection 4.2.1. The adaptive greedy iteration is initiated by computing the error estimator for the set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$ of cardinality 10. At each iteration of the surrogate model loop, the algorithm locates $c_k = 10$ parameter groups until the cardinality of the set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ reaches 40. Figure 6.7 presents monotonically decreasing singular values of the data matrix $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$ composed of c_k parameter groups at k th iteration. We noticed that the first three principal components comprised almost 99.90% of the energy, while the first five components contained 99.99% of the energy. We have used the first $p = 5$ principal components to construct a surrogate model. Figure 6.7 also shows the predicated data obtained using the surrogate model plotted against the real data of the error estimator. This comparison tells that the constructed surrogate model works positively well.

The quality of the surrogate model is judged by computing the mean squared error of prediction using the cross-validation technique, as shown in Table 6.2. At the last iteration of the surrogate model loop, $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ contains 40 parameter groups, which are further divided into

4 folds for cross-validation. We obtained the mean squared errors for each fold to calculate the MSEP_{K-CV} . The calculated MSEP_{K-CV} is 4.287×10^{-6} . However, an adjustment in the calculated MSE for the biased due to the neglected fold at each iteration of the cross-validation procedure is necessary, as explained in Subsection 5.3. After adjusting for the bias, the adjusted cross-validation error is 3.262×10^{-6} . Therefore, the total sampling error is $\epsilon_{samp} = \text{MSEP}_{K-CVadj} + \epsilon_{PCA} = 1.853 \times 10^{-5}$, which is less than the specified tolerance $\epsilon_{tol}^{samp} = 5 \times 10^{-4}$. Therefore, we can say that the designed surrogate model with $p = 5$

Figure 6.7: Floater instrument: Principal component analysis error (left) and predicted values obtained using the surrogate model for an error estimator vs actual values (right).

Table 6.2: Mean squared error of prediction

Fold No.	Squared error
$L_K = 1$	3.913×10^{-6}
$L_K = 2$	3.849×10^{-6}
$L_K = 3$	2.934×10^{-6}
$L_K = 4$	6.451×10^{-6}
MSEP_{K-CV}	4.287×10^{-6}
$\text{MSEP}_{K-CVadj}$	3.262×10^{-6}
$\epsilon_{samp} = \text{MSEP}_{K-CVadj} + \epsilon_{PCA}$	1.853×10^{-5}

principal components is enough for sampling procedure in adaptive greedy sampling. Also, the predicted data obtained using the surrogate model matches quite well with the real data, as depicted in Fig. 6.7. This assured that the designed surrogate model is working excellently.

Once we obtained $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$, the optimal parameter group updates the snapshot matrix, and consecutively the algorithm generates a new reduced basis at each greedy iteration. Figure 6.8 shows the evolution of maximum and average residual errors with each iteration

of the adaptive greedy algorithm. The residual error decreases with each incrementing iteration and hence the algorithm succeeded in locating the optimal parameter group efficiently. Furthermore, we have used the reduced basis obtained from the adaptive greedy

Figure 6.8: Maximal and average residuals per iteration of adaptive greedy algorithm for the floater instrument.

sampling procedure to design the reduced model. Figure 6.9 shows the monotonically de-

Figure 6.9: Floater instrument: Adaptive Greedy Sampling: Projection error associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition (left), and a plot of the relative error between the full model and the reduced model obtained using adaptive greedy sampling (right).

creasing projection error associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition approach in the case of an adaptive greedy approach. For the reduced dimension $d = 10$, the projection error is 4.139×10^{-8} . Figure 6.10 also presents the relative error plot for the parameter group ρ_{786} . We can see that the reduced model error ϵ_{RM} decreases with increasing reduced

dimension. The reduced model designed with the reduced dimension $d = 10$ gives the reduced model error $\epsilon_{\text{RM}} = 7.756 \times 10^{-5}$. Therefore, the total model order reduction error is $\epsilon_d = \epsilon_{\text{POD}} + \epsilon_{\text{RM}} = 4.139 \times 10^{-8} + 7.756 \times 10^{-5} = 7.7601 \times 10^{-5}$, which is less than the tolerance $e_{\text{tol}}^d = 5 \times 10^{-4}$.

This reduced model is then used to solve the remaining parameter groups and obtain the performance scenario values. Figure 6.10 shows the comparison of the classical and adaptive

Figure 6.10: Comparison of classical (CG) and adaptive (AG) greedy sampling approach for the floater instrument.

greedy sampling techniques. It presents the relative error plot for the parameter groups ρ_{238} , and ρ_{786} . We see that the adaptive greedy approach gives better results than the classical greedy method. In the case of the adaptive greedy sampling, the relative error decreases rapidly with increasing reduced dimension compared to its counterpart.

Convergence of the Adaptive Greedy Sampling Algorithm

To monitor the convergence of the adaptive greedy algorithm, we have designed an approximate model $\hat{\epsilon}_{\text{RM}}$ for the relative error ϵ_{RM} as a function of the residual error ϵ . Figure 6.11 shows the designed error model compared to the available error set E_p for four different greedy iterations. The error plot exhibits a strong correlation between the relative error and the residual error. The results indicate that a linear error model is satisfactory to capture the overall behavior of the exact error as a function of the residual error.

We have also tested the considered linear model using the goodness of fit test, which calculates the coefficient of determination as explained in Section 5.2. The calculated R-squared value is (5.27) $R^2 = 0.958$. Usually, the higher the R-squared value, the higher the confidence in the model. Therefore, the goodness of fit test shows a high degree of confidence

in our model and strengthens our linear model assumption.

Figure 6.11: An approximate model for the relative error to monitor the convergence of the adaptive greedy algorithm for the floater instrument.

Effect of Random Sampling

Figure 6.12: Randomization effect on classical and adaptive greedy sampling approaches for the floater instrument.

We have used random sampling up to a certain extent in both classical and adaptive greedy approaches. Random sampling is used to construct the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ in the classical greedy, while in the case of the adaptive greedy, it is used to initiate the algorithm. In both cases,

the random sampling somewhat affects the results. Figure 6.12 shows the maximum residual error plot with each proceeding iteration of the greedy algorithms with error bars.

These results are obtained by performing classical and adaptive procedures for 30 different sets of random numbers. It is observed that the adaptive greedy approach is less sensitive to random sampling than its counterpart. On average, the adaptive greedy approach yields a better reduced model as its residual errors are lesser than the classical approach for the floater example.

Computational cost

Three major numerical errors that lead to the total error are the discretization error, the model order reduction error, and the sampling error. Figure 6.13 presents the model hierarchy along

Figure 6.13: A model hierarchy showing errors arising in the analysis of the mathematical model for the floater instrument.

with the error associated in each stage. The total error is a sum of all significant errors and is given by (5.4)

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_T &\approx \epsilon_h + \epsilon_{\text{RM}} + \epsilon_{\text{POD}} + \epsilon_{\text{samp.}}, \\ \epsilon_T &= 3.926 \times 10^{-4} + 7.756 \times 10^{-5} + 4.139 \times 10^{-8} + 1.853 \times 10^{-5} = 4.887 \times 10^{-4}. \end{aligned}$$

As the $\epsilon_T < 10^{-3}$, it fulfills the stopping criteria prescribed in remark 5.5.1. Thus, we can say that only $\ell = 10$ full model valuations are enough to obtain the fairly accurate reduced model, and the remaining scenarios (parameter groups) can be solved using the generated

reduced model.

The total computational time T_Q^{CG} required to obtain the reduced basis after i steps of the greedy algorithm in the case of the classical greedy sampling approach is given by, (4.8),

$$T_Q^{CG} \approx \left[c \times t_{RM} + (t_{FM} + t_{SVD}) \right] \times i.$$

Similarly, in the case of the adaptive greedy approach, the total computational time T_Q^{AG} is given as, (4.12),

$$T_Q^{AG} \approx \left[c_0 \times t_{RM} + \underbrace{k(C_k \times t_{RM} + t_{SM} + t_{SM}^{ev})}_{t_{\rho_I}} + t_{FM} + t_{SVD} + 2t_{RM}^{af,bf} + t_{EM} \right] \times i,$$

Table 6.3 compares the computing times required to generate the reduced basis Q for different sets of \hat{P} in case of the classical greedy sampling approach with that needed to obtain the reduced basis in case of the adaptive greedy sampling approach. The computing time t_{ρ_I} required to locate the optimal parameter group by constructing a surrogate model for one greedy iteration is approximately 8 seconds. t_{ρ_I} is nothing but the time required to complete a while loop outlined in Algorithm 5 for a single greedy iteration. Thus, the total time contributed to generate the reduced basis via surrogate modeling is $I_{max} \times t_{\rho_I} = 78.56$ s, considering the adaptive greedy algorithm runs for I_{max} iterations. However, Fig. 6.8 shows that we can truncate the algorithm after 4 or 5 iterations as the residual error falls below 10^{-4} .

Table 6.3: Computing time/ reduction time (T_Q) to generate projection subspace for the floater instrument.

Algorithm	Cardinality $ \hat{P} $	Max. no. iterations I_{max}	Computing time
Classical greedy sampling	20	10	56.82 s
Classical greedy sampling	30	10	82.54 s
Classical greedy sampling	40	10	95.04 s
Adaptive greedy sampling	40	10	183.21 s

The computing times required to simulate reduced models and full models are presented in Table 6.4. The time required to solve the complete system with a parameter space of $10000 \times m$ for both a full and reduced model is given in the total time column.

We can see that the evaluation time required for the reduced model is at least 25 – 30 times less than that of the full model. However, there is a slight increase in total time due to the addition of the reduction time T_Q . One can also observe that with an increase in the dimension d of the reduced model, the evaluation time increases significantly. The reduced

Table 6.4: Evaluation time for the floater instrument.

Algorithm	Model	Eva. time single ρ_s	Total Eva. time (T_{eva})	Total time $T_Q + T_{\text{eva}}$
	FM, $M = 800$	0.3283 s	3413.45 s	3413.45 s
Classical greedy sampling	RM, $d = 5$	0.0102 s	102.56 s	197.60 s
Classical greedy sampling	RM, $d = 10$	0.0125 s	125.48 s	220.52 s
Adaptive greedy sampling	RM, $d = 6$	0.0104 s	104.38 s	287.59 s
Adaptive greedy sampling	RM, $d = 10$	0.0124 s	124.32 s	307.53 s

model with the classical greedy sampling approach is at least 15 – 17 times faster than that for the full model. The time required to simulate the reduced model with the adaptive greedy sampling approach is a bit higher due to the time invested in building surrogate and error models. Despite of that, the reduced model is at least 11 – 12 times faster than the full model. The computational time presented in both tables considers that the greedy algorithms run for the maximal number of iterations I_{max} . However, we can truncate the algorithms after 4 or 5 iterations, i.e., we can practically achieve even more speedup than discussed here.

In order to speed up the simulations, the truncated singular value decomposition is obtained using randomized algorithms. Table 6.5 shows the computational time comparison of the truncated SVD and the basic SVD. We noticed that the truncated SVD is at least 9 times faster than its counterpart for the floater example.

Table 6.5: Computational time comparison: SVD vs Randomized SVD for the floater instrument.

	SVD	RandSVD	Speedup factor
Computational time t_{SVD}	5.214 s	0.536 s	≈ 9.724

faster than its counterpart for the floater example.

6.1.2 Floater Performance Scenario Values

To design a key information document, we need the values of the floater at different spot rates. The spot rate r_{sp} is the yield rate at the first tenor point from the simulated yield curve. The value of a floater at the spot rate r_{sp} is nothing but the value at that short rate $r = r_{sp}$. For 10 000 simulated yield curves, we got 10 000 different spot rates and the corresponding values for the floater. At the recommended holding period, we determined a VaR equivalent volatility to calculate a market risk indicator. For the floater example, the

calculated $VEV = 0.3989\%$, which gives the market risk indicator as 1. The 10 000 values are further used to calculate three different scenarios: (i) favorable scenario, (ii) moderate scenario, (iii) unfavorable scenario which are the values at 90th percentile, 50th percentile and 10th percentile of 10 000 values, respectively. Table 6.6 shows the floater performance scenario results obtained using the reduced model and the commercially available UnRisk software for the comparison. Figure 6.14 shows the distribution of fair values of the floater, plus the coupons in the respective path obtained so far, after five years and ten years. At five years, the main contribution to price variability arises from discounting the future cash flows (between five and ten years) with a discount factor arising from log-normally distributed rates. Therefore we have (in our example) a left-skewed distribution at five years, and a right-skewed distribution at ten years.

Figure 6.14: Distribution of floater values after five years and ten years.

Table 6.6: Results for a floater with cap and floor.

Performance Scenario	5 years		10 years	
Model	ROM	UnRisk	ROM	UnRisk
Favorable (90th percentile)	1.013	1.014	1.105	1.101
Moderate (50th percentile)	1.009	1.002	1.067	1.066
Unfavorable (10th percentile)	0.988	0.984	1.038	1.041

6.2 Callable/Puttable Steepener

Steepeners are the financial instruments where the cashflows depend on differences in the evolution of two different reference rates with different tenors in one currency [1]. We considered a callable/puttable steepener instrument whose coupons depend on the difference between two *constant maturity swap* (CMS) rates, i.e., CMS10 - CMS2 [18]. Table 6.7 shows the properties of a puttable steepener. It is a puttable type of instrument, i.e., a put is an option that gives the right to a buyer to sell the underlying asset at an agreed price at some time in the future. The selling price is known as a strike price. The payoff of an option is its value at the time of its exercise. Consider K as the strike price of a put option and an underlying instrument with a value V and maturity T . The payoff of the put option is

$$P_V = \begin{cases} K - V, & \text{if } V < K. \\ 0, & \text{if } V \geq K. \end{cases}$$

$$P_V = \max(K - V, 0) = (K - V)^+.$$

Table 6.7 shows that the interest rate is capped at 3.0% p.a. and floored at 0.0% p.a. The

Table 6.7: Numerical Example of a puttable Steepener.

Maturity	10 years
Currency	EURO
Coupon frequency	Annually
Coupons:	
Year 1 to Year 3	4% fix
Year 4 to Year 10	CMS10 - CMS2
Cap rate, C_R	3.0 % p.a.
Floor rate, F_R	0.0 % p.a.

cap is nothing but an upper limit on the interest rate for a floating interest rate instrument, while the floor sets a lower limit on the interest rate. The coupon rate from the fourth year until maturity is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{coupon rate} &= \min(\text{coupon cap}, \max(\text{coupon floor}, \text{CMS10} - \text{CMS2})), \\ &= \min(3.0\%, \max(0.0\%, \text{coupon floor}, \text{CMS10} - \text{CMS2})) \end{aligned} \quad (6.3)$$

We solved the puttable steepener example using the robust two-factor Hull-White model. The partial differential equation is discretized using the finite element method to obtain the full model, which is further approximated to achieve the reduced model. The constant model parameters are $\sigma_1 = 0.0035$, $\sigma_2 = 0.008$, $\gamma = 0.65$, $\alpha = 0.75$, $b = 0.04$. We have computed the

model parameter θ_ℓ as explained in Subsection 2.4. The yield curve simulation is the first step to compute the model parameters. Based on the yield curve simulation procedure described in Subsection 2.2, we have performed the bootstrapping process for the recommended holding period and the intermediate holding period, i.e., for ten years and five years, respectively. The collected historical data has 21 tenor points and 1306 observation periods as follows (D: Day, M: Month, Y: Year):

$$m =: \{1D, 3M, 6M, 1Y, 2Y, 3Y, \dots, 10Y, 12Y, 15Y, 20Y, 25Y, 30Y, 40Y, 50Y\}$$

$$n =: \{1306 \text{ daily interest rates at each tenor point}\}$$

Figure 6.15 shows the plots of simulated yield curves obtained by bootstrapping for five

Figure 6.15: 10 000 simulated yield curves obtained by bootstrapping after five years and ten years in the future for the steepener instrument.

years and ten years in the future. The calibration generates a parameter space \mathcal{P} of order $10\,000 \times m$ for which we now solve the two-factor Hull-White model.

For calculations, we have used a structured, two-dimensional triangular mesh grid that generates a full model of order M . We have used fully implicit time-stepping so that discretizations in time and space can be chosen independently. The resulting system of linear equations is, (3.20),

$$A(\rho_\ell(t))V^{n-1} = B(\rho_\ell(t))V^n.$$

To obtain a solution, we solved this system starting at $t = T$ with an appropriate terminal condition $V(T)$ backward in time at each time step n . It is important to note that we have selected the time step $\tau = 10$ days using Algorithm 6, and ensuring that all key dates are achievable, i.e., coupon dates, put dates, or valuation dates. The tolerance e_{tol}^t of 10^{-3} is used to obtain this suitable time step. Now, we determined the value of the steepener by solving the linear system given in (3.20) as follows. If the coupon date is reached, then we update

the value of the steepener by adding the necessary coupon given by (6.3) [79]

$$V^{n-1} = V^{n-1} + CF^{n-1},$$

where V^{n-1} is the value calculated by solving the full model, and CF is either already known cashflow or a cashflow generated by the coupon if the coupon date is achieved at t^{n-1} or zero. Similarly, if the put date is reached, then we have to update the value at that time point by the following max function

$$V^{n-1} = \max(V^{n-1}, \text{Put Price}),$$

where the put price is the strike price defined by the put option contract. In this work, we have considered Put Price = 1. We have considered put dates annually starting one year after the issuing of the bond until one year before maturity.

The quality of the full model is assured by calculating the discretization error associated with the two-factor Hull-White model, as explained in Subsection 5.1. Figure 6.16 shows the discretization error along with the grid convergence index values. We can see that the error decreases with increasing order of the full model. The full model size is selected using

Figure 6.16: The discretization error estimator and the grid convergence index (5.22) vs the full model size for the steepener instrument.

Algorithm 8, which convergences when the discretization error is less than the user-defined tolerance $e_{tol}^h = 5 \times 10^{-4}$. We have designed a full model of order $M = 1600$ as the discretization error $\epsilon_h = 2.182 \times 10^{-4}$ falls below 5×10^{-4} .

A discretization error computation requires three different solutions of the full model for three different grid sizes. The error estimator is acceptable if these solutions are in the

asymptotic range of convergence, i.e., the grid convergence index is low. The observed order of accuracy \hat{p} is in the range of 1.8959 to 2.5616 with an average of 2.072. For the full model with $M = 1600$, $\hat{p} = 1.9213$, and the grid convergence index is less than 0.05%. Thus, we can say that the solutions obtained using the full model are in the asymptotic range. The factor of safety used to calculate the grid convergence index (5.22) is then 1.25.

6.2.1 Model Order Reduction

Since it is computationally costly to solve the full model for the entire parameter space \mathcal{P} , we have implemented a model order reduction approach. We have obtained the training parameter set to compute the optimal reduced basis by using either the classical greedy sampling or the adaptive greedy sampling.

Classical Greedy Sampling

For the classical greedy sampling, we have used $c = 40$ randomly selected parameter groups to train the algorithm. The allowed maximum iterations $I_{max} = 10$, i.e., at most 10 optimal parameter groups are selected, which maximize the residual error. The algorithm then updates the snapshot matrix and generates a new reduced basis. Figure 6.17 shows the evolution of

Figure 6.17: Evolution of maximum and average residuals with each iteration of the classical greedy algorithm for the steeper instrument.

maximum and average residuals with each iteration of the classical greedy sampling algorithm. It is observed that the residual error decreases with each proceeding iteration. We can truncate the greedy iteration after 4th or 5th iteration as the error dropped below 10^{-4} .

The dimension of the reduced basis d is chosen using Algorithm 10. The projection error ϵ_{POD} is plotted in Fig. 6.18. We observed that the projection error decreases monotonically with increasing d , which is determined in terms of POD eigenvalues. The monotonically

decreasing graph of the projection error shows that we have succeeded in determining an optimal reduced basis, which is later used to generate the reduced model. Figure 6.18 also

Figure 6.18: Steeper instrument: Classical Greedy Sampling: Projection error associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition (left). A plot of the relative error between the full model and the reduced model obtained using the classical greedy sampling approach (right).

shows the reduced model error ϵ_{RM} plotted against the reduced dimension d for the parameter group ρ_{732} . It is observed that the error ϵ_{RM} decreases as the dimension d increases. This shows that the reduced model is an excellent approximation of the full model. We have designed a reduced model of dimension $d = 10$ as the model order reduction error $\epsilon_d = \epsilon_{POD} + \epsilon_{RM} = 4.18 \times 10^{-5} + 1.17 \times 10^{-4} = 1.588 \times 10^{-4}$ is less than the tolerance $e_{tol}^d = 5 \times 10^{-4}$. Finally, we can use this reduced model to solve the remaining scenarios, as in Section 5.5.

In classical greedy sampling, the algorithm is trained on the randomly generated parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ of cardinality 40. We noticed that the random sampling often neglects some of the vital parameter groups within the parameter space. The reduced model designed using the classical

Figure 6.19: Drawback of the classical greedy (CG) sampling approach for the steeper instrument.

greedy sampling approach shows this drawback as illustrated in Fig. 6.19. The figure shows the reduced model error for two different parameter groups $(\rho_{342}, \rho_{5287})$. In both cases, the relative error does not drop below the user-defined tolerance $e_{tol}^d = 5 \times 10^{-4}$, and Algorithm 10 does not converge. This prompted us to implement an adaptive greedy approach that relies on the surrogate model to locate the training parameters.

Adaptive Greedy Sampling

The adaptive greedy process utilizes a surrogate model that is based on the principal component regression technique. The adaptive greedy iteration is initiated by computing the error estimator for randomly selected parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$ of cardinality $c_0 = 10$. At each surrogate model iteration, we have chosen $c_k = 10$ parameter groups. This process repeat itself until we get the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ of cardinality 40.

Figure 6.20: Steeper instrument: Principal component analysis error (left) and predicted values obtained using the surrogate model for an error estimator vs actual values (right).

Table 6.8: Mean squared error of prediction for the steeper instrument

Fold No.	Squared error
$L_K = 1$	8.7790×10^{-5}
$L_K = 2$	7.6331×10^{-5}
$L_K = 3$	7.9755×10^{-5}
$L_K = 4$	8.8776×10^{-5}
MSEP_{K-CV}	8.3163×10^{-5}
$\text{MSEP}_{K-CVadj}$	7.2815×10^{-5}
$\epsilon_{samp} = \text{MSEP}_{K-CVadj} + \epsilon_{PCA}$	2.3750×10^{-4}

Figure 6.20 shows monotonically decreasing singular values of the data matrix $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_k$ composed of c_k parameter groups at k th iteration. We noticed that the first three principal

components comprise almost 99% of energy, and within the first five components, energy level round up to 99.99%. Thus, we constructed a surrogate model with only five principal components. Figure 6.20 also demonstrates that the predicted values obtained using the surrogate model match the actual values within an acceptable range.

The quality of the designed surrogate model is further tested using a mean squared error of prediction. We have used a K -fold cross-validation technique to determine the MSEP as described in Section 5.3. The learning data matrix composed of 40 parameter groups and 40 respective error estimator values at the last iteration is divided into $K = 4$ folds. We obtained the mean square error for each fold and summed them to calculate the MSEP of the cross-validation. Table 6.8 shows the calculations and MSEP for the designed surrogate model. The sampling error ϵ_{smp} is the sum of the adjusted K -fold cross-validation error and the projection error, i.e., $\epsilon_{smp} = \text{MSEP}_{K\text{-CVadj}} + \epsilon_{\text{PCA}} = 2.3750 \times 10^{-4}$. As $\epsilon_{smp} < e_{tol}^{smp} = 5 \times 10^{-4}$, we can say that the designed surrogate model is satisfactory.

We have used this surrogate model to construct the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$. Finally, the optimal parameter group ρ_I is selected from the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ that maximized the residual error. The reduced basis is then obtained by computing the truncated singular value decomposition of the updated snapshot matrix, as shown in Algorithm 1. Figure 6.21 shows the evolution of the maximum and average residual error with each adaptive greedy iteration. It illustrates

Figure 6.21: Evolution of maximum and average residuals with each iteration of the adaptive greedy algorithm for the steeper instrument.

that the residual error decreases with increasing iteration and falls below 10^{-4} after the 4th iteration, which is enough to truncate the greedy process. The decrease of the residual error with each incrementing iteration also shows that the algorithm succeeded in efficiently locating the optimal parameter groups.

The adaptive greedy algorithm then used these efficiently located parameter groups to update the snapshot matrix and obtain the reduced basis. The reduced basis dimension d is

selected such that for the generated reduced model, ϵ_{POD} and ϵ_{RM} are below the user defined tolerance. Figure 6.22 shows the monotonically decreasing projection error ϵ_{POD} associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition. Additionally, the reduced model error ϵ_{RM} plotted

Figure 6.22: Steeper instrument: Adaptive Greedy Sampling: Projection error associated with the proper orthogonal decomposition (left), and a plot of the relative error between the full model and the reduced model obtained using adaptive greedy sampling approach (right).

in Fig. 6.22 indicates that the relative error decreases with increasing reduced dimension d . We have constructed the final reduced model using $d = 10$, as the model order reduction error is less than the user-defined tolerance e_{tol}^d , i.e., $\epsilon_d = \epsilon_{\text{POD}} + \epsilon_{\text{RM}} = 4.042 \times 10^{-6} + 1.882 \times 10^{-4} = 1.922 \times 10^{-4} < 5 \times 10^{-4}$. This means that the reduced model of order $d = 10$ is enough to obtain an excellent approximation of the full model.

Finally, the remaining scenarios are solved using this reduced model, as explained in Section 5.5.

Figure 6.23: Comparison of the classical greedy (CG) approach vs adaptive greedy (AG) approach for the steeper instrument.

We have implemented the adaptive greedy sampling approach to overcome the drawbacks

of the classical greedy sampling method, as evident from Fig. 6.23. The relative error between the full model and the reduced model obtained using the adaptive greedy sampling approach is of order 10^{-4} with the reduced dimension $d = 10$ for both ρ_{342}, ρ_{5287} . The error ϵ_{RM} keeps on decreasing with increasing d , unlike the classical greedy sampling approach. Therefore, the results depict a clear advantage of the developed adaptive greedy approach over the classical greedy approach in the model order reduction framework.

Convergence of the Adaptive Greedy Algorithm

The convergence of the classical greedy sampling approach is monitored using the residual error. However, we have used an error model $\hat{\epsilon}_{\text{RM}}$ designed using the reduced model errors and residual errors to monitor the convergence of the adaptive greedy sampling. Figure 6.24 illustrates the designed error model based on the available error set E_p for four different greedy iterations. The error plot demonstrates a strong correlation between the relative error and the residual error. The goodness of fit test gives $R^2 = 0.9454$. Thus, the results indicate that a consideration of the linear error model is adequate to capture the overall behavior of the exact error as a function of the residual error.

Figure 6.24: The error model $\bar{\epsilon}_{\text{RM}}$ based on the available error set E_p for four different greedy iterations for the steeper instrument.

Random Sampling

We have used random sampling up to a certain extent in both classical and adaptive greedy approaches. Random sampling is used to construct the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ in the classical

Figure 6.25: Effect of random sampling on classical and adaptive greedy sampling for the steeper instrument.

greedy, while in the case of the adaptive greedy, it is used to initiate the algorithm. In both cases, the random sampling somewhat affects the results. Figure 6.25 shows the maximum residual error plot with each proceeding iteration of the greedy algorithms with error bars. These results are obtained by performing classical and adaptive procedures for 30 different sets of random numbers. It is observed that the adaptive greedy approach is less sensitive to random sampling than its counterpart. On average, the adaptive greedy approach yields a better reduced model as its residual errors are lesser than the classical approach.

Computational Cost

Three major error contributors that lead to the total error are the discretization error, the model order reduction error, and the sampling error. Figure 6.26 presents the model hierarchy along with the error associated with each stage. The total error is a sum of all significant errors and is given by (5.4)

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_T &\approx \epsilon_h + \epsilon_{RM} + \epsilon_{POD} + \epsilon_{\text{samp}}, \\ \epsilon_T &= 2.182 \times 10^{-4} + 1.882 \times 10^{-4} + 4.042 \times 10^{-6} + 2.3750 \times 10^{-4} = 6.479 \times 10^{-4}. \end{aligned}$$

As the $\epsilon_T < 10^{-3}$, it fulfills the stopping criteria prescribed in remark 5.5.1. Thus, we can say that only $\ell = 10$ full model valuations are enough to obtain the fairly accurate reduced model, and the remaining scenarios (parameter groups) can be solved using the generated reduced model.

The computational time calculation is a crucial aspect enlightening the importance of the model order reduction over the full model approach. The total computational time T_Q^{CG} required to obtain the reduced basis after i iterations of the classical greedy sampling approach

Figure 6.26: A model hierarchy showing errors arising in the analysis of the mathematical model for the steepener instrument.

is given as, (4.8),

$$T_Q^{\text{CG}} \approx \left[c \times t_{\text{RM}} + (t_{\text{FM}} + t_{\text{SVD}}) \right] \times i.$$

On the other hand, the total computational time T_Q^{AG} for the adaptive greedy sampling is given as, (4.12),

$$T_Q^{\text{AG}} \approx \left[c_0 \times t_{\text{RM}} + k(c_k \times t_{\text{RM}} + t_{\text{SM}} + t_{\text{SM}}^{\text{ev}}) + t_{\text{FM}} + t_{\text{SVD}} + 2t_{\text{RM}}^{\text{aft,bef}} + t_{\text{EM}} \right] \times i.$$

Table 6.9: Computing time/ reduction time (T_Q) to generate a reduced basis for the steepener instrument.

Algorithm	Cardinality $ \hat{\mathcal{P}} $	I_{max}	Computing time
Classical greedy sampling	20	10	106.81 s
Classical greedy sampling	30	10	156.24 s
Classical greedy sampling	40	10	278.46 s
Adaptive greedy sampling	40	10	387.63 s

Table 6.9 shows the computational time required to obtain the reduced basis for both

Table 6.10: Evaluation time for the steepener instrument.

Algorithm	Model	Eva. time single ρ_s	Total Eva. time (T_{eva})	Total time $T_Q + T_{\text{eva}}$
	FM, $M = 1600$	1.9136 s	19316.5 s	19316.5 s
Classical greedy sampling	RM, $d = 5$	0.198 s	1975.31 s	2253.7 s
Classical greedy sampling	RM, $d = 10$	0.268 s	2681.45 s	2959.9 s
Adaptive greedy sampling	RM, $d = 5$	0.214 s	2143.47 s	2531.1 s
Adaptive greedy sampling	RM, $d = 10$	0.263 s	2671.30 s	3058.9 s

classical and adaptive greedy sampling. The adaptive sampling time is slightly higher than its counterpart due to the time required to build and solve the surrogate model. Despite the fact that classical greedy sampling is almost two times faster than adaptive greedy sampling, its drawbacks provoke us to use adaptive greedy sampling.

We noticed that the evaluation of the reduced model is at least 8 – 10 times faster than the full model. However, there is a slight increase in the total time due to the additional reduction time. Table 6.10 also infers that the evaluation time increases with the increasing reduced dimension d . The reduced model obtained based on the classical greedy sampling approach is at least 7 – 9 times faster than the full model. While the reduced model obtained using the adaptive greedy sampling approach is 6 – 8 times faster than the full model. The computational time presented in the table considers that the greedy algorithms run for the maximum number of iterations I_{max} . However, in practice, we can truncate the algorithms after 4th or 5th iteration and achieve even more speedup.

Table 6.11: Computational time comparison: SVD vs Randomized SVD for the steepener instrument.

	SVD	RandSVD	Speedup factor
Computational time t_{SVD}	8.756 s	0.7102 s	≈ 12.5

We have used a truncated singular value decomposition based on randomized algorithms to obtain a reduced basis. Table 6.11 shows the computational time comparison between the RandSVD and the basic SVD. For our problem of the steepener instrument, the randomized SVD is at least 12 times faster than the basic SVD.

6.2.2 Steeper Performance Scenario Values

We have solved the steeper instrument with the reduced model obtained using the adaptive greedy approach for 10 000 different parameter groups. To design a key information document, we need the values of the steeper at different spot rates. The spot rate is nothing but the yield rate at the first tenor point from the simulated yield curve. For 10 000 simulated yield curves, we procured 10 000 different spot rates and the corresponding values for the instrument. The regulations also demand to find a VaR equivalent volatility to determine

Table 6.12: Results for the puttable steeper.

Performance Scenario	5 years		10 years	
Model	RM	UnRisk	RM	UnRisk
Favorable (90th percentile)	0.983	0.972	1.001	0.994
Moderate (50th percentile)	0.931	0.926	0.940	0.934
Unfavorable (10th percentile)	0.907	0.904	0.912	0.919

a market risk indicator at the recommended holding period. For the steeper instrument, the calculated VEV is 1.3285% which gives the market risk indicator as 2. It is required to include three different performance scenarios in the KID: (i) favorable scenario, (ii) moderate scenario, (iii) unfavorable scenario, which are the values at 90th percentile, 50th percentile, 10th percentile of 10 000 values, respectively. The steeper performance scenarios obtained using the reduced model and the commercially available software UnRisk for the comparison are presented in the table 6.12 after five and ten years. Figure 6.27 shows the distribution of fair values of the instrument, plus the coupons in the respective path obtained so far after five years and ten years in the future. The histogram gives an idea about the frequency distribution and shape of a set of 10000 values for the PRIIP.

Figure 6.27: Distribution of 10 000 results for the steeper instrument after five years (left) and ten years (right).

6.3 Sensitivity Analysis

The sensitivity analysis of the numerical errors is performed to understand their contribution to the final output. It also helped to locate the computational resources efficiently throughout the study. We have obtained 30 different data points for each numerical error to generate respective distributions by varying certain key parameters. We have sampled 30 different grid sizes to compute the discretization error distribution, where the full model dimension is being varied from 100 to 2500. To compute the sampling error distribution, we have randomly generated 15 different $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$ by keeping the cardinality of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ as $|\hat{\mathcal{P}}| = 50$. Additionally, 15 data points for the sampling error are calculated by varying $|\hat{\mathcal{P}}|$ between 30 to 100 while keeping $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$ fixed using a particular seed number. The distributions for the projection error and the reduced model error are obtained by varying the reduced dimension between 5 and 60.

Sensitivity analysis results for the floater and steeper instruments are presented in Tab. 6.13 and Table 6.14, respectively.

Table 6.13: Sensitivity analysis: local and global sensitivity indices (Floater instrument).

Numerical Error	Local Index	Rank	Global Index	Rank
Discretization error ϵ_h	0.5345	1	0.4185	2
Reduced model error ϵ_{RM}	0.1034	3	0.1195	3
Projection error ϵ_{POD}	0.0167	4	0.0081	4
Sampling error ϵ_{samp}	0.3621	2	0.6178	1

Table 6.14: Sensitivity analysis: local and global sensitivity indices (Steeper instrument).

Numerical Error	Local Index	Rank	Global Index	Rank
Discretization error ϵ_h	0.3351	1	0.4172	2
Reduced model error ϵ_{RM}	0.1450	3	0.0917	3
Projection error ϵ_{POD}	0.0167	4	0.0081	4
Sampling error ϵ_{samp}	0.2247	2	0.5397	1

The local indices show that the final output is most sensitive to the discretization error followed by the sampling error, while it is least sensitive to the reduced model error and the projection error, respectively. We can mitigate the discretization error by increasing the full model dimension. Nevertheless, sensitivity indices prevail that the change in grid size considerably affects the final output. We overcome this problem by increasing the full model dimension until the further change in grid sizes does affect the solutions significantly. We have constructed the full model of order $M = 800$, for the floater example, and of order $M = 1600$,

for the steeper example, where the discretization error is of order 10^{-4} .

The global sensitivity analysis shows that the sampling error is the most sensitive numerical error. The major input factors contributing to the sampling error are the randomly sampled parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$ and the cardinality of set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$. As it is not feasible to select the entire parameter space as the parameter set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$, the surrogate model only locates a certain number of parameter groups to construct $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ and neglects the rest. This neglect of the parameter groups contributes to the sampling error together with the random sampling of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}_0$ used to initiate the surrogate model loop, as we have already demonstrated in Fig. 6.12 and 6.25. This random sampling contributes to the uncertainty and makes the sampling error more sensitive. To overcome this problem, we suggest increasing the cardinality of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ used to locate the most optimal parameter group if necessary. We have kept the cardinality of $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ as 40, as the sampling error is of order 10^{-4} .

Although increasing the cardinality of the set $\hat{\mathcal{P}}$ will increase the computational burden, it generates the optimal reduced basis that allows constructing a fairly low dimensional reduced model. This compensates for the extra computational burden necessary during the adaptive sampling. We noticed that the projection error is the least sensitive to the final output considering both local (individual contribution) and global (interactions) indices. This tells us that the singular value decay of the snapshot matrix is elegant to obtain the desired reduced basis.

Chapter 7

Conclusion and Outlook

The financial risk analysis requires solving the underlying instrument under several thousand market scenarios using some appropriate valuation functions, which demands efficient algorithms. Therefore, this work presented a parametric model order reduction approach for discretized convection-diffusion-reaction PDEs that arise in the analysis of financial risk. The parameter space with time-dependent parameters is obtained by calibrating the financial models based on a market structure called the yield curve. We have presented a detailed method for generating simulated yield curves based on the collected historical data and the calibration of model parameters based on simulated yield curves. Two prominent financial models are used as valuation functions, namely the one-factor Hull-White model and the two-factor Hull-White model. The one-factor model is discretized using the finite difference method, while the finite element method is used to discretize the two-factor model.

The main challenge of the parametric MOR is to identify the training parameter groups to obtain the best-suitable reduced basis, generating the most accurate reduced model. Thus, we have established greedy sampling approaches for parameter sampling. We have demonstrated the benefits of the residual error as an error estimator instead of the computationally costly relative error between the full and reduced model. We noticed that there are some parameter groups for which the classical greedy sampling gave unsatisfactory results. To overcome this problem, we have applied the adaptive greedy sampling method that utilizes an optimized search based on surrogate modeling to locate suitable parameter groups efficiently. The surrogate model is built using the principal component regression technique, which performed adequately, as confirmed by the cross-validation studies. This work also explains that the developed MOR approach can be pursued as a black-box model, where a user only has to input the historical interest rate data and the underlying instrument in order to obtain the performance scenario values.

The thesis also presented a detailed error analysis of the developed model order reduction framework. Three major sources of errors considered are the discretization error, the sampling error, and the model order reduction error. We have developed error estimations

and their quantification methods for each numerical error. Based on these error estimators, we have designed algorithms to select optimal grid size, suitable training parameters, and the appropriate reduced dimension. Again, the algorithms are designed such that the model order reduction framework can be used as a black box for which the user only requires to provide inputs and get the desired output.

Another major contribution of this thesis is the implementation of sensitivity analysis to rank the contribution of each numerical error. We have developed a methodology to address both deterministic (e.g., discretization error) and stochastic (sampling error) errors. Sobol’s variance-based sensitivity analysis is used, which computes local as well as global indices. The global sensitivity analysis revealed that the sampling error is most sensitive to the final output. Such information advised us to allocate more computational resources to the sampling algorithm that ultimately generated the suitable reduced basis as demonstrated by the obtained results.

We have tested the designed algorithms for numerical examples of a floater with caps and floors and a puttable steepener under the one-factor and two-factor Hull-White models, respectively. The results indicated the computational advantages of the parametric model reduction technique for the short-rate models. The reduced model is obtained such that the total error is less than the user-defined tolerance. Therefore, we can say that the developed reduced model is satisfactory. As $\epsilon_T < e_{tol}$, we can conclude that the full model valuations for the adaptively selected $\ell = 10$ parameter groups are enough, and the rest of the parameter groups can be solved inexpensively using the reduced model of dimension $d = 10$. The reduced model approach to solve the entire parameter space was at least 8 – 10 times faster than the full model approach. We also noticed that the randomized singular value decomposition provides an excellent speedup compared to the basic singular value decomposition.

7.1 Outlook

The developed algorithms have been tested for two prominent examples with two different short-rate models. In the future, more complicated financial instruments could be tested to review and improve the quality of the developed framework further.

Process automation and designing a black-box model were some of the objectives of this thesis. Many practitioners and researchers from financial industries see the future of quantitative finance by shifting away from classical models towards more network-based and data-driven techniques. In recent years, machine learning is gaining popularity for solving high dimensional computationally costly problems in mathematical finance. Thus, as an extended work of the thesis, the neural network model is considered for financial risk analysis. Instead of running costly numerical simulations, we may construct a neural network model for the relation between the market scenarios and the instrument values. We can generate the

training data by solving the financial instrument using an appropriate valuation function for some market scenarios. The trained neural network can then be used to solve the financial instrument for the remaining scenarios. Since we have to perform only a limited number of full valuations and the rest of the valuations are based on the trained neural network, we can achieve our necessary speedup. Our approach will comprise offline and online computational phases constructed to address the information flow. During the offline phase, we will perform full valuations to construct a training dataset, and then the model will be trained based on this dataset, while during the online phase, the trained surrogate model can be employed to estimate the financial instrument values directly.

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Appendix A

List of Essential Terms

This list of terms specifies essential financial terms used throughout the thesis. The terms are highlighted in italics when they are introduced first.

arbitrage Arbitrage is the simultaneous purchase and sale of an instrument to benefit from an imbalance in the price. 17

bank account A bank account is an interest-bearing account at a bank to earn interest on the invested amount. 13

bond A bond is a loan to a borrower made by a bondholder. The borrower (company, government, municipality) pays the loan principal of the bond to the bondholder on a maturity date as well as an interest for the life of the bond. 8

callable A callable instrument is an instrument with an embedded call option. A call option is an option that gives the right to the investor, but not the obligation, to buy one share of the equity at some future time T for a fixed price called the strike price K . 6

cap An upper limit on the interest rate for a floating interest rate instrument. 6

constant maturity swap A constant maturity swap (CMS) rate for a given tenor is referenced as a point on the Swap curve. A swap curve is a term structure that plots the par swap rates at every tenor point, where a swap rate is the fixed rate that the swap receiver demands in exchange for the uncertainty of having to pay a floating rate like LIBOR. 106

DAX Deutscher Aktienindex (German stock index). 9

Euribor The Euro Interbank Offered Rate (EURIBOR) is a benchmark interest rate. 91

floater A floater is an instrument that has a variable coupon depending on some reference interest rate like Libor. 6

floor An lower limit on the interest rate for a floating interest rate instrument. 6

forward rate A forward rate is an interest rate applicable to the financial transaction that will take place in the future. 26

future A futures contract, sometimes called futures, is a standardized legal contract between two parties to buy or sell something at a predetermined price at a specified time in the future. 9

libor The London Interbank Offered Rate (LIBOR) is a benchmark interest rate. 9

noncentral chi-squared distribution Let (X_1, \dots, X_n) be n independent, normally distributed random variables with means $\mu_{i=1}^n$ and unit variances. Then the random variable

$$\sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2$$

is distributed according to the noncentral chi-squared distribution. . 16

option An option is a right, but not an obligation, to purchase or sell the underlying instrument at some time at a pre-defined price. 9

Ornstein–Uhlenbeck process The Ornstein–Uhlenbeck process X_t is defined by the following stochastic differential equation

$$dX_t = -aX_t dt + b dW_t$$

where $a, b > 0$ are parameters and W_t denotes the Wiener/brownian process. . 15

portfolio In finance, a portfolio is a collection of investments held by an investment company, a hedge fund, a financial institution or an individual. 2

puttable A puttable instrument is an instrument with an enclosed put option. A put option is an option that gives the right to the investor, but not the obligation, to sell one share of the equity at some future time T for a fixed price called the strike price K . 6

recommended holding period The recommended holding period gives an idea to an investor that for how long should an investor hold the product to minimize the risk.

3

risk-neutral Risk neutral term describes the investment which is insensitive to risk. 17

S&P500 500 of the largest companies listed on stock exchanges in the United States. 9

short-rate Short rate is the rate at which bank account grows. 13

steepener A steepener is an instrument whose coupons depend on the difference between two interest rates. 6

swap a. Swap: A swap is an agreement between two parties to exchange financial instruments for a certain time.

b. Swaption: A swaption is an option to enter into a swap. 8

volatilities Volatility is a measure of the rate of fluctuations in the price of an underlying instrument over time. Mathematically, volatility is defined as the standard deviation of a sequence of random variables.. 17

yield curve The yield curve is the curve showing interest rates plotted against different maturities for the same financial instrument. 3

zero-coupon bond A bond which does not pay interest and offers full face value profits at maturity. 24